

CL-Windcon

Closed Loop Wind Farm Control

DELIVERABLE REPORT

D1.2: Description of the reference and the control-oriented wind farm models

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

More and more wind turbines are being placed together in wind farms to reduce the price of wind energy. Though, challenges arise due to the formation of wakes, which are slower, more turbulent regions of air flow, formed downwind of turbines due to the extraction of energy. These wakes lead to reduced power capture and the higher structural degradation of downwind turbines compared to turbines placed in freestream wind conditions. Wind farm control aims to mitigate wake losses by intelligently steering the flow, improving the total farm's power quality and turbine lifetimes.

Several methods for wind farm control have been proposed in the literature. One such method, so-called "wake steering", has shown potential in high-fidelity simulations, wind tunnel experiments and preliminary field experiments. In this control methodology, wakes are steered away from downstream turbines by purposely misaligning upstream turbines with the incoming wind. This control framework demands a reliable model, which can only be achieved through real-time calibration using measurements in the field; the so-called "closed-loop control" paradigm. This concept of closed-loop wind farm control is the topic of the European CL-Windcon project, which is receiving funding under the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727477.

A key topic of the European CL-Windcon project, and specifically workpackage 1 of this project, is the accurate modelling of wind turbine and wind farm dynamics at a varying range of fidelities. In this project, we arrange the model fidelities under four categories: steady-state models, control-oriented dynamical models, medium-fidelity simulation models, and high-fidelity simulation models.

Steady-state models are used for their low complexity and computational cost, predicting the time-averaged properties of the wind farm dynamics. Specifically, the steady-state FLORIS model was described in Chapter 6. While this model shows good agreement with high-fidelity data, it comes with relatively many tuning parameters, and its steady-state nature makes it only useful for wind farm control on a minutes-scale.

Control-oriented dynamical models capture the dominant flow and turbine dynamics on a second-to-second scale, but therefore go paired with a noticeably higher computational cost and complexity. These models are often derived from the physical Navier-Stokes equations, leading to fewer tuning parameters than the steady-state models such as FLORIS. Control-oriented dynamical models described were LongSim (Chapter 8), WindFarmSimulator (Chapter 9), and a reduced-order model derived from high-fidelity simulation data (Chapter 11). FarmFlow (Chapter 4) and a wake dissipation model for wake tracking (Chapter 10) are in between steady-state and a control-oriented dynamical models. These models are expected to capture the wind farm dynamics at a greater degree than the simplified steady-state models.

Medium-fidelity simulation models are not used for controller synthesis due to their computational cost and complexity. However, these models are noticeably cheaper computationally than high-fidelity large-eddy simulations, and permit a reasonable modelling accuracy for controller testing. Simulations using these models can typically be run on single desktop computers or on small clusters. Two of such models were described in this report, namely FAST.Farm (Chapter 5), and SimWindFarm (Chapter 7). These models will assist in the testing of the synthesized wind farm control solutions throughout the CL-Windcon project at a relatively low computational cost and complexity.

High-fidelity simulation models are typically large-eddy simulations with a high spatial and temporal resolution, to resolve the different scales of turbulent structures in the flow and turbine dynamics. These models go paired with a very high computational cost, and therefore typically require high performance computing clusters to perform simulations within a reasonable time. These models are exclusively used for controller testing and wind analysis. The high-fidelity simulation model used in this project is SOWFA, described in Chapter 3. Simulations in SOWFA were setup for the CL-Windcon project, specifically for certain atmospheric conditions and for the Innwind 10MW wind turbine. SOWFA will play a crucial role in the remainder of this project as both a simulation model for the generation of data used for the fitting of lower-fidelity models, and as a simulation model for the testing and validation of wind farm control solutions at a higher fidelity.

In the remainder of this project, the steady-state and control-oriented models will be used for controller synthesis. The medium-fidelity and high-fidelity simulation models will aid the controller synthesis by providing a testing platform, and a platform for the generation of high-fidelity simulation datasets to which the simplified models can be tuned. The high-fidelity simulation models may also help fill in the data gaps when we move towards the testing of the wind farm control solutions on experimental setups. Namely, in work package 3 (WP3), the advanced wind farm control algorithms will be tested in the wind tunnel at Politecnico di Milano on a scaled-down setup, and also on a subset of turbines inside the Sedini wind farm in Italy, owned by ENEL Green Power.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 The current challenge in wind farms

More and more wind turbines are being placed together in wind farms to reduce the price of wind energy. Specifically, placing turbines close to one another results in reduced deployment costs of the electricity grid, reduced land- or sea-use and visual pollution, and increased power capture per unit area at resource-rich locations/topologies. Though, challenges arise due to the formation of wakes. Wakes are slower, more turbulent regions of air flow, formed downwind of turbines due to the extraction of energy. The Lillgrund offshore wind farm shows losses in power capture of up to 23% compared to individually placed turbines, suppressing potential cost reductions in wind farms. Furthermore, the increase in turbulent structures may lead to higher structural degradation of the downwind turbines. Wind farm control aims to mitigate wake losses by intelligently steering the flow, improving the total farm’s power quality and turbine lifetimes.

The current practice in wind farms is to steer each turbine straight into the wind for maximum power capture (“greedy”), ignoring wake effects. However, high-fidelity simulations, wind tunnel experiments and preliminary field experiments show the potential of steering a wake away from downstream turbines by purposely misaligning upstream turbines with the incoming wind. To determine the optimal operation settings of each turbine in real-time, an accurate and computationally tractable surrogate model is necessary that predicts the turbine and flow dynamics inside the farm. However, due to lack of knowledge about the environment and the complex dynamics of wind at a multitude of temporal and spatial scales, no such model exists. Therefore, this demands a closed-loop framework, in which a surrogate model is calibrated in real-time using measurements. The framework is shown below.

This concept of closed-loop wind farm control is the topic of the European CL-Windcon project, which is receiving funding under the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727477.

This deliverable addresses the mathematical models of the wind farm that will be used within this project. This deliverable will address both the lower-fidelity models to be used for controller synthesis, as well as models that will function as higher-fidelity simulation models, useful for the testing and validation of the control solutions. The next section will zoom in on the various levels of fidelity in wind farm modeling.

While model-free methods exist for wind farm control, these methods suffer from slow convergence rates, and their applicability in annual wind farm operation remains questionable. Therefore, the scope of this project is limited to model-based control methods.

2.2 Wind farm control-oriented modelling

A key topic of the European Closed-Loop Wind Farm Control (CL-Windcon) project is the accurate modelling of wind turbine and wind farm dynamics at a varying range of fidelities. In this project, we arrange the model fidelities under four categories: steady-state models, control-oriented dynamical models, medium-fidelity simulation models, and high-fidelity simulation models, as shown below.

Not always a clear distinction can be made, but generally, models can be subdivided into these classes. Each level of model fidelity is described next.

Steady-state models

The steady-state wind farm models predict the time-averaged properties of the wind farm, neglecting any temporal dynamics such as wake delays. This usually means that these models only capture the 5- or 10-minute average quantities of the flow and turbine dynamics. Thus, their accuracy remains limited. However, their computational cost and complexity is very low, and thus these models are excellent candidates for real-time control on a timescale in the order of minutes. Popular steady-state models include Jensen, FLORIS, and Ainslie. The FLORIS model will be described in Chapter 6.

Control-oriented dynamical models

The second category of wind farm models are the control-oriented dynamical models. These models capture the dominant flow and turbine dynamics on a second-to-second scale. While these models are computationally significantly more expensive than the steady-state models, their accuracy is much higher, and they allow control on a second-to-second scale. These models are often derived from the physical Navier-Stokes equations, often leading to much fewer tuning parameters than analytical steady-state models such as FLORIS. Control-oriented dynamical models include LongSim (Chapter 8), WindFarmSimulator (Chapter 9), and a reduced-order model derived from high-fidelity simulation data (Chapter 11). FarmFlow (Chapter 4) and a wake dissipation model for wake tracking (Chapter 10) are in between steady-state and a control-oriented dynamical models.

Medium-fidelity simulation models

These class of models are not used for controller synthesis due to their computational cost and complexity. However, these models are significantly less costly than full high-fidelity large-eddy simulations, and still permit a reasonable modelling accuracy for controller testing. These simulations can typically be run on single desktop computers or on small clusters. Two of such models are described here, namely FAST.Farm (Chapter 5), and SimWindFarm (Chapter 7).

High-fidelity simulation models

Finally, on the highest level of computational cost are the high-fidelity simulation models. These are typically large-eddy simulations with a high spatial and temporal resolution, to resolve the different scales of turbulent structures in the flow and turbine dynamics. These models go paired with a very high computational cost, and therefore typically require high performance computing clusters to perform simulations within a reasonable time. These models are exclusively used for controller testing and wind analysis. The high-fidelity simulation model used in this project is SOWFA, described in Chapter 3.

2.3 Structure of the report

In this report, the various models will be described, one per chapter. For clarity, each chapter includes a list of references and its own choice of symbol notation. The report will be concluded in Chapter 12. Additionally, the connection to the rest of the EU project will be described too.

3 SIMULATOR FOR WIND FARM APPLICATIONS (SOWFA)

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ABL	Atmospheric boundary layer
ACL	Actuator line
BC	Boundary condition
CENER	National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain)
FAST	Fatigue, Aerodynamics, Structures and Turbulence (NREL)
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
HH	Hub Height [m]
OF	OpenFOAM
OpenFAST	The supported version of FAST
Polimi	Politecnico di Milano (Italy)
SOWFA	Simulation for Onshore/Offshore Wind Farm Applications (NREL)
TU Delft	Technical University of Delft (The Netherlands)
USTTUT	University of Stuttgart (Germany)
WF	Wind farm
WT	Wind turbine

3.1 SOWFA model description

3.1.1 Description summary

In this section, guidelines and descriptions of the simulation environment for the reference wind farms (WF) using the SOWFA (OF2.4.x+FASTv8.16 or OpenFAST v1.0.0) coupled code are provided. SOWFA is a high-fidelity numerical simulation tool for wind farms developed at NREL (U.S.A.). It could be used for model validations, controller validations, analysis and research of flows inside wind farms, evaluation of wind turbines of the wind farms, and for wind farm designs. The purpose of high-fidelity simulation is to present reference data to assess engineering tools within the project. Five WFs are defined in D1.1 [1] (a virtual 3-turbine wind farm, a virtual 9-turbine wind farm, a virtual 82-turbine offshore wind farm, a scaled-down wind farm for wind tunnel experiments, and a full-scale wind farm derived from a real scenario, the Sedin wind farm in Italy), and their simulation environments are described. These include general parameters used and guidelines for simulation.

The simulation environments are uploaded in the CL-Windcon project site, [CL-WINDCON > PROJECT](#)

[EXECUTION > WP1 > TECHNICAL INFORMATION > SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT](#). These files do not contain explicitly the mesh, initial condition and inflow boundary data due to large size of the files. However, there are available the commands and the files necessary to generate the meshes. In the near future, the complete set of data will be available on the web in this guide, directory names are depicted with ***italic bold*** font, and file names are depicted with *italic* font. Parameter names are written in Times New Roman font. Repeating number and string are labelled with <#> and <*> respectively.

3.1.2 Model purpose

SOWFA resolves time-dependant turbulence in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and its interaction with wind turbines (WTs). Two modelling strategies for the ABL and WTs are shortly described as well as coupling method between them, see [2] for more details.

The ABL is simulated by OpenFOAM (OF) and it is driven by pressure gradients. The pressure gradient is determined by the momentum balance, which forces wind at a specific height to meet the target value. To achieve a fully developed ABL, a precursor simulation of the topology excluding wind turbines is adopted, in which periodic boundary conditions (BCs) are used at in-outlet boundaries. Once the ABL is developed, wind data are saved in every time and they serve as the inflow BCs for wind farm simulations. To resolve most of turbulence, a large-eddy simulation (LES) turbulence model is used, and one equation eddy viscosity model [3] is adopted for sub-filter scale model as suggested by NREL. A second-order central difference scheme is mostly used for the convection term, but a blending between a first- and second-order scheme is used when mesh refinements are needed.

For WTs, aerodynamic forces and structural dynamics are calculated by OpenFAST. The calculated wind from OF provides inflow velocity seen by blade section, and the corresponding force vector on each blade section is calculated using blade element momentum (BEM) theory. For this, pre-defined aerodynamic data (lift and drag curves) are needed, see [4] for more details. OpenFAST can consider structural response, and also a variety of different WT control methods. To project the calculated aerodynamic forces back to the ABL, an actuator line (ACL) method could be used. It is represented as a body force term in the governing equations for OF with a Gaussian distribution on the blade region to avoid numerical oscillations. A smearing factor (ϵ) manages this distribution and it has to be properly set up to correctly reproduce the aerodynamic forces along the blades. A rule of thumb value for a constant ϵ was suggested by NREL, $\epsilon=0.035*D$.

Specific model parameters for reference wind farm cases can be found in the setup files and their structures are described in the next section.

3.1.3 Model specifications

Based on what has been requested in the 16th PRACE Project Access Call, it can be said that the configurations shown in the table should take less than:

Table 3.1: Computational cost of the SOWFA simulation model

	Total computational time [kh of CPU]	Mesh size [million cells]
Generate a precursor	430	9
Single WT case	364	15
3by1 WT case	569	40
3by3 WT case	1638	110

Mention, as well, that a typical run will require about 500Gb of disk space and will generate around 200.000 files.

3.2 Installation and usage

3.2.1 System requirements

In order to run reference wind farms, users must obtain and compile:

- OpenFOAM-2.4.x (updated on Oct 22, 2015): <https://github.com/OpenFOAM/OpenFOAM-2.4.x.git>
- SOWFA (updated on Apr 5, 2018): <https://github.com/NREL/SOWFA.git>
- FAST v8.16 (updated on Mar 14 2017) : <https://github.com/gantech/fastv8DriverProgram.git>
- OpenFAST v1.0.0 (updated on Apr 6, 2018) : <https://github.com/OpenFAST/openfast>
- SOWFA and OpenFAST are updated when bugs are detected and corrected and new capabilities are added. Therefore, the suggestion is to use the latest version available on the official repositories on github.

Minimum suggested System requirements:

- Linux OS: Ubuntu 14.04 LTS
- At least an 8 cores processor
- 15Gb of free space
- High RAM memory, at least 16Gb

3.2.2 Installation instructions

Software Requirements

To be able to run SOWFA, its three main components must be compiled: **OpenFAST**, **OpenFOAM 2.4.x**, and **SOWFA** itself.

The initial step is to ensure that the machine that will compile all the software has the proper tools and extra software to do so. The following compilers are needed:

- The GNU Compiler Collection (OpenFOAM)
- The Intel Compiler suite is highly recommended (OpenFAST – written partially in Fortran)

A bunch of extra tools and libraries are also required:

- flex
- bison
- make
- cmake
- git
- An MPI library like OpenMPI, MPICH or IntelMPI, and its development package (DP)
- A recent version of Boost Libraries and its DP
- Zlib and its DP
- libreadline and its DP
- libgmp and its DP
- libmpfr and its DP
- libcurl and its DP
- libxml2 and its DP
- libCGAL and its DP
- HDF5 and its DP
- Python and its DP
- Yaml-cpp
- A BLAS/LAPACK library. Intel MKL is recommended here but libOpenBLAS can be used too

Normally all those packages can be directly downloaded from the repositories of the Linux distribution, so there is no need to download and compile them.

Note: It's not practical to cover all the combinations of OS, package versions and environments, so this document assumes that the machine used to compile the code, runs an Ubuntu 16.04.3 LTS, with

OpenMPI as MPI library. If another OS, or another environment (like Environment Modules) is used, the commands must be adapted to the specific requirements.

On an Ubuntu 16.04.3 LTS machine, all those packages can be installed typing:

```
$ sudo apt install build-essential flex bison gfortran git cmake python
python-dev \
    zlib1g-dev libreadline-dev libncurses-dev libyaml-cpp-dev libgmp-dev
libmpfr-dev \
    libboost-system-dev libboost-thread-dev libopenmpi-dev openmpi-bin \
    libhdf5-dev libxml2-dev
```

OpenFAST compilation

OpenFAST code is basically FORTRAN (2003 standard) with some parts in C++ (2011 standard) code, so a recent C++ and FORTRAN compiler are needed. Few tests were performed at CENER and it was concluded by the *Technical Computing and Software Development Service of CENER* that the best performance was achieved using a recent version of the Intel Composer Compiler Suite.

First, download the OpenFAST code:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/OpenFAST/OpenFAST.git
```

Go to the OpenFAST directory, and create a *build* folder:

```
$ cd OpenFAST
$ mkdir build
$ cd build
```

Then, the location of the libraries and headers of the different libraries needed by OpenFAST (libhdf5, yaml-cpp) has to be declared.

For the HDF5 library, as is indicated previously in [Requirements](#), the *serial* version that comes with Ubuntu 16.04.3 LTS was used. Once installed, the libraries and development headers can be located in `/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/hdf5/serial`.

The Yaml-cpp library was also installed through the package manager, and the root location of the libraries and headers is, therefore, `/usr/`.

Then, location of all those paths through these four environment variables is declared:

```
$ export HDF5_ROOT="/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/hdf5/serial"
$ export YAML_ROOT="/usr/"
```

Afterwards, launch the `cmake` configuration tool with a bunch of flags, depending on user preferences for the compilers, the Blas/Lapack libraries and the installation directory.

Then, the compiler must be chosen. For this, `cmake` has three flags: `CMAKE_C_COMPILER`, `CMAKE_CXX_COMPILER` and `CMAKE_Fortran_COMPILER`. Since OpenFAST is mainly Fortran code, `gcc/g++/gfortran` could be used. However, the Fortran Intel Compiler is highly recommended.

Next step is to set the BLAS/LAPACK libraries to be used by OpenFAST. CENER recommendation is to use the Intel MKL libraries that can be downloaded for free from Intel. By default, cmake will use the default implementation of BLAS installed in the system, that is, OpenBLAS. For the MKL to be used, the `BLA_VENDOR` flag with the proper value, in this case: `Intel10_64lp_seq` must be added.

Finally, the `cmake` command can be launched. As can be seen in the example below, with the first three arguments the compilers for C, C++ and Fortran, that the user wanted to use, are declared. If different compilers are wanted, then the user should change these three lines accordingly. The next argument tells `cmake` to use the 64 bits sequential implementation of MKL. The `DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX` argument controls the destination path of the OpenFAST compilation. There, the path to folder where the user wants to install OpenFAST needs to be included.

The last three arguments are needed in order to couple OpenFAST with OpenFOAM.

```
$ cmake \  
  -DCMAKE_C_COMPILER=icc \  
  -DCMAKE_CXX_COMPILER=icpc \  
  -DCMAKE_Fortran_COMPILER=ifort \  
  -DBLA_VENDOR=Intel10_64lp_seq \  
  -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX="/path/to/wherever/you/want/to/install/OpenFAST"  
 \  
  -DCMAKE_CXX_FLAGS="-std=c++11" \  
  -DBUILD_FAST_CPP_API:BOOL=ON \  
  -DBUILD_SHARED_LIBS:BOOL=ON \  
  ../
```

Once the project is successfully configured, run the usual `make` and `make install`

```
$ make  
$ make install
```

OpenFOAM 2.4.x compilation

First, the OpenFOAM installation folder must be created. It could be located at `${HOME}/OpenFOAM`:

```
# Create the OpenFOAM install folder  
$ cd ${HOME}  
$ mkdir -p OpenFOAM  
$ cd OpenFOAM
```

Now, *inside* the OpenFOAM install folder, download OpenFOAM 2.4.x code, and the ThirdParty package:

```
# Download the OpenFOAM source code  
$ git clone https://github.com/OpenFOAM/OpenFOAM-2.4.x.git  
$ git clone https://github.com/OpenFOAM/ThirdParty-2.4.x.git
```

By default, OpenFOAM assumes that the installation path is going to be `${HOME}/OpenFOAM/`. If the user wants the installation folder in a different location, the file `OpenFOAM-2.4.x/etc/bashrc` must be edited, changing the variable `foamInstall` so that it points to the required location.

The next step is optional: since at CENER is preferred to use CGAL 4.7 that comes with Ubuntu instead of compiling the older version that comes in the `ThirdParty` package, the OpenFOAM is going to be configured accordingly by running:

```
$ sed -i -e 's/^\(cgal_version=\).*\/\1cgal-system/' OpenFOAM-  
2.4.x/etc/config/CGAL.sh
```

Now, prior to build OpenFOAM, few fixes are needed. OpenFOAM 2.4.x does not properly detect modern versions of Flex, so some files have to be edited:

```
$ source ${HOME}/OpenFOAM/OpenFOAM-2.4.x/etc/bashrc  
$ cd ${WM_PROJECT_DIR}  
$ find src applications -name "*.L" -type f | xargs \  
    sed -i -e 's=\(YY\FLEX\_SUBMINOR\_VERSION\) =YY_FLEX_MINOR_VERSION < 6  
\&\& \1='
```

In order to reduce the OpenFOAM compilation time, the `wmake` utility can be configured to use more than one core. For example, to set it up to four cores:

```
$ export WM_NCOMPPROCS=4
```

Finally, run the compilation:

```
$ cd ${WM_PROJECT_DIR}  
$ ./Allwmake
```

SOWFA compilation

The initial step is to load the OpenFOAM environment by:

```
$ source ${HOME}/OpenFOAM/OpenFOAM-2.4.x/etc/bashrc
```

Then, download the SOWFA code and select the OpenFAST branch:

```
# Download SOWFA code into ${HOME}  
$ cd ${HOME}  
$ git clone https://github.com/NREL/SOWFA.git  
$ cd SOWFA  
$ git checkout OpenFAST
```

At the time of writing this section, there are a couple of changes that must be done in the OpenFAST SOWFA branch.

The first one is related to the location of the HDF5 headers. If the HDF5 headers in the user's system are not in a compiler `include` default path, some applications will fail to build, due to `wmake` will not be able to find the HDF5 header file.

So, in order to be sure that the proper HDF5 header is found, the following options files are edited.
Go inside the following folder:

```
applications/solvers/incompressible/windEnergy/pisoFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedO
penFAST/2.3-and-higher/
```

Then, open the options file and add `-I$(HDF5_DIR)/include` at the end of the `EXE_INC` variable, so that it looks like this:

```
EXE_INC = \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/turbulenceModels/incompressible/turbulenceModel \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/transportModels \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/transportModels/incompressible/singlePhaseTransportModel \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/finiteVolume/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/meshTools/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/fvOptions/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/sampling/lnInclude \  
-  
I$(WM_PROJECT_USER_DIR)/src/turbineModels/turbineModelsOpenFAST/lnInclude \  
$(PFLAGS) \  
$(PINC) \  
-I$(OPENFAST_DIR)/include \  
-I$(HDF5_DIR)/include # Add this line. Add a backslash in the previous  
line if needed
```

The same include path also inside the file must be added:

```
src/turbineModels/turbineModelsOpenFAST/Make/options
```

Once edited, the `EXE_INC` variable should look like this:

```
EXE_INC = \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/triSurface/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/finiteVolume/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/meshTools/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/turbulenceModels \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/turbulenceModels/LES/LESdeltas/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/turbulenceModels/LES/LESfilters/lnInclude \  
-I$(LIB_SRC)/transportModels \  
$(PFLAGS) \  
$(PINC) \  
-I$(OPENFAST_DIR)/include \  
-I$(HDF5_DIR)/include # Add this line. Add a backslash in the previous  
line if needed
```

The next change to the SOWFA code is optional, but really recommended as it greatly improves the performance of the code. The SOWFA applications that use OpenFAST, by default initializes that library in debug mode. This yields a very low runtime performance. In order to avoid this behavior, go to the next folder:

```
src/turbineModels/turbineModelsOpenFAST/horizontalAxisWindTurbinesALMOpenFAST/
```

and edit the file `horizontalAxisWindTurbinesALMOpenFAST.C`, at line 414, so that it looks like this:

```
fi.debug = false;
```

Then, export the location of the OpenFAST installation directory. The user should change the path to wherever is installed OpenFAST:

```
$ export OPENFAST_DIR="/path/to/wherever/you/installed/OpenFAST"
```

Then, export the location of the HDF5 installation directory. The user should also change the path to wherever you have installed the HDF5 library:

```
$ export HDF5_DIR="/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/hdf5/serial"
```

Finally, go to the SOWFA root directory and launch the SOWFA compilation with:

```
$ cd ${HOME}/SOWFA  
$ WM_PROJECT_USER_DIR=${PWD} ./Allwmake
```

The resulting binaries will be at `${FOAM_USER_APPBIN}`:

```
$ ls ${FOAM_USER_APPBIN}
```

```
ABLSolver                ABLTerrainSolver  
pisoFoamTurbine.ADM      pisoFoamTurbine.ALM  
pisoFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvanced  pisoFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedOpenFAST  
setFieldsABL            turbineTestHarness.ALM  
turbineTestHarness.ALMAAdvanced  windPlantSolver.ADM  
windPlantSolver.ALM      windPlantSolver.ALMAAdvanced  
windPlantSolver.ALMAAdvancedOpenFAST
```

and the associated libraries will be inside `${FOAM_USER_LIBBIN}`:

```
$ ls ${FOAM_USER_LIBBIN}
```

```
libuserTurbineModelsOpenFAST.so  libuserTurbineModelsStandard.so  
libuserfiniteVolume.so          libuserincompressibleLESModels.so  
libusersampling.so              libuserutilityFunctionObjects.so
```

Runtime configuration

As it is shown, SOWFA binaries depend on a wide group of libraries: The OpenFOAM core libraries, the OpenFAST libraries, the Blas/Lapack libraries, the HDF5 libraries and its own group of libraries. In order to be able to run the SOWFA utilities, the user must be sure that *all* needed libraries are visible to the binaries at runtime.

So first must load the *OpenFOAM 2.4.x environment*:

```
$ source <INSTALL_PREFIX_FOR_OPENFOAM_2.4.x>/etc/bashrc
```

This ensures that the OpenFOAM core libraries are visible to our binaries.

For the other groups of libraries, their locations to the `LD_LIBRARY_PATH` variable needed to be appended. Starting with the OpenFAST libraries, if the root installation path of OpenFAST is pointed by the variable `OPENFAST_DIR`, then the libraries are located in the `OPENFAST_DIR/lib` folder.

```
$ export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=${OPENFAST_DIR}/lib:${LD_LIBRARY_PATH}
```

If the location of the *Blas/Lapack libraries* is not a *default* one, the user must also add it to its `LD_LIBRARY_PATH` variable. For example, if Intel MKL libraries are located inside the folder `/opt/intel2018/mkl/lib/intel64/`:

```
$ export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/opt/intel2018/mkl/lib/intel64/:${LD_LIBRARY_PATH}
```

Also, if for any reason the path `FOAM_USER_LIBBIN` during runtime is different from the one that was used during compilation, the SOWFA applications will not be able to start. This can happen for several reasons: if the user that compiled the code is different from the one that runs the code, each one will see a different path in the variable `FOAM_USER_LIBBIN`. Another possibility is that the user needs to move the libraries to a different location. In any case, the user should declare the new location of the SOWFA libraries in the `LD_LIBRARY_PATH` variable:

```
$ export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/location/of/SOWFA/libraries/:${LD_LIBRARY_PATH}
```

3.2.3 Folder hierarchy

In this section, the general structures for the simulation environments are explained. Case-specific setups will be detailed in the next section. There are two main parts: SOWFA input files and FAST input files. For detailed information for the FAST inputs, please see the FAST user guide [3].

10MW_Innwind : Path for OpenFAST input files (* all input file names for OpenFAST depend on WT type).

Innwind10MWRef.<#>.fst : Primary OpenFAST input file

ElastoDyn.<#>.dat : Structural dynamics input file. Sub-linked to *Innwind10MWRef.<#>.fst*

ServoDyn.<#>.dat : Control and electrical-drive dynamics input file. Sub-linked to *Innwind10MWRef.<#>.fst*

AeroDyn15.dat : Aerodynamic load input file. Sub-linked to *Innwind10MWRef.<#>.fst* Notice that 4 new input lines need to be added respect to the FAST v8.16 when using it with OpenFAST v1.0.0.

libikDiscon.so : Control for the individual WTs. Provided by IKERLAN (latest version from git Jan 31, 2018).

InnwindData : Path for structural and aerodynamic properties for the turbine.

Innwind_v2_Blade.dat : Structural properties for blade. Sub-linked to *ElastoDyn.<#>.dat*.

Innwind_v1_2_Tower.dat : Structural properties for the tower. Sub-linked to *ElastoDyn.<#>.dat*.

Innwind_v2_AeroDyn_blade.dat : Blade aerodynamic parameters. Sub-linked to *AeroDyn15.dat*.

Airfoils : Path for aerodynamic property data files for the blade. Sub-linked to *AeroDyn15.dat*.

Constant: Path for SOWFA parameter input.

ABLProperties : Input parameters for driving source terms.

g : Gravity definition.

LESProperties : Input parameters for LES model. Different models are available, together with their tuning constants.

transportProperties : Input parameters for reference values. Tuning of the viscosity model and its relative constant.

turbineArrayProperties : Input parameters for layout and ACL method. The tower calculation is deactivated as default. If it is needed, set *includeTower* as True.

turbulenceProperties : Switch for laminar, RANS or LES model.

System Path for SOWFA run control.

controlDict : Dictionary to define run control parameters. Time step, simulated time, writing precision and presence of additional functions (probes, averaging functions, residual plots, ...)

decomposeParDict : Dictionary for decomposition parameters.

fvSchemes : Numerical scheme definition.

fvSolutions : Matrix solver definition.

setFieldsABLDict : Dictionary for initial condition setup of precursor simulations.

changeDictionaryDict.udpateBCs.<>* : Pre-defined dictionary to change BCs.

topoSetDic.<>* : Dictionary to define the refinement region.

Sampling : Path for definition of sampling probe or surfaces.

setUp : Parameters used for SOWFA setup. All the other set up files are linked to this one, permitting to gather the majority of the simulation parameters inside a single file, from the mesh to the turbulence constants.

runscript.preprocess : Script for pre-processing (mesh generation and to set initial conditions. At this stage path and system dependant).

runscript.solver.1 : script for running simulation.

3.2.4 Performing a test run

The following guide is referred to the use of SOWFA coupled with OpenFAST.

In order to perform a test run all the following folders and files have to be present in the directory of the simulated case:

- 0.original: it contains the initial conditions of pressure, velocity, turbulent kinetic energy and Smagorinsky's viscosity
- Constant: it contains all the properties regarding the used turbines (file "turbineArrayProperties"), mesh (polymesh/"blockMeshDict") and turbulence model ("LESProperties")
- System: it contains all the dictionaries necessary to tune the adopted numerical schemes and mesh refinements
- OpenFAST folder: it contains all the necessary file required by OpenFAST (aerofoil properties, ElastoDyn AeroDyn, ServoDyn, ...)
- File .fst: it is the reference file set up in constant/turbineArrayProperties that contains all the main information required by OpenFAST to find its working files and to set up its simulation's parameters

Two steps are required to run a case after having loaded OpenFOAM's variables environment (e.g. terminal → current directory → type: "of24x" or the acronym of your version). The first step is building the mesh while the second one is simulating your case.

- 1- type `./runscript.preprocess`: this command launches the application `runscript.preprocess` which builds the mesh and refines it through global refinements all over the domain or local

refinements in the zone interested by the turbine. It has also the aim of decomposing the tested case in several processors and prepares it to run in parallel.

- 2- type `./runscript.solve`: this command launches the application `runscript.solve` which starts the simulation. It contains the name of the solver and the number of used processors.

3.2.5 Setting up a simulation case

Several files are required to set up a simulation case.

The file that sets up the physics of the problem is called `setUp` and it is contained inside the directory of the case. Inside this file you can modify:

- Domain size: it defines the domain extremities and the number of initial cells along the three main directions.
- Decomposition: it imposes the number of required cores and the decomposition method.
- Initial values for physical variables: it defines the initial wind conditions with its direction. It is possible to assign velocity, pressure, temperature, turbulent kinetic energy and temperature gradient of the incoming flow.
- General conditions and parameters: it defines the reference potential temperature, the position on the earth, the molecular Prandtl number and the molecular viscosity.
- Inputs for Smagorinsky model: it is possible to choose between some turbulence models for LES and impose its constants.
- Surface conditions: it describes the walls characteristics through the temperature fluxes and the roughness with all the constants necessary to model the heat exchange.

Please note that many files inside the folders showed in the previous section refer to this file. It contains most of the parameters necessary to describe the physics of the problem.

For what concerns the numerical set up of the machine, it is included in `turbineArrayProperties` contained in constant folder. It defines the name and position of the OpenFAST input file (`.fst`) and it sets up the actuator line parameters, from the force distribution (blade epsilon) to the available possibilities for the numerical integration. Here you can introduce more than one turbine with its specific location inside the domain. The geometric, aerodynamic and inertial properties of the turbine are defined inside OpenFAST input files which are contained in the folder specified inside the `.fst` file.

The setup of the numerical schemes and the management of sensors for the flow is included inside system folder. “fvSchemes” and “fvSolution” permit to choose the numerical schemes required by the solver chosen in `runscript.solve`, while `controlDict` permits to decide the simulation time, the writing interval and the application of advanced functions such as the positioning of sampling probes. Moreover, here it is also possible to manage the local refinements by looking at `topoSetDict.local.#refinement`.

3.3 Performing simulations

In this paragraph a brief procedure to execute each wind farm simulation is described. A specific atmospheric condition and fixed wind direction are chosen without defining any control strategy. These conditions are adjustable, and procedures to change the conditions are explained in the next section. A common process is,

- Change directory to specific wind farm case, e.g. `/RWF.generic.3by1`.
- Type `./runscript.preprocess`, or submit the preprocess script, e.g. `qsub runscript.preprocess`.
- Submit `runscript.solve.1`.

The provided runscript is prepared for the MOAB scheduler in NEC Cluster HPC system. Also, `mpirun` command is used to launch applications. User should adjust the batch script according to his/her local HPC system.

3.3.1 Generic 3 turbine case

Case directory: `/RWF.generic.3by1/`

Computational domain and meshing:

- The domain size is set as $[28.043 \times 28.043 \times 5.609] D^3$, i.e. $[5000 \times 5000 \times 1000] m^3$.
- The local refinement region is defined in `/system/topoSetDict.local.<#>`, and the size of the rectangular regions for the first and second levels are $[3D \times 20D \times (1D + H)]$ and $[5D \times 22D \times (2D + H)]$ where the hub height $H = 119$ m. With two levels of local refinements, the resolution near the turbine is $\Delta = 3.561$ m. It satisfies the general suggestion by NREL: $D/\Delta \geq 50$, where the turbine diameter $D = 178.3$ m. The total number of cells is 26×10^6 . The refinement region is attached to the farm layout, which direction is defined by `arrayDir` in `setUp` file.

Wind farm layout and ACL parameters:

- An idea of how could be the initial WF layout is shown in Figure 3.1. The wind farm layout is aligned with the main wind direction (South-West wind, $\text{dir}=225^\circ$). In the cases that will be run, the 3by1 and the 3by3 WT cases have a rotation of 45 degrees and the wind arrives equally from XY direction. To modify the layout direction, see Sec. 3.4.2.
- All parameters for the ACL method are defined in `/constant/turbineArrayProperties`. For the force projection method, `bladeForceProjectionType – variableUniformGaussianChord` is adopted which takes into account the chord length. The distribution parameters ε is chosen based on the rule-of-thumb guides, $\varepsilon = 2\Delta$. Details of the rest of input parameters for ACL can be found in `/constant/turbineArrayProperties` file.

Figure 3.1: Initial layout for 3 by 1 generic WF. The dash-line is `arrayDir=0`, see Figure 3.5 for the definition.

Wind turbine properties:

- Structural and aerodynamic properties for the 10M Innwind turbine were provided by CENER (available CL-Windcon project site, CL-WINDCON > PROJECT EXECUTION > WP1 > TECHNICAL INFORMATION > REFERENCE WIND TURBINE). In the example case, all degrees of freedom for the structural dynamics are deactivated, see ‘DEGREES OF FREEDOM’ section in `/10MW_Innwind/ElastoDyn.<#>.dat` file. It’s important to note that for capturing structural dynamics and apply turbine controllers, parameters (`FlapDOF1`, `FlapDOF2`, `EdgeDOF`, `DrTrDOF`, `GenDOF`, `YawDOF`, `TwFADOF1`, `TwFADOF2`, `TwSSDOF1`, `TwSSDOF2`) in `ElastoDyn.<#>.dat` have to be set as True, see also Sec. 3.4.3.

Time step and simulation time:

- The time step for SOWFA is 0.04 sec., which satisfies the condition that the tip passes less than two cells at each time. It can be set by `deltaT` in `/system/controlDict` file. Another time step is needed for the structural analysis for FAST, which is set to `DT=0.01` seconds (see `/10MW_Innwind/Innwind10MWRef.<#>.fst`). The suggestion is `DT=1/(10*highest natural frequency in Hz of coupling between modules)`, see FAST v8.16 note [4]. As the highest natural frequency of turbine is 2.2467 Hz, the current time step is sufficiently small. If either `deltaT` or `DT` need to be adjusted, `nFASTSubSteps` in `/constant/turbineArrayProperties` is also adjusted to `nFASTSubSteps = deltaT/DT`.
- The initial time given by the precursor simulations is 30,000 sec. The average starts at 30,400 sec. and the simulation is set to run until 32,000 sec., which gives more than 26 minutes of averaging time.

3.3.2 Generic 9 turbine case

Case directory: `/RWF.generic.3by3/`

Computational domain and meshing:

- The size of the rectangular regions for the first and second levels are $[13D \times 24D \times (1D + H)]$ and $[15D \times 26D \times (2D + H)]$. With two layers of the refinement region, the total number of cells is 80.8×10^6 . Other setup is the same as in 3by1 WF case.

Wind farm layout and ACL parameters:

- The initial WF layout is shown in Figure 3.2.
- All setups for the ACL method are the same as in 3by1 WF case. The locations for each turbine for 3by3 WF is predefined at specific array direction, i.e. `/constant/turbineArrayProperties.<#>`.

Figure 3.2: Initial layout for 3 by 3 generic WF. The dash-line is $\text{arrayDir}=0$, see Figure 3.5 for the definition.

Wind turbine properties:

- Same as in 3by1 WF case.

Time step and simulation time:

- Same as in 3by1 WF case.

Output files:

- Same as in 3by1 WF case.

3.3.3 Generic 82 turbine (offshore) case

Case directory: */RWF.offshore/*

Computational domain and meshing:

- The domain size is set as $[140 \times 140 \times 5.609] D^3$, i.e. $[24962 \times 24962 \times 1000] m^3$.
- The size of the rectangular regions for the first and second levels are $[13D \times 24D \times (1D + H)]$ and $[15D \times 24D \times (2D + H)]$. The total numbers of cells with two layers of refinement regions is 1.37×10^9 (It is noted that no and one layer of refinement generate 0.221×10^9 , 0.347×10^9 cells respectively). With this size of the domain, `decomposePar/reconstructPar` commands cannot be used due to memory shortage (up to 256GB memory per node at NEC Cluster HPC at USTUTT). Thus, the initial condition for offshore wind farm should be provided in a decomposed domain. It inevitably results in the number of processors for offshore WF

simulation is inherited from the precursor simulation.

- For users who want to choose the number of processor for their simulations, precursor simulation environment for the offshore wind farm is provided in */RWF.precursorData/PrecursorData.offshore.neutral.Uhub2.z2/*. Once the precursor simulation is run for 30000 sec., the final time step should be served as the initial condition for offshore wind farm in */RWF.offshore/*. It is noted that the saved inflow and source data should be transformed in order that they can be read for WF simulations. The scripts for the file transformation are provided from the SOWFA: *~/tools/boundaryDataConversion* and *~/tools/sourceDataConversion*.
- Lastly, the number of processors used in the provided environment is 2,700. Less than this number may lead to error due to memory issue.

Wind farm layout and ACL parameters:

- The initial WF layout is shown in Figure 3.3. The wind farm layout is aligned with the main wind direction (dir=240°). One wind direction and condition is available in precursor simulation of the offshore WF (*/RWF.precursorData/PrecursorData.offshore.neutral.Uhub2.z2/*) is equivalent to A5 in Table 3.5. It is noted that numbers 26 and 61 in Figure indicate substations, and thus the total number of turbines is 80 [8]. However, 82 turbines are assigned in */RWF.offshore/constant/turbineArrayProperties* due to convenience in generating layout coordinate. It is easy to exclude turbine 26 and 61 by simply commenting out turbine 25 and turbine 60 parts in */RWF.offshore/constant/turbineArrayProperties*.
- The ACL parameters in */constant/turbineArrayProperties* are the same as in 3by1 WF case except the turbine locations.

Wind turbine properties:

- The initial yaw angle needs to be set NacYaw=30 in order to align it with the main wind direction, see Figure 3.5 for definitions. Other parameters are the same as in 3by1 WF case.

Figure 3.3: Initial layout for offshore WF. The dash-line is arrayDir=0, see Figure 3.5 for the definition.

Time step and simulation time:

- Same as in 3by1 WF case, except that the average starts at 30750 sec. and the simulation is set to run until 31500 sec.

Output files:

- Same as in 3by1 WF case.

3.3.4 Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case

Case directory: */SWF.singleTurbine/*

To solve the flow around the wind turbine in the wind tunnel, a dedicated solver has been prepared, in order to take into account the effects imputable to the wind tunnel net, honeycomb and heat exchanger. The solver is the standard pisoFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedFASTv8, where the porosity effects have been introduced: the new solver is called porousPimpleFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedFASTv8. The source code of the solver can be found in the case directory.

Computational domain and meshing:

- The domain size is set as [58×14×3.8] m³.

- With three levels of local refinement and two global refinements, the resolution near the turbine is $\Delta = 0.03$ m. It satisfies the general suggestion by NREL: $D/\Delta \geq 50$, where the turbine diameter $D = 2.4$ m. The local refinement region is defined in `/system/topoSetDict.local.<#>`.

Wind farm layout and ACL parameters:

- The Wind tunnel layout is shown in Figure 3.4. The wind turbine is aligned with the main wind direction ($\text{dir}=270^\circ$), as the flow in the wind tunnel has only one direction.
- The distribution parameters ε is chosen based on a sensitivity analysis, the ratio between ε and the equivalent cell dimension is set to 2. With the selected mesh, the blade epsilon is 0.07.

Figure 3.4: Layout for the wind tunnel simulation.

Wind turbine properties:

- Structural and aerodynamic properties are the ones of the scaled DTU10MW model, but the airfoils do not include the aerodynamic instability and the interpolation on the Reynold's number (not yet implemented in Aerodyn15). The model is completely rigid and the control is not implemented yet.

Time step and simulation time:

- The time step is chosen from a previous sensitivity analysis, $\Delta t * \omega * R / EqDim = 1$. With this mesh, it has been selected a time step of 10^{-3} s. It can be set in `/system/controlDict` file. The same time-step is adopted for the structural analysis for FAST.

Output files:

- All output files from SOWFA are generated in `/postProcessing/` folder. Within this folder, `/turbineOutput/` contains all calculated variables, e.g. power, forces, and `/wakeProbes/`

contains all the data regarding the wake of the turbine at a distance downstream of 2.3D, and a distance between the sampling points of 0.1m. The plane sampled has a lateral extension of 3.2m and a vertical dimension of 3m, centred on the rotor axis.

3.3.5 Sedini real wind farm case

The Sedini wind farm is located 1.5km west of Sedini (Italy) in moderately complex terrain in the North of Sardinia. It consists of 36 GE1.5s turbines with 70.5m rotor diameter and 65m hub height, and 7 GE1.5sle turbines with 77m rotor diameter and 80m hub height. Both turbines models have a rated power of 1.5MW. Within CL-Windcon project, full scale farm control tests on a single turbine and groups of 3-5 turbines will be executed, and the focus of SOWFA simulations will be on simulating the turbines involved in the test. Normalized cartesian coordinates of the turbines involved in the test are provided in Table 3.2, Table 3.3, and Table 3.4 relative turbine WTG 30.

Table 3.2: Single turbine experiments – wind directions around 250°

Turbine	X (East) [m]	Y (North) [m]	Included in field test
WTG 30	0	0	yes
WTG 23	-75	159	upstream neighbor
WTG 24	-104	-175	upstream neighbor

Table 3.3: Three turbines in a row – wind directions around 260°

Turbine	X (East) [m]	Y (North) [m]	Included in field test
WTG 26	82	-513	yes
WTG 13	1129	-438	yes
WTG E5	517	-431	yes
WTG 11	895	-260	downstream neighbor
WTG 12	1000	-366	downstream neighbor
WTG 25	5	-358	upstream neighbor

Table 3.4: Eight turbines in a row – wind directions around 240°; subset of turbines operated with modified control setpoints in the field test still to be determined.

Turbine	X (East) [m]	Y (North) [m]	Included field in test
WTG 31	985	-610	yes
WTG 32	864	-785	yes
WTG 33	710	-882	yes

WTG 34	504	-1008	yes
WTG 35	330	-1101	yes
WTG 36	225	-1267	yes
WTG 37	101	-1356	yes
WTG 38	47	-1510	yes

The turbine model setup to be used in SOWFA is currently still in preparation and is derived from the 1.5MW turbine model from the WindPACT program available in NREL’s FAST software package, see <https://nwtc.nrel.gov/FAST>.

3.4 Operating conditions

3.4.1 Ambient conditions

Generic (3, 9, 82) turbine wind farm:

For the generic WFs (3by1 and 3by3), 12 ambient conditions were calculated and their boundary data were saved to provide turbulent BC for WF simulations. These cases are summarised in Table 3.5. Three wind speed (near cut-in, medium, rate) and three turbulence intensities (TI) by adjusting roughness height z_0 were calculated, and they correspond to the case numbers A1-A9. In addition, one high TI (A10), above-rated wind speed (A11) and unstable atmospheric condition (A12) cases are available. The domain size of the precursor simulations for generic WF is $[5000 \times 5000 \times 1000]$ m³ with $[351 \times 351 \times 71]$ uniformly distributed cells. It is noted that the domain height is set to 2000 m for unstable condition (A12), see */RWF.precursorData/PrecursorData.generic.unstableUHub2.z2/*.

Table 3.5: Ambient condition available for the generic wind farms.

Case	Case Number	z_0 (m)	UHub (m/s)	TI_Hub	qwall.z (Km/s)
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub1.z1	A1	0.001	4.5	0.0457	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub1.z2	A2	0.01	4.5	0.0560	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub1.z3	A3	0.2	4.5	0.0832	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub2.z1	A4	0.001	7.7	0.0491	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub2.z2	A5	0.01	7.7	0.0588	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub2.z3	A6	0.2	7.7	0.0793	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub3.z1	A7	0.001	11.4	0.0477	0

PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub3.z2	A8	0.01	11.4	0.0584	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub3.z2	A9	0.2	11.4	0.0803	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub2.z4	A10	2	7.7	0.1018	0
PrecursorData.generic.neutral.UHub4.z2	A11	0.01	20	0.0595	0
PrecursorData.generic.unstable.UHub2.z2	A12	0.01	7.7	0.0803	-0.02

To generate different wind conditions other than those in Table 3.5, a new precursor simulation has to be performed. Parameters which have to be adjusted are listed,

- UHub in *setUp* : Wind speed at the hub height.
- z0 in *setUp* : Roughness height.
- qwall in *setUp* : Temperature flux at the lower boundary for unstable condition.

See ***/RWF.precursorData/PrecursorData.generic.unstableUHub2.z2/*** for Setup files.

For the offshore wind farm, simulation parameters for one wind condition, but representative, are provided because one case would require excessive computational resources, see ***/RWF.precursorData/PrecursorData.offshore.neutral.Uhub2.z2/***. It corresponds to case A5 in the Table 3.5. The domain size of the precursor simulations for offshore WF is [24962×24962×1000] m³ with [1752×1752×72] uniformly distributed cells.

Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case:

Wind tunnel simulations to reproduce the scaled tests performed in PoliMi’s wind tunnel are going to be accomplished. The ambient conditions are reproduced through the addition of spires and porosity zone before them. The spires have to generate the turbulent shear flow, while the porosity zone has the aim of accounting for the dynamic pressure loss (1 dynamics) caused by the presence of the heat exchangers inside PoliMi’s facility. The wind velocity is imposed to be as the reference one adopted for real tests, but some investigations have to be performed to evaluate if the incoming shear flow is correctly reproduced or if it is necessary to run the precursor ABL solver to generate a reliable wind profile, without introducing the spires’ presence. The addition of the spires is made through OpenFOAM’s snappyHexMesh utility, which imports the geometry by a CAD file, while the porosity is taken into account by using a modified version of SOWFA’s solver `pisoFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedFASTv8` called `porousPimpleFoamTurbine.ALMAAdvancedFASTv8`. At the moment the TI reached by the flow on turbine’s hub is about 20%, modifications to the boundary conditions are now tested to reduce it.

Sedini real wind farm case:

The wind conditions at the Sedini wind farm are characterized by a relative low average wind speed at 60m above ground of about 5m/s and high average turbulence intensity (TI) of about 20%. The Weibull parameters fitted to 2 years of met mast data from 2008-2010 result in $k=1.51$ and $c=5.12\text{m/s}$. The site has pronounced diurnal patterns of wind speed, shear and TI. On average, the wind speed peaks in the afternoon around 3pm coinciding with the lowest average power law exponent of about 0.05, while TI shows a clear day-night cycle. The winter months on average see higher wind speeds with a mean close to 6m/s while in the summer the mean wind speed is around 4m/s.

The wind conditions to be simulated for Sedini will depend on type purpose of the simulation. We envision two types of scenarios:

- 1) Simulations with varying wind alignment with the group of selected turbines for benchmarking & tuning lower fidelity models for later use in the farm control experiments;
- 2) Co-simulations where the simulated atmospheric and turbine operation conditions are chosen as close as possible to a selected measured condition at site to directly compare measurement with simulation data.

A set of recommended atmospheric conditions representative for typical conditions at site for type 1 simulations is proposed in Table 3.6. Please keep in mind that the proposed conditions should be treated as indicative and that with the degrees of freedom available in SOWFA it may not be possible to achieve the exact combination of shear and turbulence intensity. In order to simplify the modelling of the turbine controls, a wind speed above the constant rotor speed region at cut-in is proposed.

Table 3.6: Proposed atmospheric conditions for type 1 simulations

Wind speed at 65m above ground	Turbulence intensity	Power-law shear exponent	Atmospheric stability
7m/s	17%	0.05	Unstable
7m/s	10%	0.25	Neutral/Stable

The conditions for type 2) simulations will be determined once the field measurements are available.

3.4.2 Wind directions

Definitions for directions (see Figure 3.5): North, East, South and West correspond to 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° respectively. It is noted that the positive x and y directions for the computational domain are aligned with East and North.

Figure 3.5: Definitions for the main wind direction (*dir*), array direction (*arrayDir*) and initial yaw angle (*NacYaw*). The array direction is based on the 3by1 wind farm as an example.

Generic (3, 9, 82) turbine wind farm:

For the generic and offshore wind farms, the wind direction can be modified by adjusting the wind farm layout with respect to the main wind direction. The main wind directions for each wind farm are RWF.generic.3by1/3by3 : 225° and RWF.offshore: 240° .

Apart from the layout aligned with the main wind direction, four additional wind directions ($\text{dir} - \text{arrayDir} = \pm 5^\circ, \pm 10^\circ$ from the main wind direction) are predefined and saved in **/constant/** folder, e.g. *turbineArrayProperties.220* for $+5^\circ$ wind direction. For an arbitrary wind direction, python script is provided to generate an appropriate *turbineArrayProperties* file, see *makeTurbineArrayProperties.py*.

Parameters which have to be modified for different wind directions are listed as,

- *arrayDir* in *runscript.preprocess* and *setUp* : The wind direction to define the layout.
- *NacYaw* in *10MW_Innwind/ElastoDyn.<#>.dat* : The initial/constant nacelle yaw angle. By default, the turbine (rotating) axis is aligned with the x-axis at $\text{NacYaw}=0^\circ$, see Figure 3.5.

Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case:

Inside the wind tunnel, the wind direction can't be changed. In order to account for different wind directions, the wind farm layout is changed varying the turbines' yaw. The main direction for the wind tunnel facility is 270° according to the adopted reference system.

Sedini real wind farm case:

For the simulation of selected subsets of turbines of the Sedini wind farm, the alignment of the wind direction with the tower positions of the respective turbines will depend on the purpose of the simulation. The desired wind alignment with the turbines will be achieved by rotating the layout relative to the wind direction used in the precursor simulations and adjusting yaw positions accordingly.

3.4.3 Controller

All control parameters for individual turbines are defined in *10MW_Innwind/ServoDyn.<#>.dat*, see the FAST user's guide [3] for details. To adopt the controller provided by IKERLAN, one should include it in the *ServoDyn.<#>.dat* files.

If controllers are used, the user should activate appropriate degrees of freedom in */10MW_Innwind/ElastoDyn.<#>.dat*. For example, if a yaw control is used, YawDOF should be set to True. Super-controller is not fully implemented yet and the report will be updated once it is implemented.

3.5 Verification

To verify the parameters used for the reference wind farm simulations, specific tests have been conducted. Some results, which support the method described in the report, are presented.

3.5.1 Quantification for precursor wind profiles

Figure 3.6: Effects of roughness height on averaged mean velocity magnitude (top) and turbulence intensity (bottom) profile. The horizontal dot-line represents the hub height $H=119$ m.

Figure 3.6 shows the averaged mean velocity magnitude $|U_{Hub}|$ and TI at the hub height (TI_{hub}). These parameters are defined as, $|U_{Hub}| = (U^2(z = H) + V^2(z = H))^{0.5}$ and $TI_{hub} = (u'u' + v'v' + w'w')/3/|U_{Hub}|$. The grey lines in $|U_{Hub}|$ represent the log-law profiles. Up to the hub height, the velocity profiles are predicted well. Above HH, the calculated profiles start to deviate from the log profiles, which is expected due to the Coriolis effect. TI_{hub} increases as z_0 increases, and the wind velocity has a limited impact on the TI_{hub} level. Similarly, $|U_{hub}|$ and TI_{hub} profiles for cases A10, 11 and 12 is shown in Figure 3.7. As expected, high z_0 (A10) leads to lower wind speed adjacent to the ground and higher TI at the hub height; high wind speed (A11) presents the target velocity at H, and similar TI_{hub} compared with A5; unstable condition (A12) leads to stronger velocity gradient near the ground and higher TI_{hub} compared with A5. Figure 3.8 shows the TI_{hub} at different z_0 . As shown, TI_{hub} shows very similar values with different wind speeds at the same z_0 under the same stability condition.

Figure 3.7: Mean velocity magnitudes (left) and TI_{hub} (right) profiles for cases A5, 10, 11, 12. The horizontal dot-line represents the hub height H=119 m.

Figure 3.8 shows the TI_{hub} at different z₀. As shown, TI_{hub} shows very similar values with different wind speeds at the same z₀ under the same stability condition.

Figure 3.8: TI at the hub height as a function of z₀. See Table for Uhub1, 2 and 3.

3.5.2 Effects of numerical schemes and resolutions

All precursor simulations have been simulated with central difference (CD) scheme. Mesh refinements near turbines are adapted for WF simulations. CD tends to present numerical oscillations at the edge of the refinement region. To avoid artificial oscillations, the blending factor is applied which mixes the central and upwind difference (UD) schemes: F_U=1 and 0 correspond to CD and UD respectively (see `/system/fvScheme`, CD and blending schemes correspond to ‘Gauss linear’ and ‘Gauss localBlended linear upwind’). To have a highest possible F_U value which sufficiently suppresses the oscillations, different F_U values are tested on the 3by1 WF, and the results are shown in Figure 3.9. Based on the tests, F_U=0.925 is needed to damp the oscillations.

Figure 3.9: Effect of the blending factor F_U at the edge of the refinement region.

Figure 3.10:1 Effects of resolutions near turbines, $D/\Delta = 12.5, 25, 50$. Velocity magnitude contour at the hub height for case A5 ($D/\Delta = 50$, left-top), and rotor power at turbine 0 (right-top), 1 (left-bottom) and 2 (right-bottom). The CD scheme is additionally applied for the coarsest resolution ($D/\Delta = 12.5$).

Figure 3.112 Averaged power (MW) for 3 by 1 WF.

Figure 3.12 Spectra for power for turbine 1 (left), 2 (middle) and 3 (right).

To identify effects of resolutions in the wake region, three resolutions were tested, $D/\Delta = 12.5, 25, 50, 100$ with the blending factor $F_U = 0.925$. The coarsest mesh does not contain refinement region, and thus the mesh size is the same as in case A5. The calculated power at each turbine is shown in Figure 3.10. Surprisingly, overall trends are predicted similarly by all resolutions, and the predictions are not significantly different each other considering a large resolution difference. The resolution effect is strongest at the first turbine T1. The averaged power during $t = 30333 - 30800$ are summarised in Figure 3.11. The power predictions for turbine 2 and 3 tend to converge as the resolution increases. The CD scheme is applied for the coarsest mesh. It slightly improves the power predictions for turbines 1 and 3.

To see more details, the power spectra for each turbine is shown in Figure 3.12. All cases at all turbines, the first peaks are observed at the blade passing frequency $f_{bf} = 0.333$ (1/s) where the rotor speed is fixed at 6.298 rpm. As the resolution decreases, the magnitudes for the spectra decrease in most of the frequency range. Again, the CD scheme slightly improves the predictions for spectra magnitude.

3.6 References

1. U. Irigoyen, "Definition of reference wind farms and simulation scenarios, Deliverable Report 1.1," CL-Windcon , 2017.
2. M. Churchfield, S. Lee and P. Moriarty, "Overview of the simulator for wind farm application," NREL, 2012.
3. S. Menon, P. Yeung and W. Kim, "Effect of subgrid models on the computed interscale energy transfer in isotropic turbulence," Comput. Fluids, vol. 25, pp. 165-180, 1996.
4. P. Moriarty and A. Hansen, "AeroDyn Theory Manual," NREL, 2004.
5. J. Jonkman and M. Buhl Jr, "FAST User's Guide," NREL, 2005.
6. B. Jonkman and J. Jonkman, "FAST v8.16.00a-bjj," NREL, 2016.
7. M. Kretschmer, "A comon pre- and post-processor for wind far simulations, Deliverable Report 1.3," CL-Windcon, 2017.
8. U. Irigoyen, "Definition of refernce wind farms and simualtion scenarios," CL-Windcon, Deliveralbe report 1.1, 2017.

4 FARMFLOW

4.1 Model description

4.1.1 Description summary

FarmFlow is a medium-fidelity wake model that is developed for energy yield calculations of large offshore wind farms. The wake model simulates the wind turbine wakes by solving the steady parabolized Navier-Stokes equations in perturbation form in three dimensions. The basic background flow is modelled by an atmospheric wind profile model based on Monin-Obukhov similarity theory.

Because the axial-pressure gradient term is neglected in the parabolized Navier-Stokes equations, the perturbation variables are initialized by a model for the near wake based on the free-wake vortex method where the wind turbine is modelled by an actuator disc model. The wake is represented by discrete constant strength vortex rings, and the solution is obtained with a panel method. To save computational effort, the pressure gradients are calculated a priori for a large number of axial induction factors, so that the wake model only needs to interpolate the pressure gradients between the two nearest induction factors in a look-up table. From the look-up table, the pressure gradients are prescribed in the source term of the flow equations.

For realistic simulation of active wake control in a wind farm, the incoming wind is prescribed from measured time series of wind speed and wind direction, averaged over 1 or 10 minutes periods. It is assumed that a wind field is travelling through the wind farm with the speed and direction of the wind vector. This means that turbines in the back of the wind farm experience a different wind vector from an earlier time period than wind turbines at the front of the wind farm. This effect is taken into account by means of a time delay for each wind turbine with respect to the incoming wind field. In order to synchronize the calculated power production of the whole wind farm, the simulation results are integrated over time, taking into account the time delay of the wind field for each wind turbine. This approach also simulates the effect of wind direction uncertainty associated with the delayed control of the yaw angle and the current wind direction.

4.1.2 Model details

Introduction

For the accurate calculation of wind turbine wake effects in (large) offshore wind farms, ECN has developed the software tool FarmFlow. FarmFlow uses a wake model based on the UPMWAKE code [1]. This model is a 3D parabolised Navier-Stokes code, using a $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model to account for turbulent processes in the wake. The ambient flow is modelled in accordance with the method of Panofsky and Dutton [2]. The free stream wind as a function of height is calculated for a prescribed

ambient turbulence intensity and the Monin-Obukhov length, which takes the atmospheric stability into account. For the deceleration and expansion of wind turbine wakes, FarmFlow uses an axisymmetric vortex wake model to calculate the stream wise pressure gradients, which are prescribed as a source term in the flow equations. This hybrid method of wake modelling in the near wake region, including an adapted near wake turbulence model, gives very accurate results in a very acceptable amount of computational time.

In various blind benchmark studies between 2009 and 2014, FarmFlow proved to provide the highest accuracy for large offshore wind farms in comparison with other wake models [3, 4]. The model is validated against wind tunnel measurements and full scale wind farms [5]. The main graphical user interface of FarmFlow is shown in Figure 4.1. FarmFlow can also run in batch mode from the command line.

Figure 4.1: Graphical user interface of FarmFlow

Wake model

The wake model in FarmFlow is based on the UPMWAKE code [1], originally developed by the Universidad Polytechnica de Madrid. In the original model, the wake is divided in a near wake region with a length of 2.25 rotor diameters (D), and a far wake region. Due to the parabolization, axial pressure gradients were neglected. Since the flow deceleration and wake expansion in the near wake are forced by axial pressure gradients, these effects could not be included in the original modelling,

by which the turbulence modelling started at the far wake, using an initial empirical wake velocity profile at $2.25D$.

The wake model has been improved in 2006 [6]. Thereto, the parabolization (and the subsequent enormous reduction in computational efficiency) was retained but the stream wise pressure gradient is not neglected anymore but prescribed as a source term in the flow equations. The stream wise pressure gradients are calculated via an inviscid, axisymmetric, free vortex wake method. The rotor is assumed to be a uniformly loaded actuator disc. From a prescribed thrust curve of the wind turbine the average axial induction is calculated according to blade element momentum (BEM) theory. The free vortex wake model then calculates the initial induced wake velocities that match the averaged axial velocity deficit in the rotor plane. With this method, the pressure gradients are a function of the axial force coefficient only. To save computational effort, the pressure gradients are calculated a priori for a large number of axial induction factors, so that the wake model only needs to interpolate the pressure gradients between the two nearest induction factors in this database. This hybrid method of wake modelling in the near wake region, including an adapted near wake turbulence model, gives very accurate results in an acceptable amount of computational time. Up to 20 calculations for different wind speeds or wind directions are automatically run in parallel using the available cores. For more detailed information on the wake modelling in FarmFlow, reference is made to [7].

Computational domain

The computational domain of the wake model in FarmFlow has the dimension of a rectangular box, see Figure 4.2. The size of the grid cells is chosen to achieve a good compromise between accuracy and computational time. The size of the grid cells perpendicular to the flow direction is chosen equal to $D/9$. In this way, the rotor area is covered by approximately 50 grid cells. In flow direction the grid begins at the rotor area with an exponentially increasing step size because of the slower wake development at larger distance downstream the rotor. At the rotor area the step size is $0.01D$ and after a distance of $15D$, the maximum step size of $1.6D$ is reached. To improve the accuracy, the effect of numerical diffusion has been compensated by calibrating the $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model in the near wake region.

Figure 4.2: Computational domain of FarmFlow

For the top and bottom boundaries Dirichlet conditions are applied (i.e. zero perturbation is prescribed) while at the side boundaries Neumann conditions are applied.

The power production of wind turbines is based on the rotor average velocity calculated with FarmFlow and the power curve data. Because of the curved velocity profile, the rotor averaged velocity is slightly lower than the velocity at hub height. For this reason, the calculated power production of undisturbed wind turbines may be around 99% of the true power curve. FarmFlow uses cubic splines with overshoot prevention to interpolate power and thrust values.

An example of the development of the calculated wind velocity in a long array of wind turbines with rotor diameter $D = 126$ m and a mutual distance of $6.8D$ is shown in Figure 4.3. The wake at $0.5D$ behind the first, the tenth and the twentieth turbine are shown. At the tenth turbine in the array, the boundary layer above the farm has been developed up to a height of approximately $5D$. At the twentieth turbine, the axial velocity at $4D$ above the farm has been reduced with 1.0 m/s. The reduced amount of kinetic energy available in the flow above the wind farm decreases the potential wake recovery. Besides this effect, the size of wakes of neighboring arrays will merge when the length of the arrays is long enough with respect to the distance between the arrays. As a result of the effect of reduced energy above the farm and the merging wakes of neighboring arrays, a ‘deep array effect’ can be observed when the array length is larger than 10 turbines. For smaller arrays, the effect may be too small to be noticeable in measurements.

Figure 4.3: Example of wind velocities behind the first, tenth and twentieth turbine in an array of turbines

Wind direction uncertainty

In the atmosphere, the velocity and direction of the wind changes continuously. By using measured power curves based on 10-min average samples, the effect of the continuous change of the wind on the power production is automatically accounted for. Unfortunately, this is not the case for the effect of wake losses in a wind farm. In a period of 10 minutes, wind directions change to values outside the wind direction bin in which the average result is stored. Due to these wind direction changes, the wake of a wind turbine rotor meanders laterally, which is not accounted for by the turbulence model. Therefore, a correction is applied for wind direction uncertainty to allow for fair comparison, i.e. accounting for the full range of wind directions in 10-min bins. This correction method assumes a Gaussian probability distribution of the wind direction change in consecutive samples. The standard deviation $\sigma_{\Delta\theta}$ of the wind direction change $\Delta\theta$ over consecutive sample periods is generally between 2.5° to 3.5° (according to measurements from the Horns Rev offshore wind farm and from ECN's test wind farm EWTW). However, sometimes long periods occur in which the standard deviation is much smaller or much larger. If possible, it is always recommended to calculate the standard deviation of the wind direction from the measured consecutive samples:

$$\sigma_{\Delta\theta} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i)^2}{n - 1}}$$

For best results it is important to reject data points for which $\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i > 3\sigma_{\Delta\theta}$. When time series are not available, a standard deviation of $\sigma_{\Delta\theta} = 3^\circ$ is a reasonable value to use.

Given the standard deviation of the wind direction change, the correction for wind direction uncertainty is applied by spreading out the results calculated for a given mean wind direction θ_m over neighbouring wind direction bins θ_i , according to a Gaussian probability distribution of the wind direction change $\Delta\theta$ with standard deviation $\sigma_{\Delta\theta}$ (see Figure 4.4):

$$P_i(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{\sigma_{\Delta\theta} \sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\theta_i - \theta_m}{\sigma_{\Delta\theta}} \right)^2}$$

Figure 4.4 Gaussian probability distribution with $\sigma_{\Delta\theta}=3^\circ$ for a wind direction bin size of 1° (left) and 5° (right)

The above explained correction method does not take into account the fact that, as the yaw orientation of the turbine rotors cannot follow these fast wind direction variations, the turbines will often operate with some yaw-misalignment. Due to that, in the near wake region the wake will be deflected further to an angle of approximately 1.2 times larger than the yaw misalignment angle. The correction method for wind direction uncertainty on calculated power deficits in wind farms is therefore somewhat conservative.

Near-wake turbulence modeling

The method of using prescribed pressure gradients made it possible to include the near wake region in the wake calculations, while still keeping the effort of a computational efficient parabolised code. However, results [7] have shown that the deficit of the axial velocity at short distances behind the rotor is underestimated considerably with the standard k- ϵ model. The reason for this underestimated velocity deficit is a strong overestimation of the turbulence production in the shear layer of the wake. The overestimation of the turbulence production in the near wake region has probably two reasons. First, the k- ϵ model is an empirical model that needs to be recalibrated for different types of flow. The flow in the near wake region is very different from flow in the far wake region. Second, due to the coarseness of the computational grid, numerical diffusion occurs inside the thin shear layer of the near wake region. To prevent numerical diffusion, the size of the grid cells need to be much smaller than the thickness of the shear layer. However, refining the grid will increase the computational time terribly and still not solve the problem of the different type of flows between the near wake region and the far wake region. Therefore, FarmFlow uses recalibrated k- ϵ model parameters in a region up to 4D downstream the rotor in order to improve the prediction of turbulence production and velocity deficits.

According to the description of the wake behaviour from Crespo et al. [8], the wake of a wind turbine can be separated into three regions: a near wake region, a far wake region, and a transition region in-between. Figure 4.5 shows the development of the vertical velocity profile downstream a wind turbine. In flow direction, the area is divided in four regions: the (undisturbed) free stream region upstream the rotor and the three wake regions. For each region, a velocity profile is drawn in the picture in Figure 4.5. The near wake region ends approximately at two rotor diameters downstream the rotor, and the far wake begins at approximately 4D-5D downstream.

Figure 4.5 Development of the vertical velocity profile downstream a wind turbine

The near wake region starts at the rotor surface where wind energy is extracted by means of a pressure drop over the rotor plane. The cylindrical shear layer separates the slow moving air inside the wake from the air outside the wake. Inside the shear layer tip vortices, which are shed from the turbine blades, are following a helical trajectory. The velocity deficit inside the wake increases as a result of increasing pressure inside the wake, until this pressure reaches the pressure of the external flow. The wake expands as a result of the increasing velocity deficit. The stable system of helical vortices inside the shear layer produce only a small amount of turbulence. Because of limited turbulent diffusion inside the shear layer, the thickness of the shear layer grows slowly. Particle image velocimetry (PIV) measurements [9] have shown that the effect of individual blades on axial velocity disappears beyond a distance of one rotor diameter, while the tip vortices stay present for a much longer time.

At the end of the near wake region, the tip vortices start to break down and produce high levels of turbulence. As a result of the increased turbulent diffusion, the shear layer thickness increases faster.

When the shear layer reaches the wake axis, the near wake ends and the transition region begins. The transition region ends where the wake is completely developed with self-similar distribution profiles of the velocity deficit and turbulence intensity. Here, in the far wake region, the wake meets the criteria for which the standard k- ϵ model has been calibrated.

For the near wake region and the transition region the standard k- ϵ model is not valid. Applying the standard k- ϵ model parameters will result in large overestimation of the turbulence production in the shear layer of the near wake region, which will then be spread over the whole wake area as a result of turbulent diffusion. Because of this, the recovery of the wake will start too soon and too fast. Kasmi and Masson [10] also noted this, and added an extra term to the transport equation for the turbulence energy dissipation rate. FarmFlow uses recalibrated k- ϵ model parameters for the near wake region and the transition region to correct the behaviour of the turbulence model. Only in the far wake region the standard k- ϵ model parameters are applied.

The target for the recalibration process of the k- ϵ model parameters has been to produce the best agreement with measurements in large offshore wind farms. For those wind farms, the distance between wind turbines are generally between 5 and 10 rotor diameters. Therefore, the aim of the recalibration process has been to get the highest accuracy of power prediction for wind turbine arrays with a turbine spacing of 5 to 10 rotor diameters.

Active wake control

AWC is a farm operation strategy that aims at improving the overall wind farm performance in terms of power production and/or turbine loads. Two concepts for AWC exist: reducing power and thrust of upstream turbines in favour of downstream turbines (called induction control), and applying yaw-misalignment of upstream turbines in order to steer the wake of these turbines away from downstream turbines (wake redirection/steering). FarmFlow supports simulations with both induction control and wake redirection. Implementation of induction control in FarmFlow is rather straightforward by applying different power and thrust curves for induction control. The implementation of the wake redirection control is more complicated and is described below.

A visualization of the AWC concept with yaw-misalignment is shown in Figure 4.6. The left hand side of this figure represents the normal situation without yaw-misalignment. The wake of the upstream turbine is visualized. The downstream turbine is operating in the right half side of that wake. The blue arrows visualize the flow in three cross-sections of the wake, and the purple arrows visualize the rotor induced flow that cause the velocity deficit. The right hand side of Figure 4.6 shows the same situation, except that the upstream turbine is misaligned with a yaw-angle $\gamma=20^\circ$. Because the induced flow of the rotor is directed normal to the rotor surface, the resultant flow field of the wake

of the yawed turbine deflects from the wind direction. As a result, a much smaller part of the downwind turbine operates inside the wake of the upwind turbine.

Figure 4.6: Visualization of AWC using yaw-misalignment

The angle of the wake deflection depends on the thrust coefficient and the yaw angle. Since FarmFlow uses prescribed pressure gradients in the near wake region in order to induce the wake, i.e. the deceleration and expansion of the flow behind the rotor, implementation of yaw-misalignment is realized by prescribing these pressure gradients with respect to the yaw angle instead of the flow direction. Two empirical correction factors were used to optimize the wake deflection angle and wake deficit values. In addition, the width of the wake is reduced by a factor $\cos(\gamma)$.

Figure 4.7: Wind speed deficits in the wake of a turbine under normal operation (Yaw) and two fixed yaw angles (237° and 253°)

Figure 4.7 shows comparisons of measurements from ECN’s scaled wind farm and calculated wakes from FarmFlow for different yaw angles at a distance of 1.9D behind the rotor [5]. The blue line shows the velocity deficit when the turbine has no yaw misalignment. For the red line the turbine has a fixed yaw angle of 237°, resulting in a yaw misalignment angle of (237° - WindDirection). Therefore, only for a wind direction WD=237° there is no yaw misalignment for the red line so that its value there is identical to the blue line. For the green line, the turbine has a fixed yaw angle of 253°, resulting in a yaw misalignment angle of (253° - WindDirection). Therefore, only for a wind direction WD=253° there is no yaw misalignment for the green line so that its value is identical to the blue line. From these comparisons, it can be concluded that FarmFlow predicts the velocity deficits in the wake of wind turbines with yaw misalignment quite well.

Yaw misalignment has a negative effect on the power production of concerning wind turbine. The mass flow through a wind turbine rotor decreases with a factor $\cos(\gamma)$ while it also changes the angle of attack of the rotor blades, leading to less efficient aerodynamic behaviour. As a result, the power of a yawed wind turbine below rated wind speed can be estimated with

$$P(\gamma) = P(0) \cos^{\beta} \gamma$$

Wind tunnel measurements reported by Dahlberg and Medici [11] showed an average exponent β of 2.48. An extensive database of field measurements analysed by Dahlberg [12] showed the exponent β to vary between 1.8 and 5.5. Schepers [13] found a value of 1.8 based on measurements taken in the large DNW tunnel. In the NREL Phase VI experiment in the NASA-Ames wind tunnel a strong dependency of the exponent on the induction was found where at low induction the power was found to increase with yaw due to unsteady aerodynamic effects. Full scale tests on ECN’s test site EWTW resulted in an average exponent of 2.1, and field test with a scaled wind farm resulted in an average exponent of 2.3. All these reported results indicate that there is a large uncertainty in the power exponent for yaw misalignment. In FarmFlow, a slightly conservative choice has been made with a power exponent $\beta = 2.3$.

Figure 4.8 shows an example of the application of AWC in FarmFlow with two turbines. As a function of wind direction, the optimized total power is found by applying yaw misalignment on the first turbine. When the wind direction is 0° (i.e. in line with the two turbines) the gain, shown by the green line and corresponding to the right axis, is negligible. The reduced power of the first turbine can be just compensated by the second turbine because of the wake deflection. When the wind direction is -8 to -5° or 5 to 8°, the gain of AWC is more than 6%. For these situations, the second turbine is positioned approximately in one half of the wake of the first turbine (as in Figure 4.6),

which is most beneficial for AWC. The results of Figure 4.8 are in very good agreement of the wind tunnel results of Dahlberg and Medici [11].

Figure 4.8: Example of optimized power output of two turbines with yaw misalignment

In comparison with the other strategy of AWC, i.e. reducing the thrust coefficient, there is a big difference in beneficial wind directions. When the thrust coefficient is reduced, the total wake effect is reduced so that the most beneficial wind direction is when the second turbine is in the centre of the wake. Because of the different beneficial wind directions of both strategies of AWC, both strategies can be applied in a wind farm in addition to each other, depending on the wind direction.

Quasi-dynamic wakes

For realistic simulation of active wake control in a wind farm, the incoming wind is prescribed from measured time series of wind speed and wind direction, averaged over 1 or 10 minutes periods. It is assumed that a wind field is travelling through the wind farm with the speed and direction of the wind vector. This means that turbines in the back of the wind farm experience a different wind vector from an earlier time period than wind turbines at the front of the wind farm. This effect is taken into account by means of a time delay for each wind turbine with respect to the incoming wind field. In order to synchronize the calculated power production of the whole wind farm, the simulation results are integrated over time, taking into account the time delay of the wind field for each wind turbine. This approach also simulates the effect of wind direction uncertainty associated with the delayed control of the yaw angle and the current wind direction.

4.2 References

1. A. Crespo and J. Hernández, "Numerical modelling of the flow field in a wind turbine wake," in Proceedings of the 3rd Joint ASCE/ASME Mechanics Conference, ASME, 1989.
2. H. Panofsky and J. Dutton, Atmospheric Turbulence, Wiley, 1984.
3. R. Barthelmie, "Flow and wakes in large wind farms: Final report for UpWind WP8," Risø-R-1765(EN), 2011.
4. C. a. G. G. Hasager, "EERA DTOC final summary report," EERA DTOC Project deliverable D7.20, 2015.
5. E. Bot, "FarmFlow validation against full scale wind farms," Energy research Center of the Netherlands (ECN), report ECN-E--15-045, August 2015.
6. S. Van der Pijl and J. Schepers, "Improvements of the WAKEFARM wake model," in Annex XXIII: Offshore wind energy technology and deployment, 2006.
7. J. Schepers and S. van der Pijl, "Improved modelling of wake aerodynamics and assessment of new farm control strategies," in Journal of Physics, Conference Series 75, 2007.
8. A. Crespo, J. Hernández and S. Frandsen, "Survey of modelling methods for wind turbine wakes and wind farms," Wind Energy, vol. 2, pp. 1-24, 1999.
9. F. Massouh and I. Dobrev, "Exploration of the vortex wake behind of wind turbine rotor," in Journal of Physics, Conference Series 7, 2007.
10. A. E. Kasmi and C. Masson, "An extended $k-\epsilon$ model for turbulent flow through horizontal-axis wind turbines," Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics , vol. 96, pp. 103-122, 2008.
11. J. Dahlberg and D. Medici, "Potential improvement of wind turbine array efficiency by active wake control (AWC)," in EWEC, Madrid, 2003.
12. J. Dahlberg and B. Montgomerie, "Wake effects and other loads (Final report: part II)," Research program of the Utgrunden demonstration offshore wind farm, 2005.
13. J. Schepers, "Engineering models in wind energy aerodynamics," PhD thesis, TU-Delft, 2012.

5 FAST.FARM

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ABLSolver	Atmospheric Boundary Layer Solver
AWAE	Ambient Wind and Array Effects
BEM	Blade-Element/Momentum
DWM	Dynamic Wake Meandering
HFM	High-Fidelity Modelling
LES	Large-Eddy Simulations
MPI	Message-Passing Interface
NREL	US National Renewable Energy Laboratory
RSS	Root-Sum-Square
SC	Super Controller
WD	Wake-Dynamics

5.1 Model description

5.1.1 Description summary

FAST.Farm is a medium-fidelity multi-physics engineering tool for predicting the power performance and structural loads of wind turbines within a wind farm developed by the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL).

Developed to overcome major drawbacks to apply Dynamic Wake Meandering (DWM) for effective wind farm control design and validation, FAST.Farm has been selected by CENER as the most promising substitute for DWM within the CL-Windcon project, in particular to allow proper dynamic consideration of the turbine controls.

At the time of submitting this deliverable, first release of the tool has not been issued yet, although it is expected in 2018. CENER is in close contact with NREL to perform tests over a pre-release version, whose results are expected for subsequent deliverables. A summarized description of the tool principles, extracted from available public information [1], is included in this section with the sole aim of being a short introduction to FAST.Farm. Reference [1] can be consulted for complete detailed mathematical insight for the whole solution. NREL has also performed calibration of FAST.Farm against SOWFA simulations [2], and similar validation is expected to also be published by NREL in the coming months.

5.1.2 Model purpose

FAST.Farm uses OpenFAST to solve the aero-hydro-servo-elastic dynamics of each individual turbine, but adds additional physics for wind farm: ambient wind in the atmospheric boundary layer, a wind-farm super controller and wake deficits like advection, deflection, meandering, and merging. FAST.Farm is based on some of the principles of the DWM model, but addresses many of the limitations of previous DWM implementations, includes also the controls capability of FLORIS, and functions more similarly to SOWFA. Validation and parameter calibration of FAST.Farm is currently performed against SOWFA simulations with widely accepted conditions.

FAST.Farm tool is applicable to engineering problems in research and industry involving wind farm performance and cost optimization, development of wind farm control or optimization of wind farm siting, among others. FAST.Farm maintains computational efficiency to support iterative and probabilistic design, as well as system-wide optimization, while properly modelling the relevant physics.

5.1.3 Model specifications

FAST.Farm addresses limitations of previous DWM model implementations by applying some novel solutions devoted to:

- Compute the ambient wind farm-wide from the Atmospheric Boundary Layer Solver (ABLSolver) precursor to SOWFA (or equivalent).
- Include a wind-farm super controller, quite similar to the one used in SOWFA.
- Advect the wake based on the local spatially averaged ambient wind speed and wake deficit.
- Solve the wake deficit in planes parallel to the rotor disk.
- Deflect the wake centreline based on the inflow skew.
- Update the wake deficit and centreline based on low-pass-filtered inflow, wind turbine control, and wind turbine motion.
- Solve the individual wind turbine and wake dynamics in parallel on multiple cores (or an HPC), interconnected through a message-passing interface (MPI).
- Allow the wake merging to influence wake dynamics.
- Calculate the wake deficits of downwind wind turbines dependent on the impingement of wakes from upwind wind turbines.

- Superimpose the wake deficits in the axial direction based on the root-sum-square (RSS) method.
- Meander the wakes both laterally and axially.

FAST.Farm is a nonlinear time-domain multi-physics engineering tool composed of multiple submodules, each modelling different physics domains of the wind farm. FAST.Farm is implemented as open-source software that follows the programming requirements of the OpenFAST modularization framework, whereby the submodules are implemented as modules interconnected through a driver code. The submodule hierarchy of FAST.Farm is illustrated in Figure 5.1. Wake advection, deflection, and meandering; near-wake correction; and wake-deficit increment are submodules of the wake-dynamics (WD) model, implemented in a single module (called WD). Ambient wind and wake merging are submodules of the ambient wind and array effects (AWAE) model, implemented in a single module (called AWAE). The super controller (SC) and OpenFAST (OF) are separated modules, meaning that FAST.Farm has four modules (SC, OF, WD, and AWAE) and one driver. There are as many instances of the OF and WD modules as wind turbines. To handle the memory requirements and parallelization, the entire wind farm is solved in parallel on multiple cores (or an HPC); but the solution will require only a modest HPC resource (a bit more than two cores per turbine in the wind farm)—not out of reach for industry and research current use. This opens wide application of FAST.Farm for iterative simulation covering the fidelity gap between simple engineering models and more complex models such Large-Eddy Simulations (LES).

Figure 5.1: FAST.Farm modules

5.1.4 Detailed mathematical derivation

FAST.Farm Driver

The FAST.Farm driver, also known as the “glue code,” is the code that couples individual modules together and drives the overall time-domain solution forward. Additionally, the FAST.Farm driver reads an input file of simulation parameters, checks the validity of these parameters, initializes the modules, writes results to a file, and releases memory at the end of the simulation.

Super Controller (Module SC)

Wind-farm-wide super controllers have the potential to achieve global benefit of improving overall power performance and reducing turbine loads, based on modifying wake deficits through variations in blade pitch or generator torque and/or redirecting (steering) wakes through variations in nacelle yaw or tilt.

OpenFAST (Module OF)

FAST.Farm makes use of OpenFAST to model the dynamics (loads and motions) of distinct turbines within the wind farm. OpenFAST captures the environmental excitations (wind inflow, and for offshore systems, waves, current, and ice) and coupled system response of the full system (the rotor, drivetrain, nacelle, tower, controller, and for offshore systems, the substructure and station-keeping system). OpenFAST itself is an interconnection of various modules, each corresponding to different physical domains of the coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic solution.

Wake Dynamics (Module WD)

The WD module of FAST.Farm calculates wake dynamics for an individual rotor, including wake advection, deflection, and meandering, a near-wake correction, which treats the near-wake (pressure-gradient zone) correction to the wake deficit and a wake-deficit increment, which increments the quasi-steady-state axisymmetric wake deficit nominally downwind.

The wake-dynamics calculations involve many user-specified parameters that are dependent, for example, on turbine operation or atmospheric conditions that can be calibrated through high-fidelity modelling (HFM), e.g., by running SOWFA (or equivalent) as a pre-processor. Default values are derived for each calibrated parameter based on SOWFA simulations, but these can be overwritten by the user of FAST.Farm. The calibration process is performed over a set of 18 parameters coming from the WD and the AWAE modules [2].

The wake-deficit evolution is solved in discrete time on an axisymmetric finite-difference grid consisting of a fixed number of wake planes, each with a fixed radial grid of nodes. Given that the wake deficit is assumed to be axisymmetric, the radial finite-difference grid can then be considered a plane. A wake plane can be thought of as a cross section of the wake wherein the wake deficit is calculated. This allows accessing the wake evolution downwind.

Module WD computes several outputs needed for the calculation of disturbed wind (ambient plus wakes), which is the input to the module AWAE. These include the orientations of the wake planes, defined using the unit vectors normal to each plane, i.e., the orientation of the wake-plane centreline. But also the global positions of the centres of the wake planes, the axial and radial wake-velocity deficits at the wake planes, radially distributed, and the wake diameters at the wake planes.

Each submodel within WD is described in the subsections below.

- **Wake Advection, Deflection, and Meandering**

By simple extensions to the passive tracer solution for transverse (horizontal and vertical) wake meandering, the wake-dynamics solution in FAST.Farm is extended to account for wake deflection and wake advection, among other physical improvements.

- **Near-Wake Correction**

The near-wake correction submodel of module WD computes the axial and radial wake-velocity deficits at the rotor disk, as an inlet boundary condition for the wake-deficit evolution. To improve the accuracy of the far-wake solution, the near-wake correction accounts for the drop-in wind speed and radial expansion of the wake in the pressure-gradient zone behind the rotor that is not otherwise accounted for in the solution for the wake-deficit evolution.

For clarity, the equations in this section are expressed using continuous variables; but within FAST.Farm, the equations are solved discretely on an axisymmetric finite-difference grid.

First, the axial induction at the rotor disk, distributed radially, $a(r)$, is derived from the low-pass time-filtered azimuthally averaged thrust-force coefficient (normal to the rotor disk), $FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r)$, evaluated at $n + 1$ using Equation 5.1. The formulation at low thrust-force coefficients ($< \frac{24}{25}$) follows from the momentum region of blade-element/momentum (BEM) theory; the formulation at high thrust-force coefficients ($\geq 24/25$) follows from Glauert's correction with Buhl's modification to the empirical region [3]. To avoid unrealistically high induction at the ends of a blade, Equation 5.1 does not directly consider hub- or tip-loss corrections, but these may be accounted for in the calculation of the applied aerodynamic loads within OpenFAST (depending on the aerodynamic options enabled within OpenFAST), which have

an effect on $FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r)$.

$$a(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r)} \right) & \text{for } \left(FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r) < \frac{24}{25} \right) \\ \frac{2 + 3\sqrt{14 FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r) - 12}}{14} & \text{for } \left(\frac{24}{25} \leq FilteredAzimAvg C_t(r) \leq 2 \right) \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

The states and outputs associated with the axial and radial wake-velocity deficits, distributed radially, $V_{x_{np}}^{Wake}(r)$ and $V_{r_{np}}^{Wake}(r)$, respectively, are derived at the rotor disk from $a(r)$ and the low-pass time-filtered rotor-disk-averaged relative wind speed (ambient plus wakes plus turbine motion), normal to the disk, $FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Rel}$, evaluated at $n + 1$ using Equation 5.2 and Equation 5.3. In Equation 5.2, r^{Plane} is the radial expansion of the wake associated with r , r' is a dummy variable of r , and $C_{NearWake}$ is a user-specified calibration parameter greater than unity, which determines how far the wind speed drops and wake expands radially in the pressure-gradient zone before recovering in the far wake; a value of $C_{NearWake} = 2$ is expected from first principles, but $C_{NearWake}$ can be calibrated by the user of FAST.Farm to better match the far wake to known particular solutions. The right-hand side of Equation 5.2 represents the axial-induced velocity at the end of the pressure-gradient zone. The negative sign appears because the axial wake deficit is in the opposite direction of the free stream axial wind. The radial expansion of the wake in the left-hand side of Equation 5.2 results from the application of the conservation of mass within an incremental annulus in the pressure-gradient zone, i.e., the incremental mass flow is:

$$d\dot{m} = 2\pi r dr \rho FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Rel} (1 - a(r)) = 2\pi r^{Plane} dr^{Plane} \rho FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Rel} (1 - C_{NearWake} a(r)),$$

So

$$r^{Plane} dr^{Plane} = \frac{1 - a(r)}{1 - C_{NearWake} a(r)} r dr,$$

which can then be integrated along the radius. The radial wake deficit is initialized to zero, as given in Equation 5.3. Because the near-wake correction is applied directly at the rotor disk, the solution to the wake-deficit evolution for downwind distances within the first few diameters of the rotor (i.e., in the near wake) is not expected to be accurate. As a result, modifications to FAST.Farm would be needed to accurately model closely spaced wind farms.

$$V_{x_{np}}^{Wake}(r^{Plane}) \Big|_{n_p=0, r^{Plane}} = \sqrt{2 \int_0^r \frac{1 - a(r')}{1 - C_{NearWake} a(r')} r' dr'} = -FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Rel} C_{NearWake} a(r) \quad (5.2)$$

$$V_{rnp}^{Wake}(r) \Big|_{np=0} = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

- **Wake-Deficit Increment**

As with most DWM implementations, the WD module of FAST.Farm models the wake-deficit evolution via the thin shear-layer approximation of the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations under quasi-steady-state conditions in axisymmetric coordinates, with turbulence closure captured by using an eddy-viscosity formulation. The thin shear-layer approximation drops the pressure term and assumes that the velocity gradients are much bigger in the radial direction than in the axial direction. With these simplifications, analytical expressions for the conservation of momentum (Equation 5.4) and conservation of mass (continuity, Equation 5.5) are as follows:

$$V_x \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + V_r \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \nu_T \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r} \right), \text{ or equivalently,}$$

$$r V_x \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + r V_r \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r} = \nu_T \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r} + r \nu_T \frac{\partial^2 V_x}{\partial r^2} + r \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r}, \quad (5.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r V_r) = 0, \text{ or equivalently, } V_r + r \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial r} + r \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

where V_x and V_r are the axial and radial velocities in the axisymmetric coordinate system, respectively, and ν_T is the eddy viscosity (all dependent on x and r , i.e., the downwind distance and radius in the axisymmetric coordinate system). The equations on the left are written in a form common in literature while the equivalent equations on the right are written in the form implemented within FAST.Farm.

V_x and V_r are related to the low-pass time-filtered rotor-disk-averaged ambient wind speed, normal to the disk $FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Wind}$, and the states and outputs associated with the axial and radial wake-velocity deficits, distributed radially, $V_x^{Wake}(x, r)$ and $V_r^{Wake}(x, r)$, by Equation 5.6 and Equation 5.7. $V_x^{Wake}(x, r)$ and $V_r^{Wake}(x, r)$ can be thought of as the change in wind velocity in the wake relative to free stream so, $V_x^{Wake}(x, r)$ usually has a negative value.

$$V_x(x, r) = FilteredDiskAvg V_x^{Wind} + V_x^{Wake}(x, r) \quad (5.6)$$

$$V_r(x, r) = V_r^{Wake}(x, r) \quad (5.7)$$

The eddy-viscosity formulation currently implemented within FAST.Farm is given by Equation 5.8, where $F_{vAmb}(x)$ and $F_{vShr}(x)$ are filter functions associated with ambient turbulence and the shear layer, respectively, and k_{vAmb} and k_{vShr} are user-specified calibration parameters

weighting the influence of ambient turbulence and the shear layer on the eddy viscosity. The filter functions currently implemented within FAST.Farm are given by Equations 5.9. and Equation 5.10, where C_{vAmb}^{DMax} , C_{vAmb}^{DMin} , C_{vAmb}^{Exp} , and C_{vAmb}^{FMin} and C_{vShr}^{DMax} , C_{vShr}^{DMin} , C_{vShr}^{Exp} , and C_{vShr}^{FMin} are user-specified calibration parameters for the functions associated with ambient turbulence and the shear layer, respectively. Although not matching any specific eddy-viscosity formulation found in prior implementations of DWM, the chosen implementation within FAST.Farm is simple to apply and inherently tailorable, allowing the user to properly calibrate the wake evolution to known solutions.

$$v_T(x, r) = F_{vAmb}(x)k_{vAmb}^{Filtered} T I_{Amb}^{Filtered} Disk Avg V_x^{Wind} \frac{Filtered D_{Rotor}}{2} + F_{vShr}(x)k_{vShr} \max\left(\left[\frac{D^{Wake}(x)}{2}\right]^2 \left|\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial r}(x, r)\right|, \frac{D^{Wake}(x)}{2} \min(V_x(x, r))\right) \quad (5.8)$$

Equation 5.8 expresses the influence of the ambient turbulence (first term on the right-hand side) and shear layer (second term) on the turbulent stresses in the wake. The dependence of the eddy viscosity on r and x is explicitly given in this equation to make it clear which terms depend on the downwind distance and/or radius.

$$F_{vAmb}(x) = \begin{cases} C_{vAmb}^{FMin} & \text{for } (x \leq C_{vAmb}^{DMin} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \\ C_{vAmb}^{FMin} + (1 - C_{vAmb}^{FMin}) \left[\frac{x}{Filtered D_{Rotor}} - C_{vAmb}^{DMin} \right]^{C_{vAmb}^{Exp}} & \text{for } (C_{vAmb}^{DMin} Filtered D_{Rotor} < x < C_{vAmb}^{DMax} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \\ 1 & \text{for } (x \geq C_{vAmb}^{DMax} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

$$F_{vShr}(x) = \begin{cases} C_{vShr}^{FMin} & \text{for } (x \leq C_{vShr}^{DMin} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \\ C_{vShr}^{FMin} + (1 - C_{vShr}^{FMin}) \left[\frac{x}{Filtered D_{Rotor}} - C_{vShr}^{DMin} \right]^{C_{vShr}^{Exp}} & \text{for } (C_{vShr}^{DMin} Filtered D_{Rotor} < x < C_{vShr}^{DMax} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \\ 1 & \text{for } (x \geq C_{vShr}^{DMax} Filtered D_{Rotor}) \end{cases} \quad (5.10)$$

The filter functions of Equations 5.9 and Equation 5.10, representing the delay in the turbulent stress generated by ambient turbulence and the development of turbulent stresses generated by

the shear layer, respectively, are made general in FAST.Farm. Each filter function is split into three regions of downstream distance, including:

- 1) a fixed minimum value (between zero and unity, inclusive) near the rotor,
- 2) a fixed value of unity far downstream from the rotor,
- 3) a transition region for intermediate distances, where the value can transition linearly or via any rational exponent of the normalized downstream distance within the transition region.

Ambient Wind Array Effects (Module AWAE)

The AWAE module of FAST.Farm processes ambient wind and wake interactions across the wind farm, including

- the ambient wind submodel, which processes ambient wind across the wind farm from a precursor ABLSolver (or equivalent) simulation, and
- the wake-merging submodel, which identifies zones of overlap between all wakes across the wind farm and merges their wake deficits.

The calculations in module AWAE make use of wake volumes, which are volumes formed by a cylinder starting at a wake plane and extending axially downstream (along the wake plane's centreline) and ending where the cylinder is sliced by the next wake plane. The diameter of the cylinder is dependent on the calculation. The calculations in module AWAE also require looping through all wind data points, turbines, and wake planes. These loops have been sped up in FAST.Farm by implementation of parallelization.

- **Ambient Wind**

FAST.Farm uses atmospheric phenomena generated by a precursor LES simulation of the entire wind farm (without wind turbines present), as is currently implemented in the ABLSolver pre-processor of SOWFA. This precursor atmospheric simulation captures more physics than synthetic turbulence including stability and complex terrain effects, but it is much less computationally expensive than a SOWFA simulation with multiple wind turbines present. A precursor atmospheric simulation could also be run with a tool equivalent to ABLSolver instead.

FAST.Farm requires ambient wind to be input in two different resolutions (see Figure 5.2). Because wind will be spatially averaged across wake volumes within module AWAE, FAST.Farm needs as input a low-resolution wind domain (in both space and time) throughout the wind farm wherever wakes may potentially reside. The spatial resolution of the low-resolution domain

consists of a (potentially unstructured) three-dimensional grid of wind data points. This is considered to be sufficient so that the spatial averaging is accurate, e.g., on the order of tens of meters for utility-scale wind turbines. For accurate load calculation by OpenFAST, FAST.Farm also needs as input high-resolution wind domains (in both space and time) around each wind turbine. These domains can take into consideration any turbine displacement, for example in yaw angle.

Figure 5.2: Wake planes, wake volumes, and zones of wake overlap for a two-turbine wind farm, with the upwind turbine yawed.

After the ambient wind is read in at a given time step, the ambient wind submodel of module AWAE computes as output the rotor-disk-averaged ambient wind speed, normal to the disk, $DiskAvgV_x^{Wind}$, for each turbine using the following equation.

$$DiskAvgV_x^{Wind} = \left(\left\{ \hat{x}_{n_p}^{Plane} \right\}^T \left\{ \frac{1}{N_{n_p}^{Wind}} \sum_{n^{Wind}=1}^{N_{n_p}^{Wind}} \vec{V}_{Amb_{n^{Wind}}}^{Low} \right\} \right) \Big|_{n_p=0} \quad (5.11)$$

where $N_{n_p}^{Wind}$ is the number of wind data points in the low-resolution domain that reside within wake volume n_p (i.e., the wake volume associated with wake plane n_p) for the given wind turbine, n^{Wind} is the point counter such that $1 \leq n^{Wind} \leq N_{n_p}^{Wind}$ for wake volume n_p , and the equation is evaluated for the wake volume at the rotor disk ($n_p = 0$).

- **Wake Merging**

In FAST.Farm, the wake-merging submodel of module AWAE identifies zones of wake overlap between all wakes across the wind farm and superimposes the wake deficits in the axial direction based on the RSS method. The transverse components (radial wake deficits) are superimposed by vector sum. The RSS method assumes that the local kinetic energy of the axial deficit in a

merged wake equals the sum of the local energies of the axial deficits for each wake at the given wind data point. This method only applies to an array of scalars, which works well for axial deficits because overlapping wakes likely have similar axial directions. This implies that only the magnitude of the vector is important in the superposition computation. A vector sum is applied to the transverse components (radial wake deficits) because any given radial direction is dependent on the azimuth angle in the axisymmetric coordinate system.

5.2 References

1. Jonkman, J. M., Annoni, J., Hayman, G., Jonkman, B., and Purkayastha, A., "Development of FAST.Farm: a new multiphysics engineering tool for wind-farm design and analysis," 35th Wind Energy Symposium, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2017, DOI: 10.2514/6.2017-0454.
2. Doubrawa, P., Annoni, J., Jonkman, J., and Ghate, A., "Optimization-Based Calibration of FAST.Farm Parameters Against SOWFA", 2018 Wind Energy Symposium, AIAA SciTech Forum, (AIAA 2018-0512), DOI: 10.2514/6.2018-0512
3. Buhl Jr., M. L. "A New Empirical Relationship between Thrust Coefficient and Induction Factor for the Turbulent Windmill State". NREL/TP-500-36834, 2005

6 FLOW REDIRECTION AND INDUCTION IN STEADY-STATE (FLORIS)

6.1 Model description

6.1.1 Description summary

The FLOW Redirection In Steady-state (FLORIS) tool is a set of low-fidelity steady-state wind farm models developed by the Delft University of Technology and the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). FLORIS has been developed for real-time online wind farm control and low-fidelity offline wind farm analysis and layout optimization. Fundamentally, it is built in a modular way and includes a number of existing steady-state wake deficit and wake deflection models from the literature to provide a relatively accurate prediction of the time-averaged flow field and turbine power capture in the wind farm at a very low computational cost.

Rather than presenting every submodule included in the FLORIS tool, this document will limit its scope to the specific submodels relevant for the CL-Windcon project.

6.1.2 Model purpose

FLORIS aims to provide accurate predictions of the time-averaged flow field and the time-averaged power capture of each turbine inside the wind farm at a very low computational cost. Due to its low computational cost, FLORIS is typically used for the optimization of the turbine control settings in order to maximize the farm's energy production. However, it has also been used for layout optimization, and can even be extended for usage in wind turbine and farm design. For example, FLORIS can be used to investigate the effects of turbine tower heights or rotor diameters on the annual power production of an envisioned farm. Furthermore, since FLORIS does not capture the temporal dynamics of neither the flow nor the turbine, structural loads are not included in FLORIS. Therefore, only the power capture can be accurately optimized.

6.1.3 Model specifications

The model specifications described here are partially derived from Annoni et al. [1].

The specific wake model inside FLORIS that will be used for the CL-Windcon project has been derived from the expressions of conservation of mass and momentum, based on the initial work by Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [2]. In this work, a Gaussian distribution for the wake velocity deficit is assumed, generally showing good agreement with experimental and LES simulation data, outperforming the popular Jensen model from the literature. The turbine is modelled using an

actuator disk representation. Then, Niayifar and Porté-Agel [3] extended this single wake model into an analytical wind farm model, including the effects of turbine-induced turbulence. Wakes of multiple turbines were combined following the sum-of-energy-deficits approach of Katić et al. [4]. Most recently, this wind farm model has been analysed and extended for yaw effects by Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [5], based on a budget analysis of the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations and wind tunnel experiments. The budget analysis separates the energy contributions in the flow for different terms in the RANS expressions (under turbine yaw), thereby allowing structural simplifications, to end up with a reliable analytical wind farm model.

The FLORIS model has been implemented both in Python by NREL [6] and in MATLAB by TU Delft [7]. For sake of consistency with the other model implementations, the MATLAB implementation is leveraged for use in CL-Windcon. This implementation includes vectorized and analytical expressions for the wakes and flow field, pushing the limits of computational efficiency within MATLAB.

6.1.4 Detailed mathematical model derivation

A sketch of the single wake deficit model is displayed in Figure 6.1, where d is the rotor diameter and $R = \frac{d}{2}$ is the rotor radius. The wake model is described as two components, namely the near wake and the far wake, respectively. In this figure, the coordinate system has its origin at the turbine hub, with x positive in downstream direction, aligned with the wind and y is the lateral direction aligned with the blades for the case in which the turbines have zero yaw. Finally, z is the vertical direction, positive in upwards direction.

Figure 6.1: A top view of the single wake modelled by the FLORIS model [5].

The FLORIS model assumes a uniform wind direction throughout the entire farm, independent of wake effects, the turbine yaw angles, or the atmospheric turbulence intensity.

Near-wake region

The near-wake region can be split up into two parts: a “core” and an outer dissipative deficit region. Namely, at the outer edges of the near-wake, the wake transitions into a Gaussian-shaped flow deficit under the assumption of self-similarity, as shown in Figure 6.1. Both this near-wake core and Gaussian-shaped deficit are described in the following paragraphs.

Near-wake core

The near-wake core (interchangeably called the “potential core”) is derived from the analogy between wakes and coflowing jets. This potential core contains a uniform flow velocity and direction, and dissipates gradually as it moves further downstream.

In the FLORIS model, the bounds of the near wake core converge linearly and form an *elliptic cone* in 3D, with its base at the rotor plane and its tip at location x_0 downstream. The base of this cone, the potential core area at $x = 0$, is bigger than the rotor area due to the conservation of mass. This area is an ellipse with vertical major axis φ_z and lateral minor axis φ_y , calculated respectively by equation 6.1 and 6.2:

$$\varphi_z = d \sqrt{\frac{u_R}{u_0}} \quad (6.1)$$

and

$$\varphi_y = d \cos(\gamma) \sqrt{\frac{u_R}{u_0}}, \quad (6.2)$$

with u_R the flow velocity at the rotor. This value is calculated in equation 6.3:

$$u_R = u_\infty \left(\frac{C_T \cos(\gamma)}{2(1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T \cos(\gamma)})} \right). \quad (6.3)$$

The lateral axis slope of this elliptic cone, denoted by θ_{c_0} , is computed as a function of the turbine control settings: the yaw angle γ and the turbine thrust coefficient C_T . This turbine thrust coefficient is calculated using a BEM code such as NREL’s FAST, for a certain inflow wind speed and controller setting. Thus, one could generate a look-up table (LUT) for C_T (and C_p) assuming, e.g., a greedy controller as a function of inflow wind speed. For wind farm control, a LUT for C_T and C_p as a function of inflow wind speed, yaw angle, blade pitch angle, and/or a power setpoint can be generated.

Furthermore, the tip location of this cone, x_0 , is calculated by equation 6.4:

$$x_0 = \frac{\sqrt{2} R \cdot \cos(\gamma) \cdot (1 + \sqrt{1 - C_T})}{\alpha I + \beta (1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T})}, \quad (6.4)$$

Where α and β are tuning parameters that affect the effect of atmospheric turbulence and turbine-induced turbulence on the near-wake core length, respectively. The parameter I is the incoming turbulence intensity at hub height, which is a value between 0 (laminar flow) and 1 (fully turbulent flow). From experimental turbine data, $\alpha = 2.32$ was found by Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [5]. The incoming turbulence intensity I is calculated as an addition of the atmospheric turbulence I_0 and upstream-turbine-induced turbulence I_j^+ , by equation 6.5:

$$I = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \left(\frac{A_w^j}{\pi R^2} I_j^+ \right)^2} + I_0^2, \quad (6.5)$$

with N_t the total number of turbines in the farm, and A_w^j the overlap area of the upstream wake with the turbine rotor in question. The upstream-turbine-induced turbulence I_j^+ is calculated by equation 6.6:

$$I_j^+ = t_a \cdot a^{t_b} \cdot I_0^{t_c} \cdot \left(\frac{x}{d} \right)^{t_d}, \quad (6.6)$$

With a the turbine axial induction factor (which is a function of C_T), and t_a, t_b, t_c, t_d tuning parameters with typical values of $t_a = 0.73, t_b = 0.8325, t_c = 0.0325, t_d = -0.32$, according to Crespo and Hernandez [8]. The induction factor a is calculated here in equation 6.7 as:

$$a = \frac{1}{2 \cos(\gamma)} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T \cos(\gamma)} \right). \quad (6.7)$$

The lateral angle of the near-wake (cone) centreline, θ_{c_0} , is calculated in equation 6.8 as:

$$\theta_{c_0} = \frac{0.3\gamma}{\cos(\gamma)} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T \cos(\gamma)} \right). \quad (6.8)$$

Then, the lateral deflection of the near-wake centreline at location $x \leq x_0$ downstream relative to the rotor centre, δ_n , is calculated in equation 6.9 as:

$$\delta_n = x \tan(\theta_{c_0}) + \delta_{\text{rot}}. \quad (6.9)$$

Here, the latter symbol defines the wake deflection induced by the rotation of the blades, previously seen by Fleming et al. [9]. This effect is included as a linear expression, in equation 6.10 by:

$$\delta_{\text{rot}} = a_d d + b_d x, \quad (6.10)$$

with a_d and b_d tuning variables.

A uniform flow velocity is assumed in the potential core. This flow, aligned with the mean wind direction, has magnitude u_0 , derived from Bernoulli's equation to be, in equation 6.11:

$$u_0 = u_\infty \sqrt{1 - C_T}, \quad (6.11)$$

where u_∞ is the freestream wind velocity. The normalized velocity deficit in the potential core is defined as C_0 , and can straight-forwardly be calculated in equation 6.12 as:

$$C_0 = \frac{u_\infty - u_0}{u_\infty} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T}. \quad (6.12)$$

The uniform flow velocity deficit of the near wake transitions to a Gaussian wake shape at the outer edges, as shown in Figure 6.1. At location x_0 , the near wake ends and a full Gaussian wake is formed.

As seen in Figure 6.1, the uniform flow velocity deficit in the potential core transitions into a Gaussian wake deficit in the y-z plane. This Gaussian wake deficit is also seen in the far-wake region, described in the next paragraph.

Far-wake region

At the onset of the near wake, a fully two-dimensional Gaussian wake has developed, under the assumption in axisymmetry. This wake dissipates as we move further downstream, promoted by the atmospheric and turbine-induced turbulent structures in the wind. The lateral deflection of this far wake δ_f is calculated in equation 6.13 as:

$$\delta_f = \tan(\theta_{c_0}) x_0 + \frac{\theta_{c_0} \cdot E_0}{5.2} \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_{y_0} \cdot \sigma_{z_0}}}{\sqrt{k_y \cdot k_z \cdot M_0}} \cdot \ln \left[\frac{(1.6 + \sqrt{M_0}) \left(1.6 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_y \cdot \sigma_z}{\sigma_{y_0} \cdot \sigma_{z_0}}} - \sqrt{M_0} \right)}{(1.6 - \sqrt{M_0}) \left(1.6 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_y \cdot \sigma_z}{\sigma_{y_0} \cdot \sigma_{z_0}}} + \sqrt{M_0} \right)} \right] + \delta_{rot}, \quad (6.13)$$

with $M_0 = C_0(2 - C_0)$, $E_0 = C_0^2 - 3e^{1/12}C_0 + 3e^{1/3}$, and σ_y and σ_z the standard deviations of the Gaussian in lateral (y-) and vertical (z-) direction, respectively. These are calculated according to equation 6.14:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y &= \sigma_{y_0} + (x - x_0)k_y, \\ \sigma_z &= \sigma_{z_0} + (x - x_0)k_z, \end{aligned} \quad (6.14)$$

With $\sigma_{y_0} = \sigma_{z_0} \cos(\gamma)$ and $\sigma_{z_0} = \frac{d}{2\sqrt{2}}$ the standard deviations at the start of the far-wake, x_0 , and k_y and k_z the linear growth rate of the far wake in their respective dimensions, similar to as in the traditional Jensen model. At the moment, these parameters are assumed to be identical and a function of the local turbulence intensity, as reported in equation 6.15:

$$k_y = k_z = k_a I + k_b, \quad (6.15)$$

where k_a and k_b are tuning parameters with default values of 0.3837 and 0.003678, respectively.

Now that the location and standard deviations of the far-wake Gaussian-shaped wake deficits are known, it is possible to formulate the actual wind speed at any location $x > x_0$ in the wind farm. For no veer case, the normalized wind speed is expressed by equation 6.16:

$$\frac{u_w}{u_\infty} = 1 - C \cdot \exp\left(-\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_y^2}\right)(y - \delta_f)^2 - \left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_z^2}\right)z^2\right), \quad (6.16)$$

with

$$C = 1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sigma_{y0}\sigma_{z0}}{\sigma_y\sigma_z} M_0}.$$

If the effect of wind shear, defined by symbol ω , is added, it is possible to obtain a rotational effect on the Gaussian wake shape. Resulting in equation 6.17:

$$\frac{u_w}{u_\infty} = 1 - C \cdot \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\cos^2 \omega}{2\sigma_y^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \omega}{2\sigma_z^2}\right)(y - \delta_f)^2 + 2\left(\frac{-\sin 2\omega}{4\sigma_y^2} + \frac{\sin 2\omega}{4\sigma_z^2}\right)(z \cdot (y - \delta_f)) - \left(\frac{\sin^2 \omega}{2\sigma_y^2} + \frac{\cos^2 \omega}{2\sigma_z^2}\right)z^2\right). \quad (6.17)$$

Finally, in order to include the effects of a boundary layer, the freestream wind speed u_∞ is reported as a function of the vertical height z , by $u_\infty(z)$. A vertical profile according to the power-law is assumed with wind speed $u_\infty(0)$ at the hub, according to equation 6.18:

$$u_\infty = u_\infty(z) = u_\infty(0) \left(\frac{z+z_{hub}}{z_{hub}}\right)^{\alpha_s}, \quad (6.18)$$

with α_s the shear coefficient. Recall that z is zero at the turbine hub, and z_{hub} is the turbine hub height relative to the ground.

Wake summation and turbine power computations

In the case of multiple wakes, the combined flow velocity deficit is calculated following the method from Katic et al. [4], where a summation of the energy deficit in the wakes is proposed. For a certain location in the wind field, the wind speed at this point (x, y, z) , denoted by u_{farm} , is calculated in figure 6.19 as:

$$u_{farm} = u_\infty \left(1 - \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \left(1 - \frac{u_{w,j}}{u_\infty}\right)^2}\right). \quad (6.19)$$

In order to determine the effective time-averaged power capture for a certain turbine with FLORIS, the wake deficits are combined according to their relative overlap area to form one rotor-averaged and time-averaged turbine wind speed. This is similar to the methodology for calculating the flow field, but now weighted according to the overlap area between each wake and the rotor plane. The

$Q_{R,j}$ is defined as volumetric flow rate over the rotor plane for the wake of upstream turbine j . Its value in the polar plane is determined by equation 6.20:

$$Q_{R,j} = \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \left(r \cdot \left\{ 1 - \frac{u_{w,j}(r,\beta)}{u_\infty(r,\beta)} \right\} \right) d\beta dr, \quad (6.20)$$

with β the azimuth angle, and r the radial distance from the rotor center. The mapping from (r, β) to (x, y, z) follows from basic geometry and is not shown here. The rotor-effective wind speed at a particular turbine is then calculated in equation 6.21 as:

$$u_R = u_\infty(0) \cdot \left[1 - \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \left(\frac{Q_{R,j}}{\pi R^2} \right)^2} \right], \quad (6.21)$$

With $u_\infty(0)$ the freestream wind speed at turbine hub height. Finally, knowing the rotor-averaged wind speed, the power capture of turbine j is straight-forwardly calculated in equation 6.22 as:

$$P_j = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot \pi R^2 \cdot C_p \cdot u_R^3 \cdot \eta \cdot \cos(\gamma)^{Pp}, \quad (6.22)$$

with ρ the air density, C_p the dimensionless turbine power coefficient (function of the control input C_T), and $\eta \leq 1$ a factor to account for turbine losses such as a non-ideal generator. The wind-farm-wide power capture is simply reported in equation 6.23:

$$P_{\text{farm}} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} P_j. \quad (6.23)$$

6.2 Installation and usage

6.2.1 System requirements

The FLORIS model is implemented in MATLAB 2017b, and has been shown to be compatible with older versions (tested for 2016a and upwards). It has no dependencies on toolboxes, and consequently with a bare MATLAB installation it is possible to run it under either PC, Linux or OSX.

6.2.2 Installation instructions

The FLORIS code can be *cloned* from Github for basic use, or *forked* for development and modification. Only the *clone* procedure is shown here. Once Git is installed on the computer (for Windows, Github Desktop [10] is recommended). Now open Git Shell (or a new terminal under Linux), and run the following command:

```
git clone https://github.com/TUDELFT-DataDrivenControl/FLORISSE_M "destination_folder"
```

with [destination_folder](#) being the desired folder location. Git will download the repository to the computer. If there are any changes to the repository online, `cd` to the folder location, and update the repository with the latest changes by:

```
git fetch  
git pull
```

For a more detailed introduction to Git, please see the Git user manual [11].

6.2.3 Folder hierarchy

The folders are arranged in a straight-forward manner.

[FLORISSE_M/](#) – This is the main folder that contains the class file, “*floris.m*”. This couples all the different components together and provides one complete wind farm model object. Furthermore, demo scripts are provided with “*demo_floris.m*”, showing how to perform simulations and optimizations using FLORIS.

[FLORISSE_M/coreFunctions](#) – This folder contains all the core code for the model and the visualization functions. The file names and contents are referred to for more information on individual files.

[FLORISSE_M/developmentTools](#) – This folder contains the backwards compatibility test and a test that runs a range of simulations at specified settings, and compares them to previous results. If the result has changed for any of these simulations, an error dialogue will pop up. This is useful for development and debugging.

[FLORISSE_M/inputFiles](#) – This folder contains the input files for a certain FLORIS simulation. There are two subfolders: one to specify the inputs for the various submodels (“model parameters”), and one to specify the wind farm layout, atmospheric conditions, and turbine control settings.

[FLORISSE_M/subModelDefinitions](#) – This folder contains the code for various wake deficit, wake deflection, and wake superposition submodels that are implemented in the FLORIS tool. The wake deficit submodels include the standard Jensen-based model with three discrete wake zones, but also the Porté-Agel implemented description described in this chapter. Furthermore, the Larsen model has been implemented and a simplified implementation of Jensen with Gaussian wake shapes. For the wake deflection model, the Jimenez and the Porté-Agel model have been implemented. For more details, see the specific files and the literature [1], [5].

6.2.4 Performing a test run

A test run is performed very easily, and a demonstration code, named “demo_floris.m”, is provided. A single simulation can be easily run through the following commands

```
FLORIS = floris(); % This loads the FLORIS model with default settings
FLORIS.run(); % This runs a single simulation with the FLORIS model
```

6.2.5 Setting up a simulation case

Which files to change and how

Setting up a new simulation case consists of a number of files that have to be created or modified.

1. Implementation of wind farm topology and atmospheric conditions

A new wind farm is easily implemented by adding a new file to the [inputFiles/siteDefinitions](#) folder. In this file, the turbine locations (in the inertial frame), the yaw angle and tilt angle of each turbine, the freestream wind speed and wind direction, the freestream turbulence intensity, the air density, and the vertical inflow profile of the wind are specified. For example:

```
% Wind turbine locations in inertial frame [x, y]
inputData.LocIF = 178.3*[14, 10.0;
                       14, 5.0;
                       13.5, 0.0];

nTurbs = size(inputData.LocIF,1); % Number of turbines
inputData.nTurbs = nTurbs; % Save to inputData for usage outside of this function

% Control settings
inputData.yawAngles = zeros(1,nTurbs); % Turbine yaw angles (radians, w.r.t.
wind)
inputData.tiltAngles = zeros(1,nTurbs); % Turbine tilt angles (radians, w.r.t.
ground)

% Atmospheric settings
inputData.windDirection = deg2rad(270.); % Wind dir in radians (inertial frame)
inputData.uInfWf = 8.0; % axial flow speed in wind frame
inputData.TI_0 = .1; % turbulence intensity [-] ex: 0.1 is 10% turbulence
intensity
inputData.airDensity = 1.1716; % Atmospheric air density (kg/m3)

% Inflow (vertical profile)
inputData.shear = .14; % shear exponent (0.14 -> neutral)
hubHeight = 119.0;
inputData.Ufun = @(z) inputData.uInfWf.*(z./hubHeight).^inputData.shear; % Boundary
layer
```

2. Implementation of new turbine in FLORIS

If the turbines in this new simulation are not yet available in FLORIS (see the [turbineDefinitions](#) folder), then it is possible to use the momentum theory (i.e., axial induction factors) to determine the dimensionless aerodynamic power and thrust force coefficients C_p and C_T . However, the axial induction factor has no direct physical interpretation, and the implementation of such a control algorithm on a real turbine is not straight-forward. Hence, look-up tables for C_p and C_T are used instead, generated typically using some aero-elastic solver. In this case, the FAST solver from NREL has been used to generate these tables.

Recently, OpenFAST [12] has the possibility to extract the rotor aerodynamic power, torque and thrust coefficients as a function of time. Note that the C_T value provided by FAST includes gravity terms, which should be nullified before implementing it into FLORIS, through equation 6.24:

$$T = 0.5\rho\pi R^2 u_R^2 C_{T,FAST} - M_{\text{rotor}} g \sin(\vartheta) \quad (6.24)$$

$$C_T = \frac{T}{0.5\rho\pi R^2 u_R^2}$$

where T is the rotor aerodynamic torque, ϑ is the rotor tilt angle, g is the gravitational acceleration, and M_{rotor} is the rotor mass.

The C_p and C_T should correspond to time-averaged values for some turbine operation. For wind farm control, this means we have to make it a function of some derating parameter, e.g., the collective blade pitch angle. Additionally, the internal turbine controller makes C_p and C_T also different for each incoming mean wind speed u_R . This is how wind farm control is implemented for the NREL 5MW turbine – through a two-dimensional look-up table of C_p and C_T as a function of u_R and the collective blade pitch angle.

Alternatively, if FLORIS is only used for e.g. layout studies, a two-dimensional LUT of C_p and C_T as a function of u_R and the collective blade pitch angle is not needed. Rather, it is possible to make a one-dimensional LUT of C_p and C_T as a function of u_R , assuming greedy control. This objective has been set in the internal turbine controller in the FAST simulation, and run FAST over a range of turbulent wind speeds.

In the current implementation, the turbine files are arranged as follows:

[turbineDefinitions/nrel5mw/cpctgreedy.mat](#) – this file holds the C_p and C_T look-up tables as a function of u_R , generated from FAST. These FAST simulations were run under a turbulent inflow and with greedy control as the internal turbine controller’s objective.

[turbineDefinitions/nrel5mw/cpPitch.csv](#) – this file holds the two-dimensional C_p look-up table as a function of u_R and the collective blade pitch angle, generated from FAST. These FAST simulations were run under a turbulent inflow and with an internal wind turbine controller, in which the minimum allowed collective blade pitch angle was changed from its nominal value.

[turbineDefinitions/nrel5mw/ctPitch.csv](#) – this file holds the two-dimensional C_T look-up table as a function of u_R and the collective blade pitch angle, generated from FAST. These FAST simulations were run under a turbulent inflow and with an internal wind turbine controller, in which the minimum allowed collective blade pitch angle was changed from its nominal value.

Once these tables are generated with the identical naming as before, it is also needed to create a [specifications.m](#) file in the turbine folder in FLORIS. This file contains some basic parameters of the turbine, namely:

```
turbine = struct(...
    'rotorRadius', 126.4/2., ...
    'genEfficiency', 0.944, ...
    'hubHeight', 90.0, ...
    'pP', 1.88 ); % yaw power correction parameter
```

Finally, the new turbine can be specified by calling FLORIS(...) with the new turbine folder name.

3. Tuning of model parameters

A common problem using steady-state models, to which FLORIS is no exception, is the tuning of the model parameters. Namely, FLORIS includes several turbulence and wake parameters, which are not straight-forwardly chosen for a different wind farm topology.

The collective set of tuning parameters of interest \mathfrak{N} has been defined. Then, for a certain set of turbine control parameters u_t , a number of simulations N_s is run in a high-fidelity LES solver (or from wind tunnel experiments), and time-average the power. The optimal parameter is found by solving the following optimization problem.

$$\mathfrak{N}_{\text{opt}} = \underset{\mathfrak{N}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_i^{N_s} \left(\sum_k^{N_T} [P_{i,\text{measured}}(u_t) - P_{i,\text{FLORIS}}^k(\mathfrak{N}, u_t)]^2 \right)$$

In this equation, the inner sum corresponds to the sum of squared errors (SSE) between each single turbine’s time-averaged power measurement and the power of this turbine predicted by FLORIS. The outer sum corresponds to the summation of these SSEs for each specific simulation.

To avoid the situation of overfitting (i.e., the situation where parameters are chosen to perfectly match given measured data, yet do not improve or reduce accuracy of the FLORIS model for other cases), it is needed to pay attention to two factors:

- i. A sufficient amount of measurement data should be fed into this optimization. Specifically, the following cases should be covered: various atmospheric conditions (turbulence intensity, wind speed, wind direction), various turbine control settings (blade pitch angles, yaw angles), wind farm layouts (longitudinal and lateral turbine spacing for two turbines, and simulations with at least one row of three or more turbines). Note that it's also possible to opt to include flow field measurements into the cost function, but this is left out for simplicity. This approach to include flow field measurements can be straight-forwardly extended.
- ii. It's not recommended to attempt to optimize all the parameters in one shot, as this may lead to overfitting (e.g., divergence of parameter pairs that counteract each other's impact on power). It can be performed a sensitivity analysis instead to see the effect of a single parameter on the power at a certain wind speed, wind direction, turbulence intensity and wind farm layout. Parameters that contribute very little to the power should not be tuned in these situations. Simulations in which a group of parameters has a large influence of the predicted power should be tuned accordingly.

Commonly, the turbine parameters are tuned separately using single turbine simulations (e.g., parameter pP). Wake deficit and wake deflection parameters are tuned in smaller sets using a combination of two-turbine and multiple-turbine simulations.

6.3 Performing simulations

6.3.1 Generic 3 turbine case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository, under "clwindcon_3turb". Since FLORIS calculates everything in the wind-aligned frame, both frames are displayed below in figure 6.2:

Figure 6.2: Turbine layout in FLORIS for the generic 3-turbine wind farm

An example simulation would produce a flow field similar to as shown next.

Figure 6.3: Turbine layout in FLORIS for the generic 3-turbine wind farm

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the FLORIS model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

6.3.2 Generic 9 turbine case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository under “clwindcon_9turb.m”. The layout and an example flowfield are provided in figure 6.5

Figure 6.5: Turbine layout in FLORIS for the generic 9-turbine wind farm

Figure 6.6: Flow field in FLORIS for the generic 9-turbine wind farm

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the FLORIS model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

6.3.3 Generic 80 turbine (offshore) case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository under the filename “clwindcon_80turb.m”. The layout and an example flowfield are provided in figure 6.7. Note that two turbines seem to be missing on the bottom row, between turbines 21 and 30, and between turbines 55 and 64. These are substations, as this virtual wind farm is considered offshore.

Figure 6.7: Turbine layout in FLORIS for the offshore 80-turbine wind farm

Figure 6.8: Flow field in FLORIS for the offshore 80-turbine wind farm

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the FLORIS model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

6.3.4 Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case

How to set it up

Turbine model

Test G1 turbine model has been implemented on the Github repository under “turbineDefinitions/TUM_G1/specifications.m”.

```
turbine = struct( ...  
    'rotorRadius', 1.1/2., ...  
    'genEfficiency', 1.000, ...  
    'hubHeight', 0.825, ...  
    'pP', 1.787); % yaw power correction parameter
```

In accordance to the turbine description in Deliverable 3.1. (D3.1, 4. Description of wind turbines) the G1 rotor radius is set to 0.55m and hub height to 0.825 m. The generator is efficiency set to 1 in order to account for the fact that the recorded turbine torque measurement (D3.1, Table 7) is corrected for drive friction losses and therefore reports the aerodynamic torque. The yaw power correction parameter pP is set to 1.787 as previously identified [13].

The ‘greedy’ lookup tables for power and thrust coefficients have been computed based on the G1 regulation trajectory w.r.t. wind speed (D3.1, Table 4). The lookup table is stored in “turbineDefinitions/TUM_G1/cpctgreedy.mat”. The values for power and thrust coefficient are shown in Figure 6.9.

Wind farm topology and atmospheric conditions

Serving as an example, the wind farm topology and atmospheric conditions of a scaled wind farm have been implemented according to the scaled wind tunnel tests of the second entry (Wind tunnel testing, Second entry October 2017).

The two wind turbines are longitudinally displaced by 5D and laterally by 0.5D. The ambient turbulence intensity and boundary layer can be set to an onshore or offshore configuration with parameters given in D3.1 (3.3 Typology of flow within the wind tunnel test chambers).

Here, the turbine yaw angle of the upstream turbine is set to 30 degrees. The corresponding site definition file can be found in the repository under “inputFiles/siteDefinitions/generic_2turb_scaled.m”.

Figure 6.9: Lookup table for power- and thrust coefficient (C_P , C_T) as function of wind speed for scaled turbine model G1.

```
% Wind turbine locations in inertial frame [x, y]
inputData.LocIF_D = [0 0; 5 +0.5]; % Wind turbine location in inertial frame
inputData.LocIF = inputData.LocIF_D*1.1;

nTurbs = size(inputData.LocIF,1); % Number of turbines
inputData.nTurbs = nTurbs;

% Control settings
inputData.yawAngles = zeros(1,nTurbs);
inputData.yawAngles(1)= deg2rad(30);
inputData.tiltAngles = zeros(1,nTurbs); % Set default as greedy

% Atmospheric settings
inputData.windDirection = deg2rad(0); % Wind dir in radians (inertial frame)
inputData.uInfWf = 5.65; % axial flow speed in wind frame

% Offshore configuration (D3.1, 3.3 Typology of flow within the wind tunnel)
inputData.TI_0 = 0.06; % Onshore: 0.12
inputData.shear = 0.079; % Onshore: 0.20
inputData.airDensity = 1.1770; % Atmospheric air density (kg/m3)

% Inflow (vertical profile)
inputData.Ufun = @(z) inputData.uInfWf.*(z./0.83).^inputData.shear; %Log-
profile
```

Demonstration

A demo of the above described turbine and topology can be run by executing the script “demo_floris_G1.m” on the Github repository. A visualization of the flow velocities at hub height is shown in Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.10: Flow velocities at hub height for a scaled 2-turbine test case with offshore configuration.

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the FLORIS model will be tuned according to wind tunnel data in following work.

6.3.5 Sedini real wind farm case

How to set it up

Since the exact simulations conditions for the Sedini wind farm are still under definition, this simulation case has not been implemented yet. The tuning parameters need to be matched to higher-fidelity data, such as large-eddy simulation data or field data. Depending on the quality of the field measurements, one or the other may be opted for, or a combination of both.

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the FLORIS model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

6.4 References

1. Annoni, J., Fleming, P., Scholbrock, A., Roadman, J., Dana, S., Adcock, C., Schlipf, D. (2018). Analysis of Control-Oriented Wake Modeling Tools Using Lidar Field Results. *Wind Energ. Sci. Discuss.*, 2018, 1-17. doi:10.5194/wes-2018-6
2. Bastankhah, M., & Porté-Agel, F. (2014). A new analytical model for wind-turbine wakes. *Renewable Energy*, 70, 116-123. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.01.002>
3. Niayifar, A., & Porté-Agel, F. (2016). Analytical Modeling of Wind Farms: A New Approach for Power Prediction. *Energies*, 9(9), 741.
4. Katic, I., Højstrup, J., & Jensen, N. O. (1987). A Simple Model for Cluster Efficiency. *EWEA Conference and Exhibition 1986*, 407-410.
5. Bastankhah, M., & Porté-Agel, F. (2016). Experimental and theoretical study of wind turbine wakes in yawed conditions. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 806, 506-541. doi:10.1017/jfm.2016.595
6. NREL. (2018). Github: WISDEM/FLORIS - A control-oriented wake model. Retrieved from <https://github.com/WISDEM/FLORIS>
7. TUDelft. (2018). Github: TUDelft-DataDrivenControl/FLORISSE_M - An exhaustive MATLAB implementation of the steady-state FLORIS wind farm model. Retrieved from https://github.com/TUDelft-DataDrivenControl/FLORISSE_M
8. Crespo, A., & Hernandez, J. (1996). Turbulence characteristics in wind-turbine wakes. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 61, 71-85
9. Fleming P., Annoni, J., Churchfield, M., Martinez, L., Gruchalla, K., Lawson, M., & Moriarty, P. (2017). From wake steering to flow control. *Wind Energ. Sci. Discuss.*, 2017, 1-17. doi:10.5194/wes-2017-52
10. Github. (2018). Github Desktop - Simple collaboration from your desktop. Retrieved from <https://desktop.github.com/>
11. Git. (2018). Git - user-manual Documentation. Retrieved from <https://git-scm.com/docs/user-manual.html>
12. NREL. (2018). OpenFAST User Documentation: AeroDyn Input Files. Retrieved from: <https://openfast.readthedocs.io/en/master/source/user/aerodyn/appendix.html>
13. Schreiber, J., Nanos, E. M., Campagnolo, F., & Bottasso, C. L. (2017). Verification and Calibration of a Reduced Order Wind Farm Model by Wind Tunnel Experiments. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 854. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/854/1/012041

7 SIMWINDFARM

7.1 Model description

7.1.1 Description summary

The SimWindFarm (SWF) toolbox is initially developed as part of the [<http://www.ict-aeolus.eu> Aeolus FP7] project and is aimed at providing a fast wind farm simulation environment for development of wind farm control algorithms.

7.1.2 Model purpose

There has been made a lot of research on wind farm control strategies based on static models Brand and Wagenaar (2010). To increase the confidence in the results also dynamic wind farm simulation tools has been developed. The state of the art in this category is SOWFA Churchfield and Lee (2013); Fleming et al. (2013). The high fidelity of SOWFA comes with the cost of long simulation time. The main idea with SimWindFarm is to fit in between these two extremes. The main purpose was to be used as a simulator for testing wind farm controllers.

7.1.3 Model specifications

SWF is designed as a Simulink toolbox, which can generate wind farm models based on the users choice of layout and turbine. The Simulink model generated has the structure shown in Figure 7.1. The two main elements are the turbines block and the wind field block. The turbines block simulates the dynamics of the wind turbines based on wind speed and power set point. Each of the turbines produce a standard set of outputs to be used during the design of the farm controller along with the thrust coefficient of the individual turbines, used to calculate the wake effects. Included are also an example farm controller, network controller and grid models, which can be replaced with whatever models or algorithms the control designer wants. The example farm controller is a simple proportional distribution algorithm, which distributes the power reference to the turbines based on a simple estimate of its current production capacity and the total power demand from the network operator.

The SimWindFarm toolbox supports the following features:

- Simulation of wind farms with arbitrary layout
- Automatic generation of wind farm models

- Integration into Simulink
- Simple farm control and network operation
- Fatigue analysis

Figure 7.1: Top level structure of SWF as illustrated by the Simulink diagram.

The following turbine models are available:

- NREL5MW This is the well known virtual turbine from NREL Jonkman et al. (2009).
- DTU10MW This is the newer virtual turbine from the UpWind project Bak et al. (2013).
- DTU10MWCLWC This is the DT10MW with the CLWindcon controller (OpenDiscon).

7.1.4 Detailed mathematical derivation

The detailed mathematical derivation is given in Appendix A.

7.2 Installation and usage

7.2.1 System requirements

The toolbox requires Matlab/Simulink. The current release (v1.2) is tested with matlab version R2017b on Ubuntu LTS16.04. SimWindFarm should run on the platforms that supports

Matlab/Simulink. The earlier versions of SimWindFarm has been tested with earlier versions of Matlab back to at least 2010a.

7.2.2 Installation instructions

The toolbox is available via GitHub (TBD). Previous versions, up to and including V1.1, are available in zipped format by the link <http://www.ict-aeolus.eu/SimWindFarm/simwindfarm-v1.1.zip>.

For easiest use of the toolbox write permissions to the Matlab path-file are needed. Else to redo the install every time Matlab is started or to set the necessary paths is needed.

- Download (and unzip) the software to a suitable location
- Run `install.m`
- Alternatively to running `install.m` the necessary path can be set by something like `addpath(genpath('Directory with SimWindFarm files'), '-end');`
- Open the Simulink Library browser and there should be a new SimWindFarm item
- Note that an installed Matlab mex compiler (run `mex -setup`) is needed.

The wind data can be generated using the m functions `gen_windfield*.m`. A precalculated wind field can also be downloaded at http://www.ict-aeolus.eu/SimWindFarm/benchmarkwind_no_taylor.mat. Remember to check if it fits the application.

7.2.3 Folder hierarchy

The directory structure is very flat with most files at the root. Only 4 sub directories are used: `DTU10MW`, `nrel5mw`, `mcrunch` and `private`. The first two holds information on the DTU10MW and NREL5MW turbines and the last two has files on fatigue etc.

7.2.4 Setting up a simulation case

In earlier versions of SimWindFarm it was possible to construct wind farm Simulink models solely by using a dialog started by double clicking e.g. `Farm_Template`. This seems not to work presently with ubuntu 16.04 and Matlab 2017b. Alternatively, a programmatic approach can be followed as explained below.

Which files to change and how

Wind is generated by running `GenWind.m`. In this file the farm geometry, turbine name, mean wind speed, turbulence intensity, size of wind field and simulation time are specified. The file, `GenWind.m`, and the next ones mentioned here, are supposed to be self explanatory.

The farm is generated by running `GenWindFarm.m`. In this file the turbine name and wind data are specified.

The wind turbine parameters used by the turbine block in Simulink are stored in various matlab structs `env`, `pub` and `wt`. Examples of setting these parameters are found in `./nrel5mw/nrelvals.m` and `./DTU10MW/DTU10MWPar.m` for the NREL5MW and DTU10MW turbine respectively.

- `env` only holds the air density in `env.rho`.
- `pub` holds rotor radius, rated power and fatigue parameters.

```
pub =  
    struct with fields:  
        rotor: [1x1 struct]  
        rated: 5000000  
        tower: [1x1 struct]  
        shaft: [1x1 struct]
```

- `wt` holds everything else needed in the dynamic model including the controller.

```
wt =  
    struct with fields:  
        cp: [1x1 struct]  
        ct: [1x1 struct]  
        blade: [1x1 struct]  
        hub: [1x1 struct]  
        nac: [1x1 struct]
```

```

tower: [1x1 struct]
  gen: [1x1 struct]
  rotor: [1x1 struct]
  pitch: [1x1 struct]
  top: [1x1 struct]
  ctrl: [1x1 struct]
  meas: [1x1 struct]
    
```

Farm controller configuration

The build in farm controller, shown in Figure 7.2, is only meant as a simple example.

Figure 7.2: Simple farm controller used in SWF.

In previous versions, it sends specific power set points to the turbines based on measured turbine powers and nacelle wind speed. Also it outputs an estimate of available power to the system operator block in Figure 7.1. Notice also that the single turbine controller for the first two turbines NREL5MW and DTU10MW only has an input for the power reference. Derating is then only possible by setting this power reference lower than available power. A probably better way of derating, below rated, is relative power derating which is included in the DTU10MWCLWC turbine controller.

Therefore, the current version of the farm controller m script includes both options for absolute and relative derating. A Mode switch is used to select different modes as follows:

- Mode= 0: Original distribution after available power using absolute power reference.
- Mode= 1: Original distribution after available power but using relative derating.
- Mode= 2: Open loop signal.
- Mode= 3: Full power on all turbines.

All the above modes can, of course, be changed by the user of SWF by building/rebuilding blocks to SWF.

Single turbine controller based on NREL5MW

For the two turbines NREL5MW and DTU10MW the single turbine controllers are based on the NREL5MW controller documented in Jonkman et al. (2009). This controller is build using Simulink blocks and the parameters are given in the struct wt. For example the proportional gain in the PI pitch controller parameters are in wt.ctrl.pitch.Pgain with the rest of the parameters being:

```
wt.ctrl.pitch =  
    struct with fields:  
        beta: [476x1 double]  
        pwr: [1000000 2000000 3000000 4000000 5000000 5290000]  
        gs: [6x476 double]  
        Pgain: -0.1965  
        Igain: -0.0842  
        ratelim: 8  
        ulim: 90  
        llim: 0
```

Single turbine controller based on OpenDiscon

For the third turbine DTU10MWCLWC the controller is written in C and then implemented in Simulink via a wrapper. The parameters and the algorithms in this controller can be changed by changing them in the C code. See <https://github.com/ielorza/OpenDiscon> for more information on this controller.

OpenDiscon provides the means to integrate the CL-Windcon controller in a Simulink model via a C MEX S-Function. This requires a C mex compiler (e.g. gcc for Linux; run `mex -setup` in Matlab to see if it is there). Download, compilation and use are as follows:

1. Clone OpenDiscon with Git: open the directory where you wish OpenDiscon to be cloned in a terminal and run

```
git clone https://github.com/ielorza/OpenDiscon.git
```

2. Checkout the right branch: OpenDiscon is actively developed by IK4-IKERLAN, so the latest features are likely to be in the dev branch. To see all branches, open your local OpenDiscon directory in a terminal and run

```
gitk -a
```

To checkout the dev branch run

```
git checkout dev
```

NOTE: you are by no means limited to the dev branch. OpenDiscon is a regular Git repository, and you may navigate its versions with Git at will. For comprehensive Git documentation visit <https://git-scm.com/doc>.

3. Initialize and update submodules: OpenDiscon uses OpenWitcon as a submodule. To initialize and update it, run

```
git submodule init
```

```
git submodule update
```

That will checkout the right version of OpenWitcon for your version of OpenDiscon.

4. Create the build directory: OpenDiscon needs to be built prior to its use, so you need a directory for that build. Open your local OpenDiscon directory in a terminal and run

```
mkdir build
```

```
cd build
```

```
cmake -DISTRIBUTION=S-Function ..
```

This will create a directory called 'build' and will put some files in it. The ones needed are:

- (a) `makeOpenDiscon.m` : this contains a function for easy compilation.
- (b) `OpenDiscon_block.mdl` : this contains an OpenDiscon Simulink block for use in Simulink models.

NOTE: SimWindFarm's DTU10MWCLWC turbine model already includes the OpenDiscon block, but you still need to compile OpenDiscon for it to work.

5. Compile OpenDiscon: for the OpenDiscon Simulink block to work, it needs a MEX S-Function. To get it, open the 'build' directory in Matlab and run

```
makeOpenDiscon
```

That will build a file called 'OpenDiscon.mexa64', or something similar, depending on your system. Put it where Matlab can find it when you run your Simulink model.

OpenDiscon controller parameters are modifiable at compile time. All CL-Windcon controller parameters are documented in the OpenDiscon documentation. To build it, after steps 1-3 above, open your local OpenDiscon directory in a terminal and run

```
cd doc
```

```
doxygen
```

This will build html documentation in a directory called 'html'. To browse it, open file 'html/index.html'. The CL-Windcon controller parameters, including how to modify them, are documented in `html/clwindcon.html`. They are all defined as constants in file:

```
CONFIGURATION/CL-Windcon/src/ikClwindconWTConfig/ikClwindconWTConfig.c
```

NOTE: the controller allows for considerably more flexibility than that achieved by modifying these parameters, which merely provide a conveniently high-level approach for those without the time or inclination for lower-level parameter modification. The same source file is a good example of how one would go about said lower-level work, and the rest of the OpenDiscon documentation goes into much detail about it.

After modification of OpenDiscon parameters, it is necessary to repeat step 5 above for the changes to take effect.

7.3 Performing simulations

7.3.1 Generic 3 turbine case

The first example is in partial load where the effect of derating is easy to see. The following parameters are chosen:

- wind speed 8 m/s
- Turbulence intensity 0.1
- Direction along the row
- Time 1200 sec.
- Operation mode
- Full power
- At start: Full power, at 400 sec 0.2 derating of front turbine, 800 sec. 0.2 derating of second turbine

Wind field generation

The wind field is generated by running `GenWind.m`. The body of this file is listed below and should be self explanatory.

```

%% Parameters
PlotWind= 1; PrintStats=1;
% The farm has three turbines, all of them the DTU10MW turbine
TurbineName= 'DTU10MWCLWC';
D= 178.3; % Find in parameters if possible
% The position of the turbines.
% (make sure that the turbines are within the grid of the wind field)
% CLWINDCON 3 turbine farm in CLWINDCON orientation where wind is blowing
% in the y direction and in rotor diameters
farm.pos=[0 0 0.5; %X values
          0 5 10]; %Y values;
% File and dir name
FileName='CLWindcon3WTWind.mat';
DirName= './';
% Average wind speed in m/s
U0= 8;
% Turbulence intensity
% 2018-02-27 10:26:36 tk: Notice that the below gives a turbulence
intensity of
% Sigmau/Ua= Ti*(0.75*Ua+5.6)/Ua i.e. not Ti which is strange
% See gen_windfield_no_taylor.m for details
Ti= 0.1; % For following the used
          % specifications IEC 61400-1(2005)

```

```

Ti= 0.1*U0/(0.75*U0+5.6);           % For exactly Ti on single wind
speeds
% Grid spacing in m
d= 15;
% Length of the wind field in m
Lx= 2e3;
% Width of the wind field in m
Ly= 1e3;
% Maximum simulation time in s
SimTime= 1200;

%% Definitions etc.
% Give all turbines the same name
farm.turbines= repmat({TurbineName},1,size(farm.pos,2));
% SimWindFarm has wind along the x-axis so rotate -pi/2 and scale with D;
% Rotate by v using [cos(v) -sin(v); sin(v) cos(v)]
farm.pos= [0 1; -1 0]*farm.pos*D;

%% Algorithm
% Generate the wind field
wind= gen_windfield_no_taylor(U0,Ti,d,Lx,Ly,farm,SimTime);
% Save the wind field
save([DirName FileName],'wind');

```

Wind farm generation

The wind farm is generated by running `GenWindFarm.m`. The body of this file is listed below:

```

%% Parameters
% The farm has three turbines, all of them the DTU10MW turbine
TurbineName= 'DTU10MWCLWC';           % With CLWindcon controller
D= 178.3;                               % Find in parameters if possible
% The position of the turbines should be available e.g. from GenWind.m.
% Filename
slxfile='CLWindcon3WT.slx';
DirName= './';

%% Definitions etc.
% Give all turbines the same name
farm.turbines= repmat({TurbineName},1,size(farm.pos,2));
slxname= slxfile(1:end-4);               % Exclude extension
% Load the wind data used
l=load('CLWindcon3WTWind.mat');
wind=l.wind;

%% Algorithm
% Generate the wind farm
gen_windfarm_no_taylor_add_turbulence(slxfile,DirName,farm,wind);
% Open wind farm Simulink diagram
open(slxfile);

```

The last line of code above opens a Simulink model which should look like figure 7.1. This model should be able to run in both normal and accelerator mode.

Results

The Simulink file can now be run in the model window. The results can be accessed in many ways e.g. by using the Simulink "simulation data inspector", which is opened by clicking the small symbols looking like a WI-FI symbol at the input and outputs from the blocks. In addition, the simulation generates an output structure `log sout` (Simulink.SimulationData.Dataset) which holds many signals. Based on `log sout` the file `PlotSimOutput.m` plots some of the most relevant signals as seen below in figure 7.3

Figure 7.3: 3 wind turbine case simulated at 8 m/s with all turbines at max power. Legend: blue, front turbine, red, middle turbine and yellow, last turbine.

Figure 7.4: 3 wind turbine case simulated at 8 m/s with the front turbines derated in steps as indicated in subplot 3.

The first subplot is the nacelle wind speed. The second is the total turbulence, included added turbulence. The third is not absolute power demand but power derating demand. Fourth subplot is the pitch, fifth, the generator speed and sixth, the generator power. In Figure 7.3 the Mode switch in the farm controller is 3 while it is 2 in Figure 7.4.

7.4 References

- C. Bak, F. Zahle, R. Bitsche, T. Kim, A. Yde, L. C. Henriksen, A. Natarajan, and M. H. Hansen. Description of the dtu 10 mw reference wind turbine. Technical Report Report-I-0092, DTU Wind Energy, 2013.
- A. Brand and J. Wagenaar. A quasi-steady wind farm flow model in the context of distributed control of the wind farm. In *European Wind Energy Conference and Exhibition (EWEC), April 20-23, 2010, Warsaw, Poland*. EWEA, EWEA, 2010.
- M. Churchfield and S. Lee. Nwtc design codes - sowfa.
<http://wind.nrel.gov/designcodes/simulators/SOWFA/>, 2013.
- P. Fleming, P. Gebraad, M. Churchfield, S. Lee, K. Johnson, J. Michalakes, J.-W. van Wingerden, and P. Moriarty. Sowfa + super controller user's manual. Technical Report Technical Report NREL/TP-5000-59197, National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), 2013.
- J. Jonkman, S. Butterfield, W. Musial, and G. Scott. Definition of a 5-mw reference wind turbine for offshore system development. Technical Report NREL/TP-500-38060, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 1617 Cole Boulevard, Golden, Colorado, USA, 2009.

8 LONGSIM

8.1 Model description

8.1.1 Description summary

This model is a development of a time-domain simulation model with the working name “LongSim”, developed by DNV GL since 2012 to help tune supervisory control parameters of a single turbine in the context of site-specific long-term wind conditions, as reported in [1]. To capture the important turbine control dynamics it runs with a timestep of around 1 second, and yet it can run very long simulations (several years if necessary), driven by site-specific met mast data, in order to capture the statistics of relatively infrequent supervisory control events which depend on low-frequency variations in meteorological conditions.

This combination of short timesteps and long simulation times is ideal for testing wind farm controllers over changing wind conditions. DNV GL has therefore extended this model to cover a whole wind farm, by generating a correlated wind field over the whole farm, adding a dynamic model for wake effects, extending the turbine controllers to respond to wind farm controller demands, and adding a wind farm controller to generate these demands.

An illustration of the use of the model for testing wind farm controllers is reported in [2]. DNV GL investigations to date have used a generic 2MW turbine model.

8.1.2 Model purpose

This model has been developed for internal use by DNV GL, for the purpose of exploring the possibilities of wind farm control, and testing and evaluating wind farm control algorithms in a realistic dynamic environment. The model is designed for low computational cost so that different control options can be investigated rapidly. Although starting with relatively low-fidelity empirical models, the intention is to allow more sophisticated models to be implemented easily when this becomes appropriate.

8.1.3 Model specifications

Computational cost	To run in real time on a typical laptop for a wind farm of ~100 turbines
Turbine aerodynamics	C_p & C_T as functions of tip speed ratio, pitch angle, yaw misalignment
Turbine dynamics	Rotor speed, pitch & yaw

Turbine control	Generator torque, blade pitch, and yaw control
Turbine loads	Database look-up from previous high-fidelity <i>Bladed</i> simulations
Timestep	~ 1 second
Input wind data	Met mast 10-minute averages (or other sources)
Simulation length	Hours to years
Wind field	Low frequencies correlated across farm, evolving as it advects
Wake profile	Ainslie model initially
Wake turbulence	Quarton-Ainslie model initially
Wake meandering	Driven by low-frequency turbulence in wind field
Wake advection	Driven by low-frequency wind field with wake deficit modification
Wake deflection	Jimenez model initially
Wind farm control	Power delta and yaw offset

8.1.4 Detailed mathematical derivation

Turbine aerodynamics

2D look-up tables of power and thrust coefficients are generated from the simulation tool *Bladed* [23], as a function of tip speed ratio and pitch angle.

The effect of yaw misalignment is important for this project, firstly to be able to predict power production accurately given the inevitable yaw misalignment variations which occur in practice and in the model, and secondly to be able to model deliberate yaw misalignments due to wake steering control.

Using a set of *Bladed* runs with steady wind conditions, an empirical fit for the effect of yaw misalignment was derived for the generic 2MW turbine. There is some concern about the ability of BEM models, as in *Bladed*, to predict the aerodynamic effect of yaw misalignment accurately, but default settings in the latest *Bladed* versions, including the Glauert skewed wake correction, are believed to provide a reasonable representation in most typical conditions. For this particular turbine, the effect of yaw could be approximated by equation 8.1:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta, \gamma) \approx C_p(\lambda, \beta) \cdot (\cos \gamma)^{f(\beta)} \quad (8.1)$$

where λ is the tip speed ratio, β the collective pitch angle and γ the yaw angle. The polynomial expression $f(\beta) = a + b\beta + c\beta^2$ was found to give a reasonable fit with $a = 1.476$, $b = 3.2715$ and $c = 15.783$. There has been some debate over the way in which wind turbine power decreases with yaw angle, with a cubic relationship to $\cos(\gamma)$ often assumed, but measurements often suggest a smaller exponent such as 1.5 – 2. The above expression gives an exponent of about 1.4 at fine pitch (-2° for this turbine).

A more general interpolation-based approach has now been implemented. Again using steady *Bladed* runs, a $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ surface is constructed for a non-zero yaw angle γ_0 (e.g. 30°), and the difference from the zero-yaw surface is calculated as $\Delta C_p(\lambda, \beta, \gamma_0)$. For any yaw angle, C_p is then obtained from equation 8.2:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta, \gamma) = C_p(\lambda, \beta, 0) + \Delta C_p(\lambda, \beta, \gamma_0) \cdot (1 - \cos(\gamma)) / (1 - \cos(\gamma_0)) \quad (8.2)$$

Similar interpolation can be used between multiple $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ surfaces calculated at different yaw angles.

Note: *LongSim* can also run from steady power and thrust curves as a function of wind speed, but turbine dynamics are then not modelled. This simplified option is sufficient for certain supervisory control optimisations, but is not sufficient for the purposes of this project.

Turbine dynamics

A simple dynamic model is used, consistent with using a timestep in the region of 1 second, so higher frequency structural dynamics are not represented. The rotor speed and blade pitch degrees of freedom are implemented, together with nacelle yaw. The first tower fore-aft mode could be readily implemented if desired.

Sensor and actuator responses currently modelled are:

- Speed sensor time constant
- Generator torque actuation time constant
- Pitch actuation time constant and/or second-order response
- Yawing at constant rate

Turbine control – power production

Standard PI(D)-based torque and collective pitch control are implemented, with pitch gain scheduling. Below-rated C_p -tracking uses either a standard quadratic gain or a look-up table.

Transitions at rated wind speed between torque and pitch control use bias terms. All these features are defined in [3]. The bias terms are calculated from an estimated wind speed, for which a Luenberger observer is available, but an ideal estimator using the rotor-average wind speed is usually allowable given the time step used.

Delta control is implemented as described in [4]. The estimated wind speed drives a parallel representation of the turbine and controller dynamics without delta control (and without yaw misalignment) to define the maximum power available at any instant. The power delta is subtracted from this, and the torque demand to the power converter is reduced by the amount necessary to achieve this reduced power. At the same time, the fine pitch is increased to maintain the desired rotor speed. The net result is that the power reduction is achieved by increasing the pitch angle while keeping the same rotor speed.

Turbine control - supervisory

Supervisory control (including yaw control) is flexibly implemented. A syntax is provided so that the user can define typical filters and alarms. Filters are typically low-pass filters for generator speed, yaw misalignment (wind vane signal), wind speed (nacelle anemometer) etc. Alarms can respond to filter outputs using conditions, which can include thresholds and durations (time since threshold crossing), latches, etc. Nacelle anemometry corrections for rotor influence are assumed to be included in the calibrations.

Turbine loads

To run fast, the turbine model does not include structural dynamics nor spatial variations in turbulence across the rotor, and it is therefore not suitable for generating fatigue loads during the simulation. Fatigue loads are therefore obtained in a post-processing step using a Fatigue Loads Database (FLD), pre-calculated for a single turbine, using a detailed *Bladed* model, with full structural dynamics, turbulence, control etc. Damage equivalent loads are calculated for 10-minute simulations over a range of wind speeds, turbulence intensities, yaw misalignments, delta set-points, etc. and stored in a multi-dimensional look-up table.

This is a pragmatic approach, but some deficiencies should be addressed in the future. In particular, wake turbulence does not have the same characteristics as ambient turbulence with just an increase in turbulence intensity; and low-frequency variations such as wake meandering will also affect the fatigue loading to some extent.

Wind field

The wind field is made up of low-frequency and high-frequency variations. This is done in order to minimise computation requirements while maintaining the most important features of the wind field. The boundary between the low and high frequency regions is defined by a user-specified cut-off wavelength, typically corresponding to a spatial resolution of around two turbine diameters ($\Delta x = 2D$). Lower-frequency variations are correlated across the wind farm, making use of coherence functions, and are also assumed to drive wake meandering. Higher-frequency variations are assumed to be uncorrelated between turbines. They affect the turbine behaviour and loads, but do not affect wake meandering.

The entire wind field is generated starting from single-point measured data from e.g. a met mast, usually consisting of 10-minute averages of wind speed, direction and standard deviation. The first step is to generate a smooth time history of wind speed and direction such that each 10-minute section has the correct (measured) mean value, and whose value and gradient are continuous at the 10-minute boundaries. This can be done by selecting start and end values and gradients for each 10-minute section, and fitting a quartic function in between. Synthetic turbulence is then added to this smooth time history. In the absence of faster-sampled data, the form of the turbulence spectrum needs to be assumed, e.g. the Kaimal spectrum, but the amplitude of the turbulence is then scaled to match the measured standard deviation. The spectrum is divided into two at the cut-off wavelength corresponding to Δx .

The low-frequency variations must cover the entire range of wind speeds and directions in the measured dataset. For this reason, the spectrum and coherence functions are expressed in terms of wavenumber rather than frequency, as they then become largely independent of wind speed. For each 10-minute section (length $T = 600s$), synthetic turbulence is added using the part of the turbulence spectrum from $1/T$ up to the frequency corresponding to Δx . The entire time history is then resampled to points uniformly spaced in along-wind distance x and converted into a wavenumber spectrum using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Using a suitable coherence function, the method of Veers [5] is used to generate correlated histories at a grid of points covering the wind farm area at hub height. To simulate advection, the phases of components at wavenumber k are adjusted by $2\pi kx$ at downwind distance x prior to the inverse FFT. The histories are converted back to the time domain by resampling at the original time points.

There is some uncertainty over suitable coherence functions to use. For turbine rotors, the IEC standard [6] provides lateral and vertical coherence functions, which can be used for the higher frequencies. Several of these are implemented in the model, with Kaimal as the default option. This

does not specify the along-wind coherence however, so an exponential decay model is assumed for this (equation 8.3):

$$\text{coh}(k,d) = \exp(-\beta kd) \quad (8.3)$$

at wavenumber $k = f/U$ for separation d , but there is uncertainty over the decay parameter β .

The Larsen exponential model [7] for mesoscale coherence is used as the default for lower frequencies (equation 8.4):

$$\text{coh}(k,d) = \exp[(1.8\cos(2\theta) - 5.9)kd] \quad (8.4)$$

for separation d at angle θ to the flow direction. A gradual transition between the two models occurs over a user-specified range of intermediate wavenumbers.

In the along-wind direction ($\theta = 0$), the Larsen model for mesoscale variations would be equivalent to $\beta = 4.1$ in the exponential model for along-wind turbulent fluctuations. This compares to the value of $\beta \approx 7$ for turbulent fluctuations suggested by Panofsky [8]. However, the Kristensen model [9] implies an order of magnitude smaller value, while the LiDAR measurements of Schlipf [10] show values of β in the range of about 0.4 - 1.25.

The low-frequency wind field generated in this way contains variations in all three components: longitudinal, lateral and vertical. However, the lateral and vertical components are zero-mean and therefore do not account for gross changes in wind direction. This is therefore simulated by rotating the entire wind field about the notional mast position by the current direction taken from the smoothed measured direction history. However, this is unrealistic for rapid direction changes so an assumption has to be made about how the direction change propagates through the farm, namely that it propagates at the mean speed, and the local wind vectors are rotated accordingly.

The low-frequency wind field is generated in the absence of turbines and their wakes. The wake deficits described below are then superimposed on this undisturbed wind field. This means that any effects of the turbines and their wakes on the underlying flow is neglected. This includes for example, wind farm blockage effects causing general flow speed reduction, and any change in the advection of turbulence caused by reduced wake flow velocities.

Wake profile

The default model for the wake velocity deficit profile is the Ainslie model [11], which uses an axisymmetric solution of the Navier-Stokes equation with a fairly simple eddy-viscosity model for the turbulence. This has been widely used, for example in the *WindFarmer* code [12], and has been validated against wind farm measurements at least in terms of 10-minute mean power production. It

produces a Gaussian-shaped velocity deficit profile as from two diameters downstream, which becomes wider and shallower as it advects further downstream such as to conserve momentum in the flow. The rate of widening increases with turbulence intensity, as defined by the eddy viscosity term. A typical velocity deficit distribution is illustrated in Figure 8.1.

Figure 8.1: typical velocity deficit distribution

The wake is initialized two diameters (2D) downstream, with centreline deficit (equation 8.5)

$$\delta = CT - 0.05 - ((16CT - 0.5) I/10) \quad (8.5)$$

for turbine thrust coefficient C_T and fractional turbulence intensity I . According to momentum conservation, the wake half-width B (in diameters) is related to the centreline deficit by equation 8.6:

$$B = (3.56 CT / (8\delta(1 - 0.5\delta)))^{0.5} \quad (8.6)$$

and this relationship always holds as the wake moves downstream, with δ decreasing and B increasing, at a rate defined by the eddy viscosity which is a function of turbulence intensity. The deficit profile remains axisymmetric and Gaussian, the deficit at a distance y diameters from the centreline being reported in equation 8.7:

$$\delta(y) = \delta(0) \exp(-3.56 y^2 / B^2) \quad (8.7)$$

Wake turbulence

Both the wake development and the downstream turbine loads depend critically on the turbulence, and it is therefore important to predict the increase in turbulence caused by the wakes themselves.

As in WindFarmer [12], the Quarton-Ainslie model ([13], as modified in [14]) for added turbulence in the wake is used by default. Although this is a completely empirical model, fitted to various measured datasets from wind tunnels and from now rather outdated wind farms in the field, validations of the WindFarmer model, of which it is a component, suggest that it may still be useful, although a more theoretically-based model would be desirable.

Wake meandering

The dynamic wake meandering model of Larsen *et al* [15] assumes that the wake is pushed around laterally and vertically by the low frequencies of the turbulence like a passive tracer, causing it to meander as it moves downstream. The low frequencies are defined in terms of spatial scales given by two ‘wake diameters’. For this application, a constant scale is needed, and anyway the wake diameter is not explicitly defined, so the spatial scale has been made user-definable. It is used in generating the low-frequency wind field as described above, and the resulting low frequency wind speed variations are then used to define the movement of the wake centreline from one timestep to the next.

One complication here is that the parameterisation of the Ainslie wake deficit model has been calibrated against 10-minute average wind farm measurements. Presumably, wake meandering will have been occurring during each 10-minute sample, resulting in a mean wake deficit profile which will have been ‘smeared out’ laterally and vertically by the meandering. Therefore, the instantaneous wake deficit profile must be narrower and deeper than the 10-minute average profile. The time-domain simulation model requires the instantaneous profile, so a correction to the profile is made following a suggestion by Ainslie [11], who derives an expression for the reduced centreline deficit of the smeared-out profile, δ' , as a function of the standard deviation of turbulence, σ_θ , at downstream distance x (diameters), as reported in equation 8.8:

$$\delta' = \delta / (1 + 7.12 * (\sigma_\theta x / B)^2)^{0.5} \quad (8.8)$$

Equation (8.6) still applies to the new profile, allowing its increased half-width B' to be calculated. However, since the Ainslie model has been parameterised against 10-minute data, it is already ‘smeared out’, so the inverse of this Ainslie correction must be applied to obtain the instantaneous profile, which can then be allowed to meander. The ratio $p = \delta' / \delta$ can be found as the solution to the quadratic equation 8.9:

$$p^2 + p [7.12 (\sigma_\theta x / B')^2 / (1 - 0.5\delta') - 1 - 3.56 \delta' (\sigma_\theta x / B')^2 / (1 - 0.5\delta')] \quad (8.9)$$

hence $\delta = \delta' / p$, and B is obtained from Equation (8.6).

When the model is run with this narrower profile, the meandering does indeed smear this out to produce the correct 10-minute mean profile, as shown in Figure 8.2, which plots the velocity profile in four wakes at a downstream location behind four turbines in two staggered rows. The original (smeared) steady-state wake profile from WindFarmer is shown by the solid line; the red circles are from the simulation model, using the smeared profile and no meandering; the green circles show the narrower (instantaneous) wakes obtained by applying the inverse Ainslie correction and when meandering is applied to these, the deficit averaged over time is smeared out to give the purple squares.

Figure 8.2: Ainslie meandering correction

Wake advection

When a change to the wake profile occurs, whether by turbine control action or a change in wind conditions, this change must advect downstream. By analogy with wake meandering in the lateral and vertical directions, this advection is assumed to be driven by the longitudinal component of the low-frequency wind field. However, it is also likely that the reduced wind speed in the wake itself causes the mean wake advection speed to be lower than the free wind speed. There is little information available in the literature to quantify this effect; in [16] some results are reviewed, suggesting that the advection speed may be around 80% of the free wind speed, but that it also depends on turbulence and downstream distance. Two options are therefore provided for the mean

advection speed, pending further work: a fixed fraction of the free wind speed, or a linear combination of free wind speed and mean speed within the wake profile.

Wake deflection

If the turbine is misaligned to the flow direction, momentum conservation dictates that the wake centreline will be deflected laterally. There will always be such yaw misalignments, since the turbine yaw control is not instantaneous but responds slowly to direction changes, due to, for example, low-pass filtering of the yaw misalignment, a dead-band to ensure that yaw manoeuvres do not occur too frequently, and a slow yaw rate (typically a fraction of a degree per second). More importantly, yaw misalignments may also be commanded deliberately for the purposes of wake steering control, where the wind farm controller deliberately yaws turbines in order to steer their wakes away from downstream turbines. For both reasons, the model must include this wake lateral deflection effect.

Jímenez [17] derives a simple model for this effect, based on momentum conservation with a rectangular wake deficit profile, but the same model has been used for other wake profiles, e.g. in Gebraad [18], where the deflection recovery parameter has been tuned against CFD simulations. This Jímenez-Gebraad model has therefore been adopted as a starting point. The somewhat more sophisticated EPFL model ([19], [20],[21]) is currently being implemented as an alternative.

Wake superposition

The combined effect of two or more wakes on a downstream turbine is not yet well understood. Several models of wake superposition have been used in the literature. Different alternatives are available in the model, the default being the ‘dominant wake’ model used by WindFarmer [12], where only the highest velocity deficit and the highest added turbulence of all the wakes impinging on a turbine are used. According to CFD calculations in [22], this works well for aligned turbines, while a linear combination of wake deficits may work better in cases where the wake centrelines are offset. Further work using CFD should help to define a more generalised model.

Wind farm control

The model includes a wind farm control module, which has access to model information such as would be expected to be available to a wind farm SCADA system, and outputs power delta and yaw misalignment set-points to all the turbines (and potentially other commands). This is flexibly implemented, to allow all kinds of wind farm control algorithms to be tested. It has currently been tested for a quasi-static open-loop or “advanced sector management” controller, with look-up tables

defining the delta and yaw set-points as a function of farm wind speed, direction and turbulence intensity. So far these inputs have been implemented as the smoothed time series coming from met mast measurements with further low-pass filtering applied, but estimations from the controllers of front-row turbines are another possibility.

8.2 Installation and usage

This model has been developed for internal use by DNV GL and is used to carry out simulations within the CL-Windcon project. Any of the wind farm controllers developed during the project could be evaluated by simulating their performance using the appropriate wind farm definition, driven by 10-minute met mast data from any appropriate source.

The model runs in Matlab, driven by input data supplied in several text files, for which full documentation is available. The calculation details file includes definitions of the wind field data, the wind farm, simulation control parameters and the other input files, which define, respectively, the turbine model(s) including control details, the wake model, and the wind farm controller.

Model outputs include detailed information about the performance and control of every turbine, as well as wind farm totals. This includes time history data for a large number of variables, as well as cumulative totals and counts of the numbers of supervisory control events (e.g. yaw manoeuvres). Dynamic plots displayed while the model is running include a contour plot of wind speeds and wakes across the wind farm, which can be stored as a video.

If the need arises, arrangements could be made to create a compiled version for use within the project by other partners. User documentation would also be made available in this case. The model should run on any standard PC running Windows.

8.3 References

1. “Long-term simulations for optimising yaw control and start-stop strategies”, E Bossanyi, T Delouvrié and S Lindahl, Proc. European Wind Energy Conference, Vienna, EWEA 2013.
2. “Dynamic wind power plant simulator for wind farm controller testing”, E Bossanyi, Proc. Wind Energy Science conference, Copenhagen, June 2017.
3. “Wind energy handbook”, Burton et al, Second edition, John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
4. “Generic grid frequency response capability for wind power plant”, E A Bossanyi, Proc. European Wind Energy Association Conference, Paris, November 2015.
5. “Three dimensional wind simulation”, P S Veers, SAND88 - 0152, Sandia National Laboratories, March 1988.

6. IEC 1400-1, Wind turbine generator systems - Part 1: Safety requirements, Third edition, 2004.
7. “Spectral structure of mesoscale winds over the water”, X G Larsen et al, Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc. 139: 685–700, April 2013 A
8. “Atmospheric Turbulence. Models and Methods for Engineering Applications”, H A Panofsky & J A Dutton, John Wiley & Sons, 1984.
9. “On longitudinal spectral coherence”, L Kristensen, Boundary Layer Meteorology 16 (1979) 145-153.
10. “Detection of Wind Evolution and Lidar Trajectory Optimization for Lidar-Assisted Wind Turbine Control”, D Schlipf et al, Meteorologische Zeitschrift Vol. 24 No. 6 (2015), p. 565 – 579.
11. “Calculating the flowfield in the wake of wind turbines”, J F Ainslie, Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics 27, 1988.
12. “WindFarmer Theory Manual v5.3”, DNV GL (2014).
13. “Turbulence in Wind Turbine Wakes”, D C Quarton & J F Ainslie, Wind Engineering, Vol. 14 No. 1, 1990.
14. “A wind tunnel investigation of the wake structure within small wind turbine farms”, U Hassan, ETSU WN 5113, 1993.
15. “Wake meandering – a pragmatic approach”, G Larsen et al, Wind Energy 11 pp377-395, 2008.
16. “Wake dynamics in offshore wind farms”, M de Mare, DTU Wind Energy PhD-0048 (EN), April 2015.
17. “Application of a LES technique to characterize the wake deflection of a wind turbine in yaw,” A. Jiménez, A. Crespo, and E. Migoya, Wind Energy, 13(6):559–572, 2010.
18. “Data-driven wind plant control”, P M O Gebraad, PhD Thesis, TU Delft, 2014.
19. “A new analytical model for wind-turbine wakes”, Majid Bastankhah and Fernando Porté-Agel, Renewable Energy 70 (2014) 116-123
20. “A new analytical model for wind farm power prediction”, Amin Niayifar and Fernando Porté-Agel, Journal of Physics: Conference Series 625 (2015) 012039 doi:10.1088/1742-6596/625/1/012039

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21. “Experimental and theoretical study of wind turbine wakes in yawed conditions”, Majid Bastankhah and Fernando Porté-Agel, J. Fluid Mech. (2016), vol. 806, pp. 506-541. (doi:10.1017/jfm.2016.595)
 22. “Limitations to the validity of single wake superposition in wind farm yield assessment”, K Gunn et al., WindEurope Summit 2016, Journal of Physics: Conference Series 749, IOP, 2016.
 23. “Bladed user manual”, DNV GL – Energy, www.dnvgl.com.

9 WINDFARMSIMULATOR (WFSIM)

9.1 Model description

9.1.1 Description summary

The WindFarmSimulator (WFSim) model is a medium-fidelity dynamical wind farm model developed by the Delft University of Technology. It has been developed for real-time dynamic wind farm control to be used as a surrogate model inside the control algorithm. In short, WFSim solves a modified set of unsteady two-dimensional (2D) Navier-Stokes equations over a spatially discretized horizontal plane at the turbine hub height. This surrogate model has a total of 5 tuning parameters, much fewer than the state of the art steady-state surrogate wind farm models from the literature. WFSim has shown success in reconstructing the flow field and turbine power signals of simulation data derived from high-fidelity LES wind farm models. This model is particularly suited for closed-loop wind farm control as it is dynamical, includes both yaw and axial induction control capabilities, handles temporally and spatially varying inflows, and yields a relatively high accuracy with a manageable computational cost. [1,2]

9.1.2 Model purpose

The medium-fidelity surrogate wind farm model “WFSim” aims to provide accurate predictions of the second-to-second flow field dynamics (at hub height) and generated power of each turbine inside the wind farm at an acceptable computational cost. The idea of wind farm control using the WFSim model is to push the accuracy of the internal control model while still allowing real-time computational tractability. Since WFSim only models the static axial rotor loads, it is still unclear whether this can be used for any kind of reliable fatigue optimization. So far, WFSim has been used exclusively for power regulation and maximization. [1-4]

9.1.3 Model specifications

WFSim is a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model that solves a modified set of the Navier-Stokes (NS) equations over a two-dimensional grid at turbine hub height. Specifically, an assumption regarding equal convergence of streamlines in lateral and vertical direction is made to reduce the speed-up effects typically found in two-dimensional NS wind farm models. Furthermore, the actuator disk model is used to represent the turbine forcing terms on the flow, and the power capture by each turbine in the farm. Wake recovery is captured by a mixing length turbulence model, modified by Boersma et al. to better capture the effects of turbine-induced turbulence. [1]

An open-source implementation of the WFSim model has been made available in MATLAB [5]. This implementation is leveraged for use in the European CL-Windcon project. This implementation leverages precompiled linear algebra solvers to efficiently propagate the model dynamics forwards in time. Compared to a native C-implementation, the MATLAB implementation of WFSim is expected to have a computational cost of equal order of magnitude.

Since the WFSim model relies on a spatial discretization of the to-be-computed flow field, there are typically several thousands states for a small farm, and many more for larger farms. At each discrete grid point, there are three states: two flow velocity terms and one pressure term. For example, for a typical small two-turbine wind farm, a meshing of 50 by 25 grid points is chosen, leading to approximately 3,000 states. The computational cost of a single forward propagation step in time (on a modern laptop CPU, single core) as a function of state size (n_q) is shown below in table 9.1 [1].

Table 9.1: Computational cost for a single core on a laptop CPU Δt^{CPU} as a function of number of states n_q

n_q	Δt^{CPU} [s]	n_q	Δt^{CPU} [s]	n_q	Δt^{CPU} [s]	n_q	Δt^{CPU} [s]
$3 \cdot 10^3$	0.02	$27 \cdot 10^3$	0.22	$115 \cdot 10^3$	1.19	$239 \cdot 10^3$	3.1
$6 \cdot 10^3$	0.04	$43 \cdot 10^3$	0.37	$147 \cdot 10^3$	1.66	$258 \cdot 10^3$	3.5
$9 \cdot 10^3$	0.06	$64 \cdot 10^3$	0.60	$182 \cdot 10^3$	2.12	$268 \cdot 10^3$	3.7
$14 \cdot 10^3$	0.10	$88 \cdot 10^3$	0.88	$221 \cdot 10^3$	2.50	$276 \cdot 10^3$	3.8

Currently, it has been shown that a 9-turbine (3 x 3) wind farm can accurately be captured using a meshing with 100 x 50 cells, leading to about 12,000 states [1,2]. The simulation results from WFSim for this wind farm show good agreement with that of high-fidelity LES data. However, no validation has yet been performed for larger wind farms.

9.1.4 Detailed mathematical model derivation

The mathematical derivation of the model is reported into the paper by Doekemeijer et al. [2] and Boersma et al. [1].

The WFSim wind farm model is based on the three-dimensional unsteady incompressible Navier-Stokes (NS) equations, simplified to two dimensions to reduce computational cost. The surrogate model can be described completely by the flow and rotor dynamics in a horizontal plane at hub height, derived from the following set of equations 9.1:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla_H) + \nabla_H \cdot \tau_H + \nabla_H \cdot p &= \mathbf{f}, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + 2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} &= 0, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla_H = \begin{bmatrix} \partial/\partial x \\ \partial/\partial y \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (9.1)$$

In these equations, u and v are the longitudinal and lateral flow velocity respectively, x and y are the spatial coordinates in longitudinal and lateral direction respectively, τ_H is a 2D tensor containing the horizontal subgrid stresses (turbulence model), p is a pressure term, and \mathbf{f} contains the forcing terms (turbine model) on the flow. These equations deviate from the traditional two-dimensional NS equations in two ways. Firstly, the diffusion term is neglected, as it plays a negligible role in the dominant flow dynamics due to the low viscosity of air. Secondly, the term $\partial v/\partial t$ in the continuity equation is multiplied with a factor 2 to approximate flow dissipating in the vertical flow dimension. This factor aims to resolve the flow speed-up issues around the turbines typically observed in the conventional 2D NS solvers. See [1] for a detailed derivation of the underlying equations of the WFSim model.

Subgrid-scale (turbulence) model

Boersma et al. [1] introduced a new model for the subgrid-scale term τ_H . The subgrid-scale model is formulated using an eddy-viscosity assumption in combination with Prandtl's mixing length model, proposed in equation 9.2:

$$\tau_H = -l_u(x, y)^2 \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \nabla_H \cdot \mathbf{u} + (\nabla_H \mathbf{u})^T \right), \quad (9.2)$$

where

$$l_u(x, y) = \begin{cases} G(x'_i, y'_i) * l_u^i(x'_i, y'_i), & \text{if } x \in X \text{ and } y \in Y, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Here, $l_u(x, y) \in R^+$ is a local spatially varying parametrization of the mixing length. $G(x'_i, y'_i)$ is a smoothing pillbox filter with radius 3, $*$ is a 2D spatial convolution operator, and X and Y define a rectangular region behind the turbine rotor to which the turbulence model applies. The bounds of this rectangle are:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= \{x: x'_i \leq x \leq x'_i + \cos(\theta) \cdot d\}, \\ Y &= \left\{ y: y'_i - \frac{D}{2} + \sin(\theta) \cdot x'_i \leq y \leq y'_i + \frac{D}{2} + \sin(\theta) \cdot x'_i \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

In these equations, θ is the mean wind direction, (x'_i, y'_i) is the wind-aligned coordinate system centred at the turbine rotor, D is the rotor diameter, and d is an upper bound on the spatial length

for which the turbulence model is enforced. Our mixing length parameter $l_u^i(x'_i, y'_i)$ can further be defined as

$$l_u^i(x'_i, y'_i) = \begin{cases} (x'_i - d')l_s, & \text{if } d' \leq x'_i \leq d \text{ and } -D/2 \leq y'_i \leq D/2, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This formulation implies that the mixing length parameter increases with downstream distance, being 0 at $x'_i = d'$, and having its highest value at $x'_i = d$. For $x'_i > d$, the turbulence model is no longer active. Thus, in this equation, d and d' are an upper and lower bound on the spatial domain for which the turbulence model is enforced and l_s defines the slope. This downstream-distance dependence on the turbulence model was inspired by work from Iungo et al. [6].

Turbine model

The turbines in the WFSim model are represented as actuator disks, projected onto the two-dimensional plane at hub height. The turbine forcing term in the Navier-Stokes equations, \mathbf{f} , can be calculated at a specific spatial location $\mathbf{s} = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}$ as $\mathbf{f} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} \mathbf{f}_i$, where \mathbf{f}_i are reported in equation 9.3:

$$\mathbf{f}_i = \frac{c_f}{2} C'_{T_i} (U_i \cos \gamma_i)^2 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\gamma_i + \theta) \\ \sin(\gamma_i + \theta) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{H}\left(\frac{D}{2} - \|\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{t}_i\|\right) \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta}\left((\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{t}_i) \cdot \mathbf{e}_{\text{orthogonal},i}\right). \quad (9.3)$$

In this equation, $\mathbf{H}(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function, $\boldsymbol{\delta}(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, $\mathbf{e}_{\text{orthogonal},i}$ is the unit vector perpendicular to the rotor disk of turbine i , which has spatial location \mathbf{t}_i . Furthermore, the scalar C'_{T_i} is the non-dimensional thrust coefficient of turbine i , which can be related to physical turbine parameters such as the generator torque and blade pitch angles. γ_i is the yaw angle of the turbine with respect to the incoming flow. c_f is a static tuning variable to account for the time-invariant properties and grid effects, making it the fourth tuning parameter (next to d , d' , and l_s). Thus, for control optimization, the degrees of freedom are γ_i and C'_{T_i} for $i = 1, \dots, N_T$, with N_T the total number of wind turbines inside the farm.

Furthermore, the turbine model predicts the power extracted from the wind. In a similar approach, $P_{\text{farm}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} P_i$, with P_i reported in equation 9.4:

$$P_i = \frac{c_p}{2} \rho A C'_{T_i} (U_i \cos \gamma)^3, \quad (9.4)$$

with scalar c_p the fifth and final tuning parameter (not to be confused with the nondimensional power coefficient C_p), accounting for the grid effects and time-invariant turbine properties (e.g., generator losses), and A the rotor swept surface area.

Discretization, boundary conditions, and generalized formulation

The Navier-Stokes equations including subgrid-scale model and turbine model are spatially discretized on a quadrilateral grid employing the finite volume method and the hybrid differencing scheme. Temporal discretization is performed using the implicit method. Dirichlet boundary conditions for u and v are applied on one side of the grid for inflow, while Neumann boundary conditions are applied on the remaining sides for the outflow. After discretization, the surrogate wind farm model described in this section reduces to a nonlinear discrete-time deterministic state-space model, described by equation 9.5:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= f(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{q}_k), \\ \mathbf{z}_k &= h(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{q}_k), \end{aligned} \quad (9.5)$$

Where \mathbf{x}_k is the system state at discrete time instant k , which is a column vector containing the collocated longitudinal flow velocity at each cell in the domain, the lateral flow velocity at each cell in the domain and the pressure term at each cell in the domain. Thus, \mathbf{x}_k is formulated in equation (9.6) as:

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{v}_k \\ \mathbf{p}_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9.6)$$

where \mathbf{u}_k , \mathbf{v}_k and \mathbf{p}_k each have about the same number of entries as the number of cells of the discretized grid. Empirically, good results have been achieved with cell dimensions of about 30-50 m in width and length, resulting in a typical state dimension in the order of $10^3 - 10^4$ for medium-sized wind farms (e.g., [1-5]). Such a number of states may seem very small for LES simulations, it is very high for control purposes instead. Furthermore, \mathbf{q}_k includes the system inputs, i.e., the turbine control settings. The system outputs \mathbf{z}_k are defined by sensors. It can include, among others, flow field measurements ($\mathbf{z}_k \subset \mathbf{x}_k$) and power measurements. The nonlinear functions f and h are called the state forward propagation and output equation, respectively.

9.2 Installation and usage

9.2.1 System requirements

The WFSim model is implemented in MATLAB 2017b, and has been shown to be compatible with older versions (tested for 2016a and upwards). It has been made to have limited dependencies, and only requires *the Image Processing Toolbox*. Compatibility has been confirmed for PC and Linux, but one should also be able to run it under OSX.

9.2.2 Installation instructions

The WFSim code can be *cloned* from Github for basic use, or *forked* for development and modification. Only the clone procedure is shown here. Make sure Git is installed on the computer. For Windows, it is recommended the Github Desktop software [7]. Now Git Shell (or a new terminal under Linux) must be opened, and the following command must be executed:

```
git clone https://github.com/TUdelft-DataDrivenControl/WFSim "destination_folder"
```

with "destination_folder" the desired location of the repository. Git will download the repository to the computer. If there are any changes to the repository online, *cd* to the local repository and update it with the latest updates by the following commands:

```
git fetch  
git pull
```

For a more detailed introduction to Git, please see the Git user manual [8].

9.2.3 Folder hierarchy

The folders are arranged in a straight-forward manner.

WFSim/ – This is the main folder that contains the main simulation file, "*WFSim.m*". This couples the different components together and demonstrates the use of WFSims functions for a wind farm simulation.

WFSim /bin – This folder contains all the core code for the model (in the **bin/core/** folder), and additionally some development and analysis code (in the **bin/analysis/** folder). The file names and contents are referred to for more information on individual files.

[WFSim /data_LES](#) – This folder, initially empty, is where all the downloaded LES data will be saved, used for simulation and comparisons. The LES data will be downloaded from a remote server when its contents are requested.

[WFSim/documentation](#) – This folder contains an archive with some (partially outdated) documentation of the WFSim model. Note that the latest documentation is reference [1], and this folder is outdated.

[WFSim /libraries](#) – This folder contains a number of external libraries used in the WFSim model, such as a sparse computations toolbox, a toolbox to import PALM (LES code from Hannover) data, and a toolbox for exporting figures from MATLAB.

9.2.4 Performing a test run

A test run is performed very easily, and a demonstration code is provided named “WFSim.m”. Within this file, it is needed to:

```
Wp.name          = '2turb_adm_turb';    % Choose which scenario to simulate.
```

1. Specify the desired wind farm layout, turbine properties, and site properties in line 67.

2. Specify the desired model solver settings and output information in lines 70-84.

```
scriptOptions.Projection = 0; % Solve by projecting away the continuity
equation
scriptOptions.Linearversion = 0; % Calculate linear system matrices of WFSim
scriptOptions.exportLinearSol = 0; % Calculate linear solution of
WFSim
scriptOptions.Derivatives = 0; % Compute derivatives, useful for predictive
control
scriptOptions.exportPressures = ~scriptOptions.Projection; % Calculate.
pressure fields.

% Convergence settings (recommended: leave default)
scriptOptions.conv_eps = 1e-6; % Convergence threshold. Default: 1e-6.
scriptOptions.max_it_dyn = 1; % Maximum number of iterations for k > 1.
Default: 1.

% Display and visualization settings
scriptOptions.printProgress = 1; % Print progress in cmd window every
timestep.
scriptOptions.printConvergence = 0; % Print convergence values every
timestep.
scriptOptions.Animate = 5; % Plot flow fields every [X] iterations (0: no
plots).
scriptOptions.plotMesh = 1; % Plot mesh, turbine locations, and print grid
offset values. Default: false.
```

3. Run the *WFSim.m* file.

9.2.5 Setting up a simulation case

Which files to change and how

The simulation case settings and parameters are fully described in a single file: [/bin/core/meshing.m](#). Within this file, one can create their own wind farm simulation “case” with the desired turbine properties, locations, control settings, atmospheric conditions, and grid properties. An example case for the generic 3-turbine case displayed in the next subsection is shown here:

```

case lower('clwindcon_3turb')
    gridType      = 'lin'; % Grid type (currently only linear is supported)
    Drotor        = 178.3; % Turbine rotor diameter
    Lx             = 15*Drotor; % Grid length (x-direction)
    Ly            = 5*Drotor; % Grid width (y-direction)
    Nx            = 100; % Number of grid points in x-direction
    Ny            = 40; % Number of grid points in y-direction
    Crx           = [1.0*Drotor 6.0*Drotor 11.*Drotor]; % Turbine locations (x)
    Cry           = [2.5*Drotor 2.5*Drotor 3.0*Drotor]; % Turbine locations (y)
    h             = 1; % Discrete timestep (s)
    L             = 600; % Final simulation time (s)

    NT = length(Crx); % Number of wind turbines
    for i = 1:L+1 % Generate a time-series of control settings
        turbInput(i) = struct('t',h*i,... % Time
                              'phi',zeros(NT,1),... % Yaw angle
                              'CT_prime',2*ones(NT,1)); % CT'
    end

    u_Inf         = 8.0; % Freestream wind speed (x-direction)
    v_Inf         = 0.0; % Freestream wind speed (y-direction)
    Rho           = 1.20; % Air density
    startUniform = true; % Start from uniform (T) or from fully developed
    (including wake formations) flow field (F).
    powerscale   = .95; % Turbine power scaling
    forcescale    = 1.5; % Turbine force scaling
    p_init       = 0.0; % Initial values for pressure terms (Pa)
    turbul       = true; % Use mixing length turbulence model
    (true/false)
    turbModel    = 'WFSim3'; % Turbulence model of choice
    mu           = 0.0; % Dynamic flow viscosity

    d_lower      = 50; % Turbulence model gridding property (WES: d')
    d_upper      = 700; % Turbulence model gridding property (WES: d)
    lm_slope     = 0.05; % Turbulence model gridding property (WES: l_s)

```

In this case, the turbine properties such as location and rotor diameter need no explanation. The grid specifications are typically chosen to have cells of approximately 30 m – 50 m in each direction, where accuracy (many cells) is traded off against computational cost (few cells). The timestep is currently chosen at 1 second, but can be chosen as lower or higher, depending on what frequency

one desires to control the wind turbines, the computational resources available, and what temporal resolution of flow dynamics are of interest.

The turbine control signals can be chosen by defining the variable `turbInput`. When validating the WFSim model, these control signals should accurately capture the true control signals of the high-fidelity/experimental turbines. In simulation, this can often be achieved without additional work (i.e., by simply requesting the desired outputs out of the high-fidelity simulation environment). For experimental turbines, one needs to rely on aerofoil tables to map the physical turbine control settings to the non-dimensional thrust coefficient. This is comparable to the look-up tables for C_T and C_p described in the previous section on the “FLORIS” model.

Finally, there are five tuning parameters in the model, namely `powerscale`, `forcescale`, `d_lower`, `d_upper`, and `lm_slope`. The former two parameters are mainly to tune the turbine model. The `powerscale` has no influence on the flow, and solely is a scaling factor on the output of the turbine power outputs predicted by actuator disk theory. This scaling factor can include, for example, model mismatches and generator efficiency losses. Typically, this parameter is chosen by comparison to high-fidelity data, after the flow has been matched accurately (i.e., the other tuning parameters have been chosen). Secondly, `forcescale` is chosen to accurately represent the wake shape and depth, especially in proximity of the relevant turbine. The final three tuning parameters, `d_lower`, `d_upper`, and `lm_slope`, are related to the turbulence model. While usually, not much time is spend on tuning the parameters `d_lower` and `d_upper` (results have appeared fairly consistent over various simulations), `lm_slope` is tuned. Its value is typically chosen using LES data, focusing on the far-wake recovery region. The higher the value of `lm_slope`, the more wake recovery is seen in the downstream flow.

Typically, a grid-search is performed over the various parameters (`forcescale` and the 3 turbulence parameters), to match the WFSim model optimally to the LES data. The cost function here is the mean squared error between the two flow fields over several hundred seconds of simulation time. Additionally, as many combinations of parameters result in fairly similar performance, the match in power curves is looked at, both quantitatively (*root-mean-squared error*) and qualitatively (*variance accounted for*).

9.3 Performing simulations

9.3.1 Generic 3 turbine case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository. The settings are specified in the case “clwindcon_3turb”, in the [/bin/core/meshing.m](#) file. The layout and an example flowfield are provided next in figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: layout and an example flowfield of the generic 3-turbine case in WFSim

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the WFSim model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

9.3.2 Generic 9 turbine case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository, case “clwindcon_9turb”, in the `/bin/core/meshing.m` file. The layout and an example flowfield are provided next in figure 9.2 and 9.3.

Figure 9.2: layout of the generic 9-turbine wind farm case in WFSim

Figure 9.3: example flowfield of the 9-turbine wind farm case in WFSim

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the WFSim model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

9.3.3 Generic 80 turbine (offshore) case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository. The settings are specified in the case “clwindcon_80turb”, in the [/bin/core/meshing.m](#) file. The layout and an example flowfield are provided next in figure 9.4 and 9.5. Note that two turbines seem to be missing on the bottom row, between turbines 21 and 30, and between turbines 55 and 64. These are substations, as this virtual wind farm is considered offshore.

Figure 9.4: layout of the offshore 80-turbine wind farm case in WFSim

The main flow direction is along the x-axis, thus vertically, from bottom to top.

Figure 9.5: an example flowfield of the offshore 80-turbine wind farm case in WFSim

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the WFSim model will be tuned according to SOWFA data in following work.

9.3.4 Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case

How to set it up

The wind farm topology has been implemented on the Github repository. The settings are specified in the case “clwindcon_windTunnel”, in the </bin/core/meshing.m> file. The layout and an example flowfield are provided next in figure 9.6.

Figure 9.6: layout and an example flowfield of the 2-turbine wind tunnel case in WFSim

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the WFSim model will be tuned according to SOWFA data and/or experimental data in following work.

9.3.5 Sedini real wind farm case

How to set it up

Since the exact simulations conditions for the Sedini wind farm are still under definition, this simulation case has not been implemented yet. However, in some scenarios, it must be accounted for various wind turbine types (hub height, rotor diameter), which means that the rotor diameter variable will become a vector rather than a scalar. This is a small but noticeable adjustment that has to be made to the WFSim model.

Secondly, the tuning parameters need to be matched to higher-fidelity data, such as large-eddy simulation data or field data. Depending on the quality of the field measurements, one or the other may be opted for, or a combination of both.

Motivation for choices of parameters

The parameters of the WFSim model will be tuned according to SOWFA data and/or field data in following work.

9.4 References

1. Boersma, S., Doekemeijer, B., Vali, M., Meyers, J., & van Wingerden, J. W. (2017). A control-oriented dynamic wind farm model: WFSim. *Wind Energ. Sci. Discuss.*, 2017, 1-34. doi:10.5194/wes-2017-44
2. Doekemeijer, B., Boersma, S., Knudsen, T., Pao, L. Y., & van Wingerden, J. W. (2018). Online model calibration for a simplified LES model in pursuit of real-time closed-loop wind farm control. *Wind Energ. Sci. Discuss.*, 2018. In preparation, to be submitted in Spring 2018.
3. Doekemeijer, B. M., Boersma, S., Pao, L. Y., & van Wingerden, J. W. (2017, 24-26 May 2017). *Ensemble Kalman filtering for wind field estimation in wind farms*. Paper presented at the 2017 American Control Conference (ACC).
4. Vali, M., Petrović, V., Boersma, S., van Wingerden, J.-W., & Kühn, M. (2017). Adjoint-based model predictive control of wind farms: Beyond the quasi steady-state power maximization. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 50(1), 4510-4515. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.382
5. TUDelft. (2018). Github: TUDelft-DataDrivenControl/WFSim - A control-oriented medium-fidelity wind farm model based on the unsteady 2D Navier-Stokes equations. Retrieved from <https://github.com/TUDelft-DataDrivenControl/WFSim>
6. Iungo, G. V., Viola, F., Ciri, U., Rotea, M. A., & Leonardi, S. (2015). Data-driven RANS for simulations of large wind farms. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 625(1), 012025.

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7. Github. (2018). Github Desktop - Simple collaboration from your desktop. Retrieved from <https://desktop.github.com/>
 8. Git. (2018). Git - user-manual Documentation. Retrieved from <https://git-scm.com/docs/user-manual.html>

10 WAKE DISSIPATION MODEL FOR WAKE TRACKING

10.1 Model description

The wake dissipation model is an engineering model that described several effects of a turbine wake. Mainly the wake deficit, the wake evolution and the wake redirection is included. Its primal purpose is to serve as internal model in a model-based wake tracking approach for closed-loop wake redirection as introduced in [1]. The computational costs are very low since engineering modelling techniques are used. In the following, the general model and the single different sub-models are described. Furthermore, an adaption to a simplified dynamic version is performed. The current source code can be downloaded at [2].

10.1.1 General model description

The model is based on the assumption of a wind field models in a wind field coordinate system, W . The orientation of the wind field coordinate system with respect to the inertial coordinate system can be expressed by the rotational degree of freedom, α_H , in equation 10.1, that describes a horizontal rotation along.

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}_I = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha_H & -\sin \alpha_H & 0 \\ \sin \alpha_H & \cos \alpha_H & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}_W \quad (10.1)$$

The basis wind field in the wind field coordinate system is expressed by the effective wind speed, v_0 , and a linear vertical wind shear component, δ_V , as report in equation 10.2:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}_{i,W} = \begin{bmatrix} v_0 + z_i \delta_V \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10.2)$$

where z_i is the height above the ground. The basis wind field is linearly superposed with the wake components according to equation 10.3:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}_{i,W} = \begin{bmatrix} v_0 + z_i \delta_V + \Psi_{u,i} \\ \Psi_{v,i} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10.3)$$

Wake deficit and wake evolution model

The wake deficit is modelled calculating the energy extraction along the blade starting with an initial wake deficit at the rotor disk with tip and root losses depending on the energy extraction. At point $[y_i \quad z_i]$ in the wind field, the energy extraction is expressed by equation 10.4:

$$\Gamma_i = \begin{cases} \left. \frac{dc_p}{dr} \right|_{r_i} & \text{if } \sqrt{y_i^2 + z_i^2} = r_i \leq R \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (10.4)$$

With r_i the normalized radius at $[y_i \ z_i]$ along the specific blade with radius R . $\frac{dc_p}{dr}$ is the distribution of the power extraction over the blade, e.g., with CCBlade, see [3]. Applying the energy conservation assumption and the assumption of energy extraction according the previous expression with $\Psi_{\text{init}} = \Gamma x$ yields to equation 10.5:

$$(v_0 + \Psi_{\text{init}})^2 - (1 - c_p)v_0 = 0 \quad (10.5)$$

With the power coefficient c_p . Solving the equation yields the initial wake deficit. An exemplary initial wake deficit is shown in Figure 10.1.

Figure 10.1: An example of an initial wake deficit over the normalized rotor disk.

The wake is evolving as it moves away from the wind turbine. New energy is flowing from the side and above and the flow is mixed. This effect is modelled with an empirical model by a Gaussian shape 2D filter. The 2D filter Ξ depends on the distance d behind the wind turbine according to equation 10.6:

$$\Xi(d, y_i, z_i) = \exp \frac{y_i^2 + z_i^2}{2\sigma_f^2(d)} \quad (10.6)$$

With

$$\sigma_f(d) = \frac{d\epsilon}{2\sqrt{2\log(2)}}$$

The dissipation rate can be set with the parameter ϵ . Now, for every distance behind the rotor, the wake can be evaluated using the initial wake deficit by convolution with the filter according to equation 10.7:

$$\Psi(d, y_i, z_i) = \Xi(d, y_i, z_i) * \Psi_{\text{init}} \quad (10.7)$$

Wake deflection model

The wake deflection caused by a yaw misalignment γ is additionally modelled. The relationship is derived in the work of [4]. The angle of the wake with respect to the main wind direction is reported in equation 10.7:

$$\xi(d, c_T, \gamma) = \frac{\xi_{\text{init}}(c_T, \gamma)}{(1 + \beta \frac{d}{D})^2} \quad (10.7)$$

With the initial angle of the wake at the rotor defined in equation 10.8:

$$\xi_{\text{init}}(c_T, \gamma) = \frac{1}{2} c_T \cos^2 \gamma \sin \gamma \quad (10.8)$$

and the model parameter β , that defines the sensitivity of the wake deflection to yaw. Furthermore, c_T is the thrust coefficient and D the rotor diameter. According to [5], the deflection at the downwind distance d is expressed by equation 10.9:

$$\delta_{\text{yaw}}(d, c_T, \gamma) = -\xi_{\text{init}}(c_T, \gamma) \frac{D}{30\beta} \left[15 \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{2\beta d}{D}} \right) + \xi_{\text{init}}(c_T, \gamma)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{2\beta d}{D})^5} \right) \right] \quad (10.9)$$

The rotation is applied to the wake deficit and yields a u and v component of the wake model, according to equation 10.10:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{u,i} \\ \Psi_{v,i} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}_W = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \xi & -\sin \xi & 0 \\ \sin \xi & \cos \xi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}_W \quad (10.10)$$

In Figure 10.2 two different wake situations are shown, the first is a non-yawed case and in the second case the turbine is yawed with $\gamma = 25$ deg. In both cases the basis wind field has a constant wind speed of $v_0 = 16$ m/s and no vertical shear.

Figure 10.2: Visualization of two wake situations within a constant wind field of $v_0 = 16$ m/s and no vertical shear. The yaw angles are 0 and 25 deg

Dynamical adaption of the model

During the CL-Windcon project the model is developed further by introducing dynamics to enable time dependant simulation. This modifies the model from being a static model to a dynamic model. However, the model dynamics bases on simple assumptions that are described in the following.

The general idea is to introduce particles in which the wake properties are stored and that can only travel in x- direction in the wind field coordinate system of the wake. Each particle has its origin at the rotor. They travel with the mean wind speed at their current cross section of the wind field. The wake is then evaluated at the different particle locations. This yields at wake description based on n different wake properties, where n is the number of particles for each wake. See Figure 10.3 for a description of the execution sequence of a turbine’s wake at one time step.

Furthermore, the ability to use turbulent wind fields are introduced. This gives the possibility to perform time simulations not only with homogeneous wind field, but also with different turbulent wind fields. Figure 10.4 gives a flow snapshot of a homogeneous simulation case of two turbines at $U_{Ref} = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

Figure 10.3: Execution sequence of the dynamic wake model for one turbine at one time step.

Figure 10.4: Example result of a uniform simulation at $U_{Ref} = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ with a two turbine layout.

10.2 Installation and usage

10.2.1 System requirements

The wake model and the simulation environment is implemented in Matlab and tested with version R2015b. It runs on a normal personal computer in acceptable execution time, however the time heavily depends on the grid parameter.

10.2.2 Installation instructions

To install the model, the last version can be downloaded from the Github repository on: <https://github.com/SWE-UniStuttgart/DynamicWakeDissipationModel>.

10.2.3 Folder hierarchy

The simulation environment consists of a configuration file (config) and a main script. In the config file *DynamicWakeDissipationModelConfig* the simulation cases are defined. The main script is *DynamicWakeDissipationModel* and it executes the defined simulation case of the config. All necessary functions for the simulation environment is stored in the core folder.

10.2.4 Performing a test run

A test run can be performed by selecting the homogeneous initial test case in the config file (*InitialTest-CL-Windcon-homogeneous*).

10.2.5 Setting up a simulation case

In order to set up a new simulation case, a new case needs to be defined in the the config file and afterwards selected for execution. In the case, all necessary parameters are defined. The model parameters are according to the model description and mainly self-explaining. At the current stage, the turbine controller is not implemented, however turbine operation can be included using the *TurbineData* struct variable. In a later stage, a controller is included, which gives the axial induction and the yaw angle for the turbine.

10.3 Performing simulations

10.3.1 Generic 3 turbine case

The three turbine case is already implemented in the example config file. By selecting the simulation case *ThreeTurbine-CL-Windcon* the simulation can be run. For different wind speed conditions `Parameter.Windfarm.UREf` needs to be adjusted. Furthermore, a turbulent wind field can be imposed by loading it into the `BasicWindField` struct.

10.3.2 Generic 9 turbine case

The nine turbine case is already implemented in the example config file. By selecting the simulation case *NineTurbine-CL-Windcon* the simulation can be run. For different wind speed conditions `Parameter.Windfarm.UREf` needs to be adjusted. Furthermore, a turbulent wind field can be imposed by loading it into the `BasicWindField` struct. Results are shown in figure 10.5

Figure 10.5: Snapshot of the flow of the nine turbine case at $U_{Ref} = 9 \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

10.3.3 Generic 80 turbine, scaled wind tunnel & Sedini wind farm cases

To set up the 80 turbine case or other cases like realized in wind tunnel experiments, a new config case needs to be defined in which the layout, the turbine properties and the operational data must be defined. Furthermore, adjustments on specific tuning parameters for wake decay and wake

redirection capability can be done to meet the specific turbine properties. It is referred to the example cases in which all necessary parameters are defined and which can be used as template.

10.4 References

1. S. Raach, D. Schlipf, and P. W. Cheng, “Lidar-based wake tracking for closed-loop wind farm control,” *Wind Energy Science*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 257–267, 2017.
2. SWE Github repository, “DynamicWakeDissipationModel”, URL: <https://github.com/SWE-UniStuttgart/DynamicWakeDissipationModel>
3. *NWTC Information Portal (CCBlade)*. <https://nwtc.nrel.gov/CCBlade>.
4. Á. Jiménez, A. Crespo, and E. Migoya, “Application of a LES technique to characterize the wake deflection of a wind turbine in yaw,” *Wind Energy*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 559–572, 2010.
5. P. M. O. Gebraad, “Data-driven wind plant control,” Ph.D. dissertation, Delft University of Technology, 2014

11 USING DATA REDUCTION TECHNIQUES FOR WIND FARM MODELING

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
POD	Proper-orthogonal decomposition
POM	POD mode
ROM	Reduced-order model
SOWFA	Simulation for Onshore/Offshore Wind Farm Applications
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
WF	Wind farm
WT	Wind turbine

11.1 Model description

11.1.1 Description summary

In this section, the main features and motivation for the implementation of these models, based on data reduction techniques, are explained. These reduced-order models (ROMs) enable the development of control strategies with a better management of the wind turbines within a wind farm. This could potentially increase the overall wind plant power output, as well as increase the wind turbines lifetime by reducing their loads. In particular, the models are able to properly predict the deflection experienced by the wake shed by a wind turbine that is rotated out of the wind, as well as the impact that such a technique has on the performance of downstream wind turbines. Indeed, it has been shown, either by means of experiments or simulations [1] [2], that this technique could potentially induce a substantial increase of the power produced by downstream wind turbines.

The implementation of these models require the availability of detailed flow measurements, obtained, for our case, by means of CFD simulations performed with SOWFA, which is a high-fidelity large-eddy simulation tool developed at the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) to support wind farm control research. SOWFA is a CFD solver based on OpenFOAM coupled with NREL's FAST wind turbine simulator; the reader is therefore referred to the documentation of SOWFA and FAST [3] [4] [5] for further details about the used CFD framework.

11.1.2 Model purpose

The models based on data reduction techniques are expected to support the design of wind farm control algorithms, which could then be real-time executed with modest computational resources. In this regard, the models aim at accurately reproducing the dominant dynamics of the main wind turbines parameters as well as their shed wakes. Regarding the flow field within and outside the wind turbine wakes, the models are capable to predict the temporal variation of the three velocity components in the whole domain of interest. With respect to the performance, the models are currently used to solely predict the power production of the wind turbines in the wind farm, but the develop framework has been conceived so that other quantities, like torque, thrust, blade root bending moments, etc. could be easily included in the models, as long as they are listed among the outputs of the previously-performed CFD simulation. Another relevant aspect, of these reduced-order models, is that they do not only predict steady-state wakes for specific yaw misalignment. Since these reduced-order models are dynamic models, transients are also taken into account and modeled.

11.1.3 Model specifications

As already mentioned, the models require the outputs of previously performed CFD simulations. In this regard, it has been used an already extensively validated LES framework [6]. In particular, a digital copy of a scaled wind farm, described in Deliverable D3.1 - Definition of wind tunnel testing conditions (wind tunnel case), has been realized within the LES framework. The modeled wind turbines are therefore G1 scaled models ('G1' for Generic 1 m diameter rotor) operated in a boundary layer wind tunnel. A brief description of such G1 scaled models is provided in Table 11.1, while further details are given in Deliverable D3.1 - Definition of wind tunnel testing conditions.

Table 11.1: G1 scaled model characteristics

Rotor orientation	Upwind wind turbine
Rotor diameter	1.1 m
Hub height	0.825 m
Number of blades	3
Rated rotor speed	850 rpm
Nacelle tilt angle	0°
Rotor cone angle	0°
Control	Variable speed, pitch, and yaw

In this section about model specifications, it is also appropriate to highlight the limitations related to the adopted data-reduction techniques. Indeed, the procedure used to develop these reduced-order models is based on system identification methods. These methods derive models from flow data and wind turbines performance for particular conditions, e.g. specific wind farm layout and inflow condition. Therefore, these models could not be directly used to predict the flow within a wind farm characterized by configurations that considerably differ from the one used to derive the model, e.g. different lateral/longitudinal spacing, or inflow condition. Consequently, the range of operating conditions for which the models can be used is limited. For a better understanding of the motivations at the base of this statement, the reader is referred to the next section. Currently, the models have been derived for a particularly configured wind farm and a given mean wind speed and turbulence intensity. If other wind farm layouts or other inflow conditions were desired, it would be necessary to execute other CFD simulations and derive again reduced-order models using the new generated outputs. To overcome this drawback, an extension of the methodology proposed in the next section is currently under investigation.

11.1.4 Detailed mathematical derivation

In this subsection, that regards the mathematical derivation of the proposed control-oriented models, a description of the methodology is presented. In order to avoid an excessively long documentation, some steps of the mathematical derivation will be neglected; however, the crucial mathematical background and some approach specifically developed for this application will be highlighted. For a better and more comprehensive understanding of the methodology, the reader is referred to Refs. [7], [8], [9], and [10].

The mathematical procedure described in the following and required to obtain reduced-order models, aims at properly reducing and treating the big amount of data collected from the CFD simulations in order to obtain models that can be computationally manageable for the design of wind farm control algorithms. The procedure to obtain the models can be classified as a data-driven, equation-free, system identification procedure.

The data are collected from the high-fidelity CFD simulations in the form of snapshot of physical quantities (flow field or wind turbine performances), sampled at a specific time step. The specific collected data are essentially the following:

- Velocity components of the flow sampled at a specific grid of points within the CFD simulation domain;
- Wind turbines performances: typically power output of the wind turbines in the wind farm; however, other physical quantities such as torque or thrust can also be collected;

- Prescribed control inputs: typically yaw misalignment for each wind turbine, but also other input, such as pitch angle, can be collected.

The collected data are therefore arranged in the following matrices:

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= [x_1 \quad x_2 \quad \cdots \quad x_{n_s-1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times (n_s-1)}, \\
 X' &= [x_2 \quad x_3 \quad \cdots \quad x_{n_s-1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times (n_s-1)}, \\
 U &= [u_1 \quad u_2 \quad \cdots \quad u_{n_s-1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times (n_s-1)}, \\
 Y &= [y_1 \quad y_2 \quad \cdots \quad y_{n_s-1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times (n_s-1)},
 \end{aligned} \tag{11.1}$$

where x_k is the vector of the 3 velocity components of the flow recorded, for all grid points, at time instant k ; u_k represents the control inputs (e.g. yaw misalignments) at time instant k ; y_k represents the simulation outputs (e.g. wind turbines power) collected at time instant k . The scalars n_s , n_x , n_u and n_y are the number of snapshots, the number of grid points multiplied by the number of recorded velocity components (generally 3), the number of inputs and the number of outputs, respectively.

The proposed method therefore attempts to fit the snapshot measurements by equation 11.2:

$$\begin{cases} x_{k+1} = A x_k + B u_k, \\ y_k = C x_k + D u_k, \end{cases} \tag{11.2}$$

with the goal, therefore, of fitting a non-linear system with a linear model. It's important, however, to stress that a state matrix A , built with CFD velocity data sampled at thousands of grid points, could easily occupy hundredths of GB of memory. This simple example illustrates the extreme need of a powerful method capable of reducing the size of the models, obtained using equation-free system identification procedures, so as they could be used to develop model-based control algorithms.

With this aim, the model can be represented as an explicit discrete-time-invariant linear system by means of the following state-space form reported in equation 11.3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{x}_{k+1} &= \tilde{A} \tilde{x}_k + \tilde{B} u_k, \\
 y_k &= \tilde{C} \tilde{x}_k + \tilde{D} u_k,
 \end{aligned} \tag{11.3}$$

where $\tilde{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is the reduce-order state vector, $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the input vector (e.g. yaw misalignments) and y_k is the output vector (e.g. wind turbines power). Matrices \tilde{A} , \tilde{B} , \tilde{C} and \tilde{D} have the required, appropriate dimensions.

The reduction from the full-order state vector x_k to the reduced-order state vector \tilde{x}_k is done by “projecting” the former onto a reduced-order subspace (with dimension $r \ll n_x$) by means of a subspace projection matrix. The goal behind this projection is to obtain a model characterized by a substantial lower number of states that could be used for control purposes.

As described in Refs. [8] and [9], the projection from the full-order states to the reduced-order state is defined in equation 11.4 as:

$$\tilde{x}_k = Px_k, \quad (11.4)$$

where $P \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n_x}$ is the projection subspace matrix. The projection subspace matrix is obtained by exploiting the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) modes of the snapshot matrix X (see Eq. (11.1)), whose computation requires performing the following Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) reported in equation 11.5:

$$X = U_{\text{SVD}} \Sigma_{\text{SVD}} V_{\text{SVD}}^T, \quad (11.5)$$

where $U_{\text{SVD}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times (n_s-1)}$ contains the left-singular vectors, $V_{\text{SVD}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_s-1) \times (n_s-1)}$ contains the right-singular vectors, and $\Sigma_{\text{SVD}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_s-1) \times (n_s-1)}$ the singular values. The POD modes (POMs) are the left-singular vectors of the snapshot matrix. Choosing such POD modes for the generation of the subspace projection provide major benefits, since they represent a series of intrinsic, spatial, non-temporal patterns of the flow. Indeed, the flow within the domain can be spatially reconstructed by properly adding these POMs. Each POM has also a temporal description associated that gives the evolution over time of each POM. This can be extracted from the right-singular vectors of the SVD decomposition. Lastly, the energy, or the weight, with which each one of the POMs contributes to the original flow, is given by the corresponding singular value.

The advantage of this decomposition is that, by only retaining a subset r of the POD modes, a certainly high degree of compression of the original CFD data can be obtained while still preserving satisfactory performance. As a consequence, matrix X would be approximated as:

$$X \approx U_r \Sigma_r V_r^T, \quad (11.6)$$

where $(\cdot)_r$ corresponds to the truncation by the first r POD modes.

As previously stated, the projection subspace matrix that relates full-order states and reduced-order states is chosen to be the POD modes, in particular, a selection of the first r POD modes since they are the most energetic ones (higher singular values) and the ones with lower frequencies associated (better resolved POD modes). Hence, the chosen projection subspace matrix is defined in equation 11.7 as:

$$P := U_r^T, \quad P \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n_x} \quad (11.7)$$

Finally, if the system in Eq. (11.3) is written in compact form (i.e. as matrices for all snapshots) and the projection in Eq. (11.4) is applied considering the projection subspace matrix expressed by

Eq.(11.7), the final expression for the matrices of the state-space representation of the reduced-order model is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{A} & \tilde{B} \\ \tilde{C} & \tilde{D} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_r^T X' \\ Y \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_r^T X \\ U \end{bmatrix}^\dagger. \quad (11.8)$$

The reconstructed full-order flow produced by the ROM can be approximated combining Eqs. (11.4) and (11.7).

To improve the accuracy of the model in predicting the effects that misaligning of the first wind turbine has on the flow and on the power outputs, the input vector u_k is conveniently adapted. The following expression has then been implemented:

$$u_k = f(\gamma_k) = [\gamma_k \quad \gamma_k^2 \quad \gamma_k^3 \quad \gamma_k^4 \quad \cos^p(\gamma_k) - 1]^T, \quad (11.9)$$

where γ_k is the prescribed yaw angle signal at discrete time k . In detail, the non-linear relationship between the yaw input and the variations of the flow state and of the power outputs is modeled by means of a combination of a fourth order polynomial and a \cos^p term, where the latter is included considering the experimentally-derived relation between upwind turbine's yaw angle and power output [11]. Particularly, a value of $p = 1.787$ was chosen according to that study. Apart from the system non-linearities that the polynomial fit partially handles, it is also relevant to highlight that it is well known that power is mostly independent on the sign of the yaw angle misalignment. For this reason, even functions are required for properly modeling the relationship between yaw misalignment and power, which also means that a simple linear, proportional dependency would never properly work. For the wind flow prediction, instead, it was found, by means of a trial-and-error approach, that the proposed input vector is the one that allows to better capture the relation between flow and yaw misalignment. All these considerations support the choice of the indicated input signal transformation.

11.2 Installation and usage

11.2.1 System requirements

Currently, the “models based on data reduction techniques” are obtained and used directly in the MATLAB environment, and the framework is composed, basically, of several MATLAB scripts. No particular recommendation is given regarding the needed version of MATLAB. However, the framework has been successfully tested only on MATLAB 2016a and following versions. Other programming environment might not be so appropriate, since some scripts make use of built-in MATLAB functions and MATLAB toolboxes; for instance, the `svd()` MATLAB function or functions of Control System Toolbox.

11.2.2 Installation instructions

The installation procedure has been kept straightforward. The folder hierarchy, described in the next section, is located in “<https://gitlab.lrz.de/ga42foc/ROM4WakeDeflection.git>”.

11.2.3 Folder hierarchy

In this section, the general structure of the folders prepared to obtain these reduced-order models based on data reduction techniques is described.

- *\ROM4WakeDeflection*
 - This is the main folder that contains the subfolders needed for the extraction and execution of ROMs as well as for results visualization. It also contains “Extract_ROM.m” and “Run_ROM.m”, which are the main scripts required to extract ROMs from CFD data, to evaluate their outputs for given inputs and visualize the results.
- *\ROM4WakeDeflection\InputFiles*
 - This folder contains the CFD data that are required to extract reduced-order models. The snapshots of the flow must be saved in “\flowDATA”, the recorded input/output of the simulation in “\input_outputDATA”, while folder “\coordinatesDATA” contains the coordinates of the grid points at which the flow data were collected.
- *\ROM4WakeDeflection\ROMDerivation*
 - This folder contains the scripts and code required to extract, from the CDF data stored in *\ROM4WakeDeflection\InputFiles*, the ROMs discussed in this document.
- *\ROM4WakeDeflection\ROMVisualization*
 - This folder contains the scripts required to visualize POD modes and other results that can be obtained using ROMs. Some plots of these plots are: the wind flow evolution, the power output evolution, time-averaged error, POD mode shapes.
- *\ROM4WakeDeflection\Tests*
 - This folder has to contain the input files that are going to be used to test the ROM prediction. This folder also contains a demo case, i.e. an already computed ROM “Demo_ROM.mat” and an input file “Demo_yaw.mat”.

11.2.4 Performing a test run

A test run can be easily performed by typing, within MATLAB’s Command Window, the following command:

Run_ROM

For a successful run, the user will have to define the desired new inputs, as well as to load a previously derived ROM model. Additionally, some visualization features as, for example, the visualization of the time-averaged error between CFD-recorded flow and ROM-reconstructed flow, are only available if the user provides the CFD data required for such a comparison.

11.2.5 Setting up a simulation case

Setting up a new simulation case consists of a number of files that have to be created or modified. We will go through them one by one.

1. Perform CFD simulations of the desired wind farm.

As already explained in 11.1.3, the development of the models requires the user to provide outputs of CFD simulations that should be stored in \ROM4WakeDeflection\InputFiles. In details, the outputs should be stored as in the following:

- Within “\flowDATA” several folders should be created, i.e. one for every snapshot of physical quantities (flow field), whose name must be the time at which the data were sampled, as shown in Figure 11.1.

- 27.4783
- 27.4883
- 27.4983
- 27.5083
- 27.5183
- 27.5283
- 27.5383
- 27.5483
- 27.5583
- 27.5683
- 27.5783

Figure 11.1: Structure of the folders where flow data has to be saved.

Within each of these folders, several subfolders should again be created, each one containing the flow data sampled at grid points that belong to a specific plane. For example, Figure 11.2 shows a possible structure of subfolders that was used to store flow data mapped on a horizontal plane, passing through hub height, and one vertical plane, passing through the wind turbines tower axes.

Figure 11.2: Structure of the subfolders within each snapshot folder.

Within each subfolder, a file named “\U” has to be stored. This file must contain as many rows as the number of grid points; for every row, the stream-wise, the cross-wise and vertical velocity components have to be written in this order.

- Within “\input_outputDATA” a file named “input_output.dat” has to be stored. This file, shown in Figure 11.4, must contain as many rows as the number of snapshots. For every row, the first number must be the simulation time, while the other quantities should be the ones of interest, both inputs (e.g. upwind turbine yaw misalignment in column 4 in Figure 11.4) and outputs (e.g. upwind turbine power output in column 2 in Figure 11.4).

```
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.310874088373 0.172771013615 -0.011952410987)
(-0.209016446737 0.514261769408 0.167732675388)
(4.87161267576 0.161994857064 -0.0712219165816)
(4.87161267576 0.161994857064 -0.0712219165816)
(4.87161267576 0.161994857064 -0.0712219165816)
(4.87161267576 0.161994857064 -0.0712219165816)
(4.61589471689 -0.095194159234 -0.124983795712)
(4.85581114317 0.151713799394 -0.0910498187565)
(4.85581114317 0.151713799394 -0.0910498187565)
(4.85581114317 0.151713799394 -0.0910498187565)
(3.8850750573 0.260237766252 -0.0770518110577)
(3.8850750573 0.260237766252 -0.0770518110577)
(3.8850750573 0.260237766252 -0.0770518110577)
(3.8850750573 0.260237766252 -0.0770518110577)
```

Figure 11.3: CFD-generated flow data

	Time (s)	Power_0 (W)	Speed_0 (rpm)	Yaw_0 (deg)	Pitch1_0 (deg)	Pitch2_0 (deg)	Pitch3_0 (deg)
1	26.6987	22.21	827	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
2	26.6991	57.5189	827.33	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
3	26.6995	47.663	827.84	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
4	26.6999	36.4476	827.659	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
5	26.7003	35.5518	827.329	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
6	26.7007	43.6039	827.183	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
7	26.7011	50.3803	827.37	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
8	26.7015	48.8942	827.68	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
9	26.7019	43.4438	827.777	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
10	26.7023	41.06	827.644	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
11	26.7027	43.565	827.547	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
12	26.7031	47.3489	827.618	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
13	26.7035	47.3367	827.791	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
14	26.7039	44.8384	827.9	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
15	26.7043	43.499	827.868	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
16	26.7047	44.9006	827.841	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
17	26.7051	46.1143	827.903	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
18	26.7055	46.9347	828.015	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
19	26.7059	45.7803	828.085	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
20	26.7063	45.3115	828.139	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
21	26.7067	45.4848	828.145	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
22	26.7071	46.0263	828.212	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
23	26.7075	46.2632	828.279	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
24	26.7079	46.2205	828.349	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
25	26.7083	46.0745	828.406	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
26	26.7087	45.9825	828.461	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259
27	26.7091	46.1518	828.516	0	0.4259	0.4259	0.4259

Figure 11.4: CFD-generated input and output data

- Within “\coordinatesDATA” a number of subfolders should be created, each one for each plane used to collect the flow data (same names as in Figure 11.2). Each subfolder must contain a file called “coordinates.dat” that contains the coordinates of the grid points that belong to the corresponding plane.

The model-compression procedure explained in the section 11.1.4 must applied to raw CFD data in order to obtain the desired reduced-order model. To this end, it is required to excite the system by properly changing the desired turbine's yaw angle. To this aim, an APRBS (Amplitude-modulated Pseudo Random Binary Sequence) signal can be chosen. Such kind of signal is based on the PRBS signal, which is a deterministic approximation of white noise in discrete time. By mimicking white noise, the system is intended to be excited in all range of frequencies.

```

1
2 53237
3 (
4 (20.16 3.4733333333 0.8)
5 (20.1666666667 3.47 0.8)
6 (20.1733333333 3.4633333333 0.8)
7 (20.2466666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
8 (20.2533333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
9 (20.3266666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
10 (20.3333333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
11 (20.4133333333 3.4733333333 0.8)
12 (20.4066666667 3.4666666667 0.8)
13 (20.48 3.48 0.8)
14 (20.4866666667 3.4666666667 0.8)
15 (20.4866666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
16 (20.5666666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
17 (20.5733333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
18 (20.6466666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
19 (20.66 3.4666666667 0.8)
20 (20.6533333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
21 (20.6533333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
22 (20.66 3.4666666667 0.8)
23 (20.7333333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
24 (20.7266666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
25 (20.8066666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
26 (20.82 3.4666666667 0.8)
27 (20.8133333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
28 (20.8133333333 3.4666666667 0.8)
29 (20.82 3.4666666667 0.8)
30 (20.88 3.4733333333 0.8)
31 (20.8933333333 3.46 0.8)
32 (20.8866666667 3.4666666667 0.8)
33 (20.96 3.48 0.8)
34 (20.9666666667 3.4666666667 0.8)
35 (20.9666666667 3.4733333333 0.8)
36 (20.1666666667 3.5533333333 0.8)
37 (20.16 3.54 0.8)
38 (20.16 3.5466666667 0.8)
39 (20.2466666667 3.5533333333 0.8)
40 (20.2533333333 3.5466666667 0.8)
41 (20.32 3.5533333333 0.8)
42 (20.32 3.5466666667 0.8)
43 (20.3266666667 3.54 0.8)
44 (20.4066666667 3.5533333333 0.8)
45 (20.4133333333 3.5466666667 0.8)

```

Figure 11.5: Coordinates of the CFD grid points

The length of the training simulation should be set long enough to properly excite the system with the desired range of yaw misalignments, while considering the limitations dictated by computational costs. The amount of collected flow data should consist of three velocity components recorded at several grid points of the domain. We successfully obtained good reduced-order models by sampling the 3D flow field at points located on one horizontal plane, passing through hub height, and one

vertical plane, passing through the wind turbines tower axes. Other options, like sampling only the stream-wise speed or using different grid points, could also be effective.

As a general suggestion, the spatial and temporal resolutions of the stored CFD data should be comparable with those adopted within other works [9] [12].

2. Perform SVD decomposition and define the order of the model.

In the first place, the SVD decomposition must be performed, in order to obtain the projection subspace matrix. Successively, the ROM can be derived after specifying the desired order of the reduced model. Both these steps are executed by the following self-explanatory script “\ROM4WakeDeflection\Extract_ROM.m”.

```
%% EXTRACT ROM
% MATLAB script to extract ROMs from simulation data

%% Input/Output selection

% Positions, within the file
% './ROM4WakeDeflection/InputFiles/input_outputDATA/input_output', of the
% quantities that belongs to the model input vector
input_column_index = [4];

% Positions, within the file
% './ROM4WakeDeflection/InputFiles/input_outputDATA/input_output', of the
% quantities that belongs to the model output vector
output_column_index = [2,8];

%% Model order selection
% Order of the ROM
ROM_order = 20;

%% Reduced-order model computation
addpath('ROMDerivation')

[ROM]=ROM_computation(input_column_index,output_column_index,ROM_order);
% "ROM" is a structure array containing the output of MATLAB
% built-in function "ss()" of the Control System Toolbox and the
% projection subspace matrix (selection of the first "ROM_order" POD
% modes obtained through the SVD).
```

Figure 11.6 shows the stream-wise velocities, sampled on a horizontal plane at hub height, related to the first low-index POD modes, i.e. the most energetic ones, derived for a scaled wind turbine cluster. This last is composed by two G1 models, aligned with the prevailing wind flow direction, simulated in the 3D CFD environment that digitally copy the boundary layer wind tunnel of the Politecnico di Milano.

Figure 11.6: Low-index POD modes: stream-wise vel. comp. on horizontal plane XY.

The plots depict the principal spatial patterns of the flow. Since the simulation was performed for a varying upwind turbine yaw angle, the pattern observed, particularly for POM #1 and #2, is coherent with the physics, since it is clearly visible the flow deviation due to yaw-based wake deflection. Figure 11.7 shows for high-index, i.e. low energy, POD modes the stream-wise velocity component on a horizontal plane at hub height. As observed, no clear pattern is visible, while it is clearly observable the high-fluctuating spatial behavior of typical turbulent phenomena.

Figure 11.7: High-index POD modes: stream-wise vel. comp. on horizontal plane XY.

Additionally, the stream-wise velocity component is shown in Figure 11.8 and Figure 11.9, but for a vertical plane (XZ) passing through the centers of the two wind turbines.

Figure 11.8: Low-index POD modes: stream-wise vel. comp. on vertical plane XZ.

Figure 11.9: High-index POD modes: stream-wise vel. comp. on vertical plane XZ

It is worth mentioning that the ROM models, that can be produced by means of the provided MATLAB scripts, predict variations around an equilibrium point. This equilibrium point corresponds to an averaged flow and turbine powers at zero yaw angle. To determine the order r of the reduced-order model (i.e. the number of POD modes included, or the dimensions of the projection subspace) it is required to apply the procedure explained in 11.1.4 for a desired range of values of r . The output of each model should be compared, in terms of time-averaged error for both flow and power output, to the CFD data. However, not much difference is generally observed once the most energetic modes are already taken into account. Therefore, values of r around 15 to 25 POD modes should provide

satisfactory and time-efficient estimation for both wind turbine wake characteristics and power outputs, when compared to the high-fidelity CFD-simulated data.

3. ROM execution and visualization of the results

Once the ROM model has been derived, the following self-explicative script “\ROM4WakeDeflection\Run_ROM.m” can be used to evaluate the output of the model for given new inputs.

```
%% RUN ROM
% MATLAB script to evaluate the output of the ROM for given new inputs

%% Input definition
% Specify the name of the file, stored in ./ROM4WakeDeflection/Tests, where
% the time histories of the desired inputs are stored. The time step is
% assumed equal to the one of the data used to derive the ROM.
InputFileName='./ROM4WakeDeflection/Tests/Input.dat';

%% Load ROM
% Specify the name of the file, stored in ./ROM4WakeDeflection/Tests, where
% the ROM model is stored.
ROM_File_Name = './ROM4WakeDeflection/Tests/ROM.mat';

%% Execution of Reduced-order model
addpath('ROMDerivation')

Inputs=LoadInput(InputFileName);

[ROM]=LoadROM(ROM_File_Name);

[Flow_field,Outputs]=ROM_execution(ROM,Inputs);
% "Flow_field" contains the reconstructed flow field. "Outputs" contains
% the reconstructed wind turbines output quantities of interest.

%% Visualize ROM outputs
addpath('ROMVisualization')

ROM_Output_Visualization(Flow_field,Outputs)
```

11.3 Performing simulations

The presented control model requires, as input, data collected from high-fidelity CFD simulations, in the form of snapshot of physical quantities (flow field or wind turbine performances) sampled at a specific time step. Given the high computational resources required to perform such simulations, only the results concerning the scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case are presented.

11.3.1 Scaled wind farm (wind tunnel) case

The reduced-order models presented in this section is capable of reproducing the flow field and power of a scaled wind turbine cluster composed by two G1 models, aligned with the prevailing wind flow direction, simulated in the 3D CFD environment that digitally copy the boundary layer wind tunnel of the Politecnico di Milano [13].

The free stream flow average speed used was 5.7 m/s, with a turbulence intensity (TI) of about 6% at upwind turbine's hub height. Simulations were run with a time step of 0.0004 s, while data were collected in snapshots sampled every 0.01 s. Approximately 400.000 velocity values were recorded per snapshot, leading to around 50 Gb of text-formatted CFD data. Due to limited space availability within GitLab, these data could not be uploaded. However, the derived ROM is saved, as a MATLAB file "Demo_ROM.mat", within "\ROM4WakeDeflection\Tests".

The procedure explained in 11.1.4 was applied to the complete set of data, and a model of 17 POD modes was obtained. The flow comparisons, shown in Figure 11.10 and Figure 11.11, and the power output comparison, reported in Figure 11.12, highlight that the developed control-oriented model is capable of properly predicting the wake development, within a cluster of t scaled models, when yaw misalignment for wake deflection is adopted on the upstream wind turbine.

Figure 11.10: Flow comparison: CFD vs ROM , stream-wise vel. com. (both planes) at -15° yaw

Figure 11.11: Flow comparison: CFD vs ROM (stream-wise vel. com., both planes) at +25° yaw

Figure 11.12: Power output comparison: CFD vs ROM for yaw angle varying over time.

11.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, a reduced-order modelling technique is applied to obtain reduced-order models that could support the development of model-based wind farm control strategies, which would require very low computational cost for being real-time executed.

Emphasis has been placed in the study of control-oriented models that reproduce the phenomenon of wake steering. Results indicate that the proposed method estimates satisfactorily and time-efficiently both wind turbine wake characteristics and power outputs, when compared to high-fidelity CFD-simulated data, even in turbulent conditions. Regarding the flow predictions, proper deflection and development of the wake is mainly observed. With respect to the power outputs, the predictions are also accurate and correlated to the changes in upwind turbine's yaw angle.

Current and future perspectives of this work are focused on enhancing the model in order to cover a broader range of realistic scenarios for a successful coordinated control of wind turbines within a farm. Thus far, since the method used is based on system identification, ROMs are derived for a particular configuration (wind farm layout, wind speed, TI, etc.). If other conditions were desired, another CFD simulation would be, in principle, required. Therefore, the range of operating conditions is assumed as limited. To overcome this drawback, other authors successfully propose techniques like LPV control (Linear Parameter-Varying) [12], which will be investigated in the next future, as well as other possibilities currently under study.

11.5 References

1. F. Campagnolo, A. Croce, E. M. Nanos, V. Petrovic, J. Schreiber and C. L. Bottasso, "Wind tunnel testing of a closed-loop wake deflection controller for wind farm power maximization," in *Torque 2016*, Munich, Germany, 2016.
2. P. M. O. Gebraad, F. W. Teeuwisse, J. W. van Wingerden, P. A. Fleming, S. D. Ruben, J. R. Marden and L. Y. Pao, "Wind plant power optimization through yaw control using a parametric model for wake effects-a CFD simulation study," *Wind Energy*, 2014.
3. M. Churchfield and S. Lee, "NWTC design codes (SOWFA)," 2012.
4. M. Churchfield, S. Lee and P. Moriarty, "Overview of the simulator for wind farm application," NREL, 2012.
5. J. Jonkman and M. Buhl Jr, "FAST User's Guide," NREL, 2005.
6. J. Wang, S. Foley, E. M. Nanos, T. Yu, F. Campagnolo, C. L. Bottasso, A. Zanotti and A. Croce, "Numerical and Experimental Study of Wake Redirection Techniques in a Boundary Layer Wind Tunnel," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 854, p. 012048, 2017.

-
7. A. Fortes-Plaza, F. Campagnolo, C. L. Bottasso, J. Wang and C. Wang, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Paper submitted to TORQUE 2018).
 8. J. Proctor, S. Brunton and J. Kutz, *SIAM Journal on Applied Dynamical Systems*, vol. 15, pp. 142-161, 2016.
 9. J. Annoni, P. Gebraad and P. Seiler, *American Control Conference*, pp. 506-512, 2016.
 10. G. Kerschen and J.-C. Golinval, *Journal of Sound and vibration*, pp. 849-865, 2002.
 11. J. Schreiber, E. M. Nanos, F. Campagnolo and C. L. Bottasso, "Verification and Calibration of a Reduced Order Wind Farm Model by Wind Tunnel Experiments," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 854, p. 012041, 2017.
 12. J. Annoini and P. Seiler, "A method to construct reduced-order parameter-varying models," *International Journal of Robust and Nonlinear Control*, vol. 27, pp. 582-597, 2017.
 13. C. L. Bottasso, F. Campagnolo and V. Petrovic, "Wind tunnel testing of scaled wind turbine models: Beyond aerodynamics," *Journal of wind engineering and industrial aerodynamics*, vol. 127, pp. 11-28, 2014.

12 CONCLUSION

The objective of this document was to provide an overview of the different models that will be used in the CL-Windcon project, including documentation on their applicability and usage. Specifically, the various models were outlined, covering four different modelling classes:

1. Steady-state models
2. Control-oriented dynamic models
3. Medium-fidelity simulation models
4. High-fidelity simulation models

For each model the mathematical derivation has been reported, together with the main features and all the properties relevant for the CL-Windcon project. Information on model installation, configuration, set up and run are also reported. The models are currently ready to be used within the CL-Windcon project for both the synthesis (using models from the former two classes) and the validation (using models from the latter two classes) of supervisory wind farm control algorithms.

Connection to the remainder of the project

In the remainder of this project, the steady-state and control-oriented models will be used for controller synthesis. The medium-fidelity and high-fidelity simulation models will aid the controller synthesis by providing a testing platform, and a platform for the generation of high-fidelity simulation datasets to which the simplified models can be tuned. The high-fidelity simulation models may also help fill in the data gaps when we move towards the testing of the wind farm control solutions on experimental setups. Namely, in work package 3 (WP3), the advanced wind farm control algorithms will be tested in the wind tunnel at Politecnico di Milano on a scaled-down setup, and also on a subset of turbines inside the Sedini wind farm in Italy, owned by ENEL Green Power.

13 REFERENCES

Due to the size of the report and for clarity, each of Chapters 3 to 11 contains its own list of references. Please see the end of each corresponding chapter for the respective literature lists.

14 APPENDIX A

Appendix: Detailed mathematical description for SimWindFarm

Wind turbine

Simplified turbine model for Simulink

The turbines included in the toolbox are either the NREL5MW or DTU10MW virtual turbine. The models used are dynamic but relatively simple. The equations and parameters are described in details below.

The turbine simulation model used in SimWindFarm is a simplified aeroelastic model based on lookup tables for the aerodynamics (C_P , C_T), a simple 3rd order drive train model, a 1st order generator model, 1st order pitch actuator, and a 2nd order tower dynamics.

The turbines NREL5MW are controlled using the control strategy from Jonkman et al. [2009], which includes a simplified start up procedure and pitch control for full load operation. The turbine DTU10MW has a similar controller but with parameters adapted to DTU10MW. The DTU10MWCLWC turbine uses the OpenDiscon controller <https://github.com/ielorza/OpenDiscon> IK4-IKERLAN [2017].

Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the turbine model, with inputs being the wind speed at the nacelle, the average wind speed over the rotor area (effective wind speed), and the power reference supplied by the farm controller. The outputs available to the farm controller are produced power, measured generator speed, nacelle wind speed, and blade pitch angle.

Figure 1: Top level structure of SWF as illustrated by the Simulink diagram.

The variables used in the turbine model are shown in table `tab:Variables`.

Variable	Description	unit
Ω	rotor speed	rad/s
ω	generator speed	rad/s
β	pitch angle	degrees
M_{shaft}	main shaft torque	Nm
M_{gen}	generator torque	Nm
F_{tow}	tower thrust	N
P_{dem}	power demand	W
P_{ref}	generator power reference	W
β_{ref}	pitch angle reference	degrees
V_{nac}	nacelle wind speed	m/s
V_{rot}	average wind speed over the rotor	m/s
V_E	effective wind speed	m/s
V_{meas}	measured wind speed	m/s
β_{meas}	measured pitch angle	degrees
P_{meas}	measured produced power	W
ω_{meas}	measured generator speed	rad/s

Aerodynamics

The aerodynamics of the turbine can be described using two static relationships,

$$M_{shaft} = \frac{1}{2} v_{rot}^3 \rho A C_P(\lambda, \beta) \Omega^{-1}$$

$$F_{tow} = \frac{1}{2} v_{rot}^2 \rho A C_T(\lambda, \beta)$$

where C_P and C_T are two look-up tables derived from the geometry of the blades with inputs tip speed ration ($\lambda = R\Omega/v_{rot}$) and pitch angle β . The parameters are air density ρ , and rotor disc area, A .

Drive Train

The 3rd order drive train model is based on two rotating shafts connected through a gearbox with torsion spring constant K_{shaft} , viscous friction B_{shaft} , and gear ration N .

$$\dot{\Omega} = \frac{1}{I_{rot}} \left(M_{shaft} - \phi K_{shaft} - \dot{\phi} B_{shaft} \right)$$

$$\dot{\omega} = \frac{1}{I_{gen}} \left(-M_{gen} + \frac{1}{N} (\phi K_{shaft} + \dot{\phi} B_{shaft}) \right)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \Omega - \frac{1}{N} \omega$$

where ϕ is the shaft torsion angle and I_{gen}, I_{rot} are the inertias of the generator and rotor respectively.

Generator

In the baseline NREL 5MW turbine there is no generator model, but a simple 1st order model is included in this benchmark, with input P_{ref} and time constant τ_{gen} .

$$\dot{M}_{gen} = \frac{1}{\tau_{gen}} \left(\frac{P_{ref}}{\omega} - M_{gen} \right)$$

Notice that the baseline turbine assumes a torque reference, but a power reference is used here instead.

Tower

The tower deflection, z , is modeled as a spring-damper system with spring constant K_{tow} and damping B_{tow} .

$$\ddot{z} = \frac{1}{m_{tow}} (F_{tow} - K_{tow}z - B_{tow}\dot{z})$$

Pitch Servo

The pitch actuator does not use the NREL model which is a spring-damper system and not used in their FAST simulation. Instead a second order system with a time constant of τ_{β} and input delay λ from input u_{β} to pitch rate $\dot{\beta}$ is used.

The actuator is controlled by a proportional regulator with constant K_{beta} resulting in a pitch servo.

$$\ddot{\beta} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\beta}} (u_{\beta}^{\lambda} - \dot{\beta})$$

$$u_{\beta} = K_{\beta} (\beta_{ref} - \beta_{meas})$$

Control

Notice that the different turbines in the Simulink SimWindFarm turbine library can have different controllers. Currently (<2018-01-18 Thu>) NREL5MW and DTU10MW has the NREL5MW type controller explained below while the DTU10MWCLWC has the IK4-IKERLAN controller IK4-IKERLAN [2017].

Control based on NREL5MW

The control strategy for the NREL5MW is divided into two regions; 1) partial load and 2) full load.

In region 1) the control is a simple lookup-table with generator speed as input and generator power reference as output. The blade pitch is kept constant at 0, see figure 2 below.

In region 2) the generator power reference is kept constant at the rated power while the rotor speed is controlled using the blade pitch angle, by a gain scheduled PI controller.

Figure 2: Turbine Pitch Control Regions.

The gain scheduled PI controller is shown in the equation below, and the gains are based on linearization of the power production sensitivity to blade pitch angle.

$$\beta_{ref} = K_P(\beta)\omega_{err} + K_I(\beta) \int_0^t \omega_{err}$$

$$K_{P/I}(\beta) = K_{P/I,0} \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_2 + \beta}$$

where $\omega_{err} = \omega_{rated} - \omega$, and $K_{P/I}$ are the proportional and integral gains, $K_{P/I,0}$ is the base gain at $\beta = 0^\circ$ and β_2 is the pitch angle where the pitch sensitivity is doubled.

The controller presented in Jonkman et al. [2009] always operates at full power rating and in order to be able to derate the turbine the control strategy has been altered slightly by letting the dynamic power rating change the transition point between region 1 and region 2.

Wind and wake part

Wind field modelling

The wind simulation and modelling can be divided into an ambient field model, which describes the wind field if no turbines were present and a wake model which describes the turbines effect on the ambient wind field. The following description is relevant for both SimWindFarm, expect where stated otherwise, i.e., where there are differences a subsection titled SWF Taylor will describe the original version and SWF No Taylor will describe the new version.

SWF Taylor

In this version of SWF both ambient field model and wake model assume Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis for inviscid flow Davidson [2004] to be true. This greatly simplifies the effort of generating an ambient wind field, and provides relatively simple equations for the wake effect models.

SWF No Taylor

In this version of SWF the wake model assumes Taylor’s frozen turbulence hypothesis for inviscid flow Davidson [2004] to be true. This assumption is, however, not made in the ambient wind field model. The coherence between two points separated by a distance downwind will be one if Taylor’s frozen turbulence hypothesis is assumed, i.e., the wind at these points will be identical except for a time delay. This is not realistic, which is the reason for introducing a version without the assumption.

Ambient wind field

The ambient wind in a wind farm is usually described by spectral matrices describing the wind speed variation at a number of points in the wind farm and their relation using the method described in Veers [1988]. The wind model assumes a constant mean wind speed and a zero lateral mean wind speed, i.e. the mean wind direction is constant in the longitudinal direction.

- SWF Taylor Due to the frozen turbulence assumption in this version it is only necessary to simulate stochastic processes in the first line in the lateral direction in the park. These velocities are then assumed to travel with the average wind speed in the longitudinal direction. In this way the wind speeds at downwind grid points will eventually be generated.
- SWF No Taylor lateral wind component, more or less, is only used for wake meandering and is therefore generated using Taylor - The lateral component, which is the largest part of wind turbines see, is generated for x point at each turbine according to the spectrum described next. where the lateral wind is implemented as a number of stochastic processes, one for each point.

Turbulence Spectrum

The wind field is generated according to the recommendations in IEC 61400-3 concerning offshore turbines, which state that for non-site specific wind conditions the parameter values in IEC 61400-1 (2005) Commission [2005] can be used. The spectrum used is the Kaimal spectrum

$$S_k(f) = \sigma_k^2 \frac{4 \frac{L_k}{U}}{(1 + 6f \frac{L_k}{U})^{\frac{5}{3}}}$$

where L_k is velocity component integral scale parameter, f is the frequency in Hertz, k denotes the velocity component, U is the hub height mean wind speed and σ_k is the variance determined by the turbulence intensity, T_i , given by [Commission, 2005, P. 24, eqn. (11)]

$$\sigma_x = T_i \left(\frac{3}{4}U + 5.6 \right)$$

$$\sigma_y = 0.8\sigma_x$$

Notice that the above relation between σ_x and T_i results in $T_i \neq \sigma_x/U$ but rather

$$\frac{\sigma_x}{U} = T_i \left(\frac{3}{4} + \frac{5.6}{U} \right)$$

The coherence between two point separated by distance l is given as

$$C_k(f) = e^{-c_k f \frac{l}{U}}$$

where c_k is the coherence parameter, which depends on the separation direction. In SWF three coherence parameters are used, c_{xx} is used for the coherence of longitudinal wind speed component between points separated by a longitudinal distance, c_{xy} is used for the coherence of longitudinal wind speed component between points separated by a lateral distance, and c_{yy} is used for the coherence of lateral wind speed component between points separated by a lateral distance.

As the hub height is assumed to be above 60m then $L_x = 340.2$ and $L_y = 113.4$ and according to Kristensen and Jensen [1979] c_{xy} and c_{yy} can be set to 7.1 and 4.2 respectively.

- SWF Taylor: In this version only c_{xy} and c_{yy} is needed for wind generation as Taylor's frozen turbulence is assumed and only point separated by a lateral displacement is needed. Notice that the simple wind field model using the frozen turbulence assumption has a coherence of 1 in the longitudinal direction, which does not conform to IEC 61400-1, and care should thus be taken not to design controllers that rely on this fact.
- SWF No Taylor: Generating wind in this version is based on Sørensen et al. [2002]. The coherence between each turbine is needed and as turbines need not be displaced only in the lateral or longitudinal direction the following equation is used

$$c_{rc}(\alpha) = \sqrt{(c_{xx} \cos \alpha)^2 + (c_{xy} \sin \alpha)^2}$$

where α is the angle between wind direction and a line between the two turbine r and turbine c . Furthermore, the delay from turbine to turbine is needed, which can be calculated as

$$\tau_{rc} = \frac{d_{rc} \cos \alpha}{U_0}$$

where d is the distance between turbines, α the angle between turbines, and U_0 is the mean wind speed. Now the cross spectrum between turbines can be found from

$$S_{rc}(f) = C_{rc}(f) \sqrt{S_{rr}(f) S_{cc}(f)} \exp(-j2\pi f \tau_{rc})$$

where S_{rc} is the cross spectrum between turbine r and turbine c , C_{rc} is the coherence, S_{rr} is the auto spectrum at turbine r , S_{cc} is the auto spectrum at turbine c , and τ_{rc} is the time delay from turbine r to turbine c .

Wake effects

It has been shown in Larsen et al. [2008] that a good approximation of the meandering is to consider the wake center as a passive tracer which moves downwind with the mean wind speed. It is, therefore, possible to rank turbines relative to each other as being either downwind or upwind.

For wake effect calculations at a given turbine it is only necessary to consider upwind turbines, and as this relationship is fixed it considerably simplifies the calculations.

SWF considers three wake effects; deficit, expansion and center, where wake deficit is a measure of the decrease in downwind wind speed, wake expansion describes the size of the downwind area affected by the wake and wake center defines the lateral position (meandering) of the wake area, see the figure below and Larsen et al. [2008]. The wake effects are illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Wind turbine wake illustration.

Expressions for wake deficit, center and expansion was developed in Frandsen et al. [2006], Jensen [1983]. The wake center, expansion and deficit at a given point p downwind from a turbine at time t_1 is defined by the wind field at the turbine and its coefficient of thrust at the time of tracer release, t_0 ,

$$t_0 = t_1 - \frac{d}{U}$$

where d is the longitudinal distance between the upwind turbine and p .

Wake Expansion

- SWF Taylor: In this version of SWF in particular we use the equation below from Jensen [1983] to calculate the wake expansion radius, which is a simplified model independent of C_T .

$$e_i(d) = 2R\sqrt{1 + \frac{d}{4R}} = \sqrt{4R^2 + dR},$$

where R is the rotor radius.

- SWF No Taylor: In this version of SWF, we use the equation below from Frandsen et al.

[2006] to calculate the wake expansion (radius of the wake, $e_i(d)$)

$$e_i(d) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\beta^{\frac{k}{2}} + \alpha \frac{d}{D_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{k}} D_0,$$

where D_0 is the rotor diameter, α and k are parameters which here are set to 0.5 and 2, respectively. Furthermore,

$$\beta = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{2\sqrt{1 - C_T}}.$$

Wake Center

The wake center is computed as a passive tracer, such that the center at time t_k is a function of the center at time t_{k-1} and the average lateral wind speed, over the wake area,

$$\begin{aligned} W_i(d, t_{k-1}) &= \{(x, y) | x = d \wedge y \in W_y\} \\ W_y &= [w_i(d, t_{k-1}) - e_i(d); w_i(d, t_{k-1}) + e_i(d)] \\ w_i(d, t_k) &= w_i(d, t_{k-1}) + \bar{v}_{y,i}(d, W_i(d, t_{k-1})) \end{aligned}$$

where $w_i(d, t_k)$ is the wake center at time k , $W_i(d, t_{k-1})$ is the wake area distance d from the turbine at time t_{k-1} and $\bar{v}_{y,i}(d, W_i(d, t_{k-1}))$ is the average lateral wind speed over the wake area.

Wake Deficit

- SWF Taylor: The deficit from turbine i at distance d can according to Jensen [1983] be approximated as

$$dU_i(d) = \frac{U(d)}{U_0} = 1 - 2a_i(t_0) \left(\frac{R}{R + \kappa d} \right)^2$$

where dU_i is the wind deficit, $\kappa = 0.1$, $U(d)$ is the wind speed distance d down wind, U_0 is the ambient wind speed. a_i is the induction factor of turbine i at time t_0 and R is the radius of the rotor.

Instead of using the induction factor, a more realistic result is obtained by using the simulated thrust coefficient. The thrust coefficient is given by

$$C_T = 4a_i(1 - a_i)$$

According to Frandsen et al. [2006], the above expressions can be approximated by

$$dU_i(d) \approx 1 - \frac{1}{2} C_{T,i}(t_0) \left(1 + \frac{d}{4R} \right)^{-1}$$

where $C_{T,i}(t_0)$ is the coefficient of thrust of turbine i at time t_0 .

- SWF No Taylor: In this version of SWF the deficit behind a single turbine is given by the equation below from Frandsen et al. [2006]

$$c = \frac{U(d)}{U_0} \approx 1 - \frac{C_T}{2} \frac{D_0^2}{D^2(d)}$$

where $U(d)$ is the wind speed distance d down wind, U_0 is the ambient wind speed, C_T is the thrust coefficient, D_0 is the rotor diameter, and $D(d)$ is the wake diameter distance d down wind.

Wake Merging

- SWF Taylor: Using equations the equations for meandering, expansion and deficit it is possible to calculate the wake contributions for each turbine and this enables us to calculate the actual wind speed at any point in the farm as

$$v_x(x, y) = u_x(x, y) \prod_{i \in I} a_i(d_i)$$

where I contains the indices of all turbines where the point (x, y) is in its wake area, $y \in W_i(x - P_{x,i})$, with $P_{x,i}$ being the longitudinal position of the i 'th turbine.

- SWF No Taylor: In this version of SWF a slightly different approach is taken. In Frandsen et al. [2006] a row of turbines is considered and the deficit at turbine $n + 1$ can be described as

$$c_{n+1} = 1 - \left(\frac{D_n^2}{D_{n+1}^2} (1 - c_n) + \frac{C_{T_n}}{2} \frac{D_R^2}{D_{n+1}^2} c_n \right)$$

where $c_{n+1} = U_{n+1}/U_0$ is the deficit at turbine $n + 1$, D_n is the wake diameter at turbine n , D_{n+1} is the diameter at turbine $n + 1$, c_n is the deficit at turbine n , C_{T_n} is the thrust coefficient of turbine n and D_R is the diameter of the rotor.

Model of Added Turbulence Intensity

- SWF No Taylor: The model of added turbulence intensity which is used here is the one suggested in the IEC 61400-1 Commission [2014] which comes from Frandsen [2007] and is given by

$$I_{add,j} = \frac{\sigma_{add,j}}{U_j} = \frac{1}{1.5 + 0.8 \frac{s_{ij}}{\sqrt{C_{T,i}}}}$$

where $\sigma_{add,j}$ is the added standard deviation in the wind field at the j 'th WT which is in wake; U_j is the effective wind speed at the j 'th WT; s_{ij} is the spacing in rotor diameters between the wake generating WT and the WT in wake; $C_{T,i}$ is the thrust coefficient of the wake generating WT.

References

- I. E. Commission. International standard 61400-1 - wind turbines. Technical report, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2005.

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- I. E. Commission. 61400-1 cd iec:2014(e) draft. Technical report, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2014.
- P. A. Davidson. *Turbulence*. Oxford University Press, 2004.
- S. Frandsen, R. Barthelmie, S. Pryor, O. Rathmann, S. Larsen, and J. Højstrup. Analytical modelling of wind speed deficit in large offshore wind farms. *Wind Energy*, 9:39–53, 2006.
- S. T. Frandsen. Turbulence and turbulence-generated structural loading in wind turbine clusters. Technical report, Risø National Laboratory, 2007. Danish Doctor Technices Thesis Risø-R-1188(EN).
- IK4-IKERLAN. Open source implementation of the legacy gbladed external controller interface. Internet <https://github.com/ielorza/OpenDiscon>, 2017.
- N. Jensen. A note on wind generator interaction. Technical Report ris-m-2411, Risø National Laboratory, 1983.
- J. Jonkman, S. Butterfield, W. Musial, and G. Scott. Definition of a 5-mw reference wind turbine for offshore system development. Technical Report NREL/TP-500-38060, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 1617 Cole Boulevard, Golden, Colorado, USA, 2009.
- L. Kristensen and N. O. Jensen. Lateral coherence in isotropic turbulence and in the natural wind. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 17:353–373, 1979. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00117924>.
- G. C. Larsen, H. A. Madsen, K. Thomsen, and T. J. Larsen. Wake meandering: A pragmatic approach. *Wind Energy*, 11:377–395, 2008.
- P. Sørensen, A. D. Hansen, P. André, and C. Rosas. Wind models for simulation of power fluctuations from wind farms. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 90:1381–1402, 2002.
- P. S. Veers. Three-dimensional wind simulation. Technical Report SAND88-0152 UC-261, Sandia National Laboratories, 1988.